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International Studies in Computational Linguistics (ISCL)

Master thesis

Refinement of Large Language Models by Domain Specialization, using Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback

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Tübingen, July 30, 2024

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Abbreviations

AGS	Atmospheric and Geospace Sciences
AI	Artificial Intelligence
APE	Automatic Prompt Engineer
APE	Advanced Placement Examinations
API	Application Programming Interface
ASR	Attack Success Rate
BERT	Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers
BOS	Beginning Of Sequence
CoT	Chain of Thought
DRL	Deep Reinforcement Learning
EAR	Earth Sciences
EKG	Enterprise Knowledge Graph
EOS	End Of Sequence
FT	Fine-Tuning
GPT	Generative pre-trained transformers
GIS	Geographic Information System
GAKG	Geoscience Academic Knowledge Graphs
HPC	High-Performance Computing
HTML	Hyper Text Markup Language
IR	Information Retrieval
ISKO	International Society for Knowledge Organization
KG	Knowledge Graph
KL	Kullback-Leibler
LLM	Large Language Model
LoRA	Low-rank adaptation
MC	Multiple Choice (NLP Task)
MDP	Markov Decision Process
NER	Named Entity Recognition (NLP Task)
NLI	Natural Language Inference
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NPEE	National Postgraduate Entrance Exam
OCE	Ocean Sciences
OOD	out-of-distribution

OOM	out-of-memory
PEFT	Parameter Efficient Finetuning
PHI	Personal Health Information
PLM	Pre-Trained Language Model
PoS	Part-of-Speech Tagging (NLP Task)
PPO	Proximal Policy Optimization
PT	Pre-Training
PTST	Pure Tuning, Safe Testing
QA	Question Answering (NLP Task)
QLoRA	Quantized Low-rank adaptation
RL	Reinforcement Learning
RLHF	Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback
RM	Reward Model
SFT	Supervised Fine-Tuning
SOTA	State of the art
SVD	Singular Value Decomposition
SVFT	Singular Value Fine-Tuning
SWA	Stochastic Weight Averaging
TF	True-False questions (NLP Task)
UTF	Unified Time Framework

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1 Introduction

Advanced Large Language Models (LLMs) have revolutionized the field of Natural Language Processing (NLP). They offer a valuable base and show great potential, due to their ability to be adapted to a wide range of different tasks and topics. Common NLP tasks involve text preprocessing tasks, such as Part-of-Speech (PoS) Tagging; classification tasks, such as sentiment analysis; text-to-text generation tasks, such as machine translation; or information retrieval tasks, such as question answering (QA) [57].

Especially dialogue systems became very prominent with the release of *ChatGPT* since they can help users in everyday real-world scenarios by providing information or performing a particular task. With the growing prominence and expertise for the vast amount of functions and topics models like *ChatGPT* can perform, the need for LLMs with more in-depth knowledge and qualifications for certain domains arose [92]. However, using these models to tackle complex issues within specialized domains still poses several challenges. These challenges include but are not limited to the "diverse nature of domain information, the complexity of domain expertise, the distinctiveness of domain goals, and the multifaceted set of restrictions present in each application area." [71, p. 1] Differences in social, cultural, or religious conventions and ethical guidelines, can become an obstacle when implementing LLMs in various domain contexts.

The challenges in refining an LLM to become an overall expert for a specific domain caused a shift towards training LLMs for narrow tasks only. Although initial efforts have been made to develop domain-specialized general-purpose models, several of the research on enriching LLMs with expert knowledge focuses on specific tasks, such as predicting the weather for a particular region in Europe [141]. However, tasks-specific models are inflexible and limited to predefined tasks, which prevents them from being widely used.

However, research centered around refining general-purpose LLMs to become domain-specialized dialogue systems has emerged in the last two years. But up to now, the results these domain-specialized models produce still leave room for improvement, e.g. accuracy scores for closed QA-tasks of about 20-40% are achieved on average [70].

This thesis aims to contribute to the field of domain specialization for LLMs. In particular, a new approach to refining a general-purpose open-source LLM in the geoscience domain is tested. The geoscience domain serves as an example throughout this thesis; however, the aim is to propose a new approach for domain specialization that is generalizable and, therefore, applicable to all kinds of domains in the future. The potential of using Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (RLHF) for domain specialization has been only explored marginally yet [71]. This is why this thesis tries to adapt an LLM to the geoscience domain with the help of RLHF. Further, combining different refinement strategies has proved promising in related works, which is why the process of RLHF will be enriched by prompt crafting. Specifically, prompt crafting will be performed before RLHF, which is expected to enhance RLHF training outcomes by using the optimized prompts for training the LLM.

The approach of domain specialization via RLHF is explained throughout 11 Chapters within this thesis. First, Chapter 2 defines the concepts and provides an overview of previously published literature in prompt crafting, RLHF, including Supervised Fine-Tuning (SFT), and domain specialization. Chapter 3 further elaborates on the objectives of this thesis. Next, in Chapter 4, the geoscience domain is defined, which serves as an example throughout the process. Chapter 5 describes the process of choosing a general-purpose LLM that serves as the model for this investigation. Chapters 6 to 8 discuss the essential steps of specializing an LLM in the geoscience domain. Besides a description of the data and details of the technical implementation, first insights into the potential outcomes of prompt crafting (6), SFT (7) as well as RLHF (8) are given. Chapter 9 provides an extensive qualitative and quantitative evaluation of the model, whereas Chapter 10 further discusses these findings. Lastly, Chapter 11 contains the conclusion.

The code and all additional files, such as human evaluation results, are made available in the GitHub repository of this thesis. Furthermore, all models, i.e. the geoscience-specialized models after SFT and after RLHF, as well as the fine-tuned Reward Model used during RLHF, have been uploaded to the author's Huggingface profile.

2 Theoretical Background

This chapter provides the theoretical background knowledge that underpins this work. Four primary approaches are discussed: Prompt Crafting (Section 2.1), Supervised-Fine Tuning (Section 2.2), Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (Section 2.3), and Domain Specialization (Section 2.4).

All four approaches are presented in the context of optimizing and adapting LLMs. LLMs receive input in text that serves as a base for understanding and processing the context. An additional textual sentence, a prompt, is often included to specify and explain the task the LLM should perform. For instance, the prompt "Summarize the key facts contained in the following passage:" could proceed with the input passage. The LLM then generates an output in the form of text by predicting the next token in the response to the input. LLMs are commonly used for sentiment classification, summary generation, or machine translation [71, p. 5].

Each of the four approaches aims at refining the ability of an LLM to provide textual output according to the implementation goal. The following chapters provide definitions for these approaches and explain the main concepts. These introductions try to give a broad overview.

Delving deeper into the current research, some state-of-the-art studies are presented and discussed for each approach. The presented works are not exhaustive and serve only as an exemplary insight into the topics currently addressed in the research. Furthermore, the literature review mainly focuses on aspects of the technical implementation only. It leaves out factors such as the collection of data and the evaluation strategies after the training process is completed. Lastly, challenges and limitations are discussed for each approach.

2.1 Prompting Crafting

In this section, the concept of prompt crafting is presented. First, prompting and prompt crafting are defined in Subsection 2.1.1. Following this definition, current state-of-the-art studies in prompt crafting are discussed in Subsection 2.1.2, including manual and automated approaches. Lastly, some of the vital challenges encountered when designing prompts are addressed in Subsection 2.1.3.

2.1.1 Definitions & Concepts

Prompting is a crucial concept in the realm of NLP, mainly when querying LLMs. At its core, prompting addresses the question of how it is possible to get LLMs to do what the user intends. Therefore, the prompting field has gained attention due to its ability to effectively use pre-trained LLMs for various tasks without requiring extensive fine-tuning [73, p. 3].

In current literature, different terms related to prompting are used interchangeably, e.g., prompt engineering, tuning, prompt crafting, and prompt design. This section defines the key concepts of prompting and prompt crafting. The explanations are mainly based on the survey *Pre-train, Prompt, and Predict: A Systematic Survey of Prompting Methods in Natural Language Processing* by Liu et al. [73].

The term *prompting* refers to selecting the most suitable prompt that manipulates the pre-trained LLM to generate the desired output [73, p. 3]. Prompts can either be an instruction in natural language that provides context to guide the model during the output generation or learned vector representations that activate the model's base knowledge relevant to answering the question [107, p. 1].

Sahoo et al. [107, p.1] define prompting as follows: "Rather than updating the model parameters, prompts allow seamless integration of pre-trained models into downstream tasks by eliciting desired model behaviors solely based on the given prompt." Lester, Al-Rfou, and Constant [63, p. 2] describe prompting as providing extra information for the model within the prompt to guide the model during the output generation. Zhou et al. [147, p.3] further emphasize the natural and intuitive nature of prompting, making it easier for users to interact with LLMs more efficiently. The overall goal of prompting is to retrieve the knowledge a model has gained during pre-training [116, p. 4229]

Prompt crafting, *prompt design*, and *prompt engineering* are terms used interchangeably to describe structuring input texts for LLMs. In this thesis, the term *prompt crafting* will be used.

Prompt crafting is motivated by the observation that plain language prompts may not yield the intended outcomes, although the model can produce this outcome using a different input prompt. This is why users often need to test various prompts to achieve the desired behavior from the models [147, p. 1]. However, what started as the practice of editing prompts to guide LLMs during the generation of outputs became a structured research area with its methodologies and best practices [19, p. 2].

Chen et al. [19, p. 1] describe prompt crafting as "a technique integral to optimizing the efficacy of LLMs." Hou et al. [45, p. 22] highlight that prompt crafting is based on the careful design of prompts. These prompts serve two different purposes. On one side, they guide LLMs toward generating desired outputs; on the other, they serve as an interface to extract the prompt-related knowledge contained in these models [45, p. 22]. Prompt crafting includes various prompt optimization techniques, from more fundamental methods like role-prompting [114] to more advanced approaches like chain-of-thought prompting [134].

Compared to Fine-Tuning, prompt crafting has several benefits for real-world tasks. Firstly, prompt crafting can yield higher accuracy than fine-tuning when data is limited, making it a valuable solution for resource-constrained tasks and domains [116]. Secondly, prompt crafting reduces the cost and complexity when multiple NLP should be solved with the same model; during Fine-Tuning, separate language model checkpoints for every task should be saved and deployed simultaneously. Using prompt crafting, only the prompts for each task need to be stored, and these prompts can be used to query the same pre-trained model [116, 4229f.]. Thirdly, using suitable prompts helps to reduce hallucinations within the generated outputs [19, 15]. However, it is essential to note that prompt crafting "has seen little **systematic** research [...]" and for users remains mostly a **trial and error process**" [28, p. 3].

2.1.2 State of the Art

Prompt crafting has gained significant attention in recent research due to its impact on LLMs' performance. A systematic review by Sahoo et al. [107] suggests at least 29 different prompt crafting techniques, all of which were introduced between 2022 and 2023. More detailed overviews of the latest prompt crafting techniques for LLMs can be found in [107] and [73].

The current research differentiates between **manually** designing prompts and **automatically** designing prompts.

Manual prompt crafting

Looking at the manual prompt crafting from a user's perspective reveals that creating effective prompts remains largely a trial-and-error process [28]. However, some studies describe systematic approaches, on how a prompt can be optimized manually.

Unambiguous and specific instructions: Chen et al. [19, p. 3] emphasize the importance of clear, concise, and unambiguous instructions to help the model generate precise and relevant outputs. Formulating too broad or vague prompts forces the LLMs to interpret which output is desired and the answer therefore remains unspecific as well. Specifying the desired outcome can guide the model towards producing the intended result [95].

Role promoting: Another strategy is role promoting, where you assign a particular role to the model, like a helpful assistant or an expert [114]. For example, "if the model is prompted to act as a historian, it is more likely to provide a detailed and contextually accurate response when asked about a historical event" [19, 4f.] The role helps the model to better activate its prompt-specific knowledge [95].

Use of triple quotes: Triple quotes are used to separate different parts of a prompt or encapsulate multi-line strings. This helps to sharpen the model's understanding of complex prompts containing multiple components or embedded quotes [19]. An example would be *Summarize the text delimited by triple quotes with a haiku.* `"""insert text here"""` [95].

One-shot vs. few-shot prompting: One-shot prompting describes the strategy of presenting a single example to the model to learn from, whereas few-shot uses multiple examples as a guideline for the model [19, p. 5]. The primary goal of inserting examples in the prompt is not necessarily to teach the model a new task but to help it recall previously learned concepts [19, p. 5]. An example of a regular and a one-shot prompt can be found in Figure 2.1.

Long context: According to Beltagy, Peters, and Cohan [11] and Khandelwal et al. [56], providing more extended context in prompts can lead to superior text outputs. However, Wu, Terry, and Cai [140] state that conflicts can arise whenever the instructions are not stated clearly within a long context body. Therefore, O'Connor and Andreas [93, p. 9] have investigated the extent to which LLMs profit from the structural and lexical information within long contexts. They provide a framework to determine how much information from the input context can actively be used by the model in the generation process. Their results suggest that it is more important to provide an extended context than what syntactic and propositional structure the content is of [93, p. 1].

Fig. 4 Comparison of standard prompt and one-shot prompt.

Figure 2.1: Comparison of standard prompt and one-shot prompt [19, p. 6]

Word order: Lu et al. [78] discovered that word order impacts generated outcomes: "For the same prompt, the order in which samples are provided can make the difference between state-of-the-art and random performance." [78, p. 8] However, it is essential to note that order preferences vary across LLMs models [78, p. 3].

Dividing a complex task into smaller tasks: Zhou et al. [146, p. 9] proposed a strategy where a "prompt must be designed to demonstrate decomposition for [...] problems in order to achieve optimal performance". Figure 2.2 shows an example of such a prompt. The division into smaller tasks helps the model to solve more complex tasks since LLMs often perform poorly whenever a task needs generalization [146, p. 1]. OpenAI [95] also advises splitting complex tasks into simpler subtasks to achieve better performance.

Q: Elsa has 5 apples. Anna has 2 more apples than Elsa. How many apples do they have together?
 A: Let's break down this problem: 1. How many apples does Anna have? 2. How many apples do they have together?

1. Anna has 2 more apples than Elsa. So Anna has $2 + 5 = 7$ apples.
2. Elsa and Anna have $5 + 7 = 12$ apples together.

The answer is: 12.

Figure 2.2: Example of prompt decomposition for mathematical prompts [146, p. 7]

Using predefined templates: Sanh et al. [108] conducted a study investigating whether multitask learning could achieve zero-shot generalization. They aimed to create a system capable of converting any natural language task into a human-readable format. As part of their work, they provide a comprehensive list of target and input prompt templates for 61 datasets covering 13 distinct NLP tasks.

In summary, some best practices and techniques aimed at enhancing LLM performance are established in manual prompt crafting. However, following these established guidelines does not necessarily improve the model's outputs since each LLM has different input prompt preferences. The process of manual prompt crafting still relies on trial and error.

Automatic prompt crafting

Researchers have explored various ways to automate designing effective prompts for LLMs, which aim at reducing the effort and time needed to manually optimize the input prompts [107, p. 5]. Some of the current works are presented in the following paragraphs.

The Automatic Prompt Engineer (APE) is a solution introduced by [147]. It uses an LLM to dynamically generate and select a prompt that enhances the performance of this LLM for a specific task. Figure 2.3 (a) illustrates the workflow of APE. An LLM generates an instruction prompt based on output demonstrations as a first step. Secondly, the same model is asked to create multiple instruction candidates either through inference directly or via a recursive process based on semantic similarity. Thirdly, the target model is used to produce answers for generated instructions. Lastly, the generated outputs are evaluated, and the most suitable instruction is chosen based on evaluation scores [147, p. 2]. 2.3 (b) shows that APE nearly matches or surpasses human performance in prompt crafting. Moreover, it also proved helpful in maintaining truthfulness and informativeness during the output generation process [147, p. 1]. Sahoo et al. [107, p. 5] describe APE as a "breakthrough in automatic prompt engineering."

Other prominent research includes Liu et al. [72]'s method of using sentence embeddings to generate prompt alternatives to compare the model's performance. Shin et al. [116] propose *AutoPrompt*. AutoPrompt uses an LLM to create prompts based on a gradient-guided search for multiple tasks. They show that reformulating

Figure 2.3: Automatic Prompt Engineer (APE) workflow and evaluation in comparison to human prompting skills [147, p. 2]

a prompt such that it becomes a different type of task, e.g., as a fill-in-the-blanks problem, can also help to guide the model to activate its prompt-specific knowledge.

Betz, Richardson, and Voigt [13] try to automatize prompt crafting with the help of the “think aloud” strategy humans use to solve complex problems. Figure 2.4 shows an example. Before an LLM is queried with a prompt, it should further elaborate on the context. The prompt is then adjusted by including the elaboration of the LLM before it is used to query the model.

Figure 2.4: Example: Dynamic problem elaboration of a reasoning task [13, p. 2]

Many other existing studies in the context of prompting primarily concentrate on fine-tuning approaches such as prefix tuning [64] and prompt tuning [63] rather than prompt crafting.

However, the approaches presented in this section also provide valuable insights into

the process of optimizing a prompt. The studies are mainly based on querying an LLM to modify the prompt or generate multiple similar prompts and evaluate which prompt candidates work best.

2.1.3 Challenges

This Subsection focuses on the challenges associated with manual and automatic prompt crafting.

Firstly, Shin et al. [116] report difficulties in manual prompt crafting: "prompts generated manually [...] did not perform considerably better than chance." They further state that different methods have different tasks and phenomena they are suitable for and that there are tasks for which prompt crafting cannot optimize the model's behavior at all.

Liu et al. [73, p. 27] are in line with these observations. They highlight that most existing research focuses on text classification or generation-related tasks. Applying these methods to more sophisticated tasks, such as information extraction and text analysis, is less discussed since it is less straightforward. Liu et al. [73, p. 27] predict that prompt crafting for these kinds of tasks requires either a reformulation of tasks as classification or generation-based problems or more effective answer engineering that helps to express various outputs in an appropriate textual format is necessary.

Moreover, dealing with structured information poses significant challenges since many NLP tasks incorporate inputs, such as trees, graphs, tables, or relational structures [73, p. 27]. Expressing these structures in prompts remains an open research question. To tackle this problem, for instance, Chen et al. [22] added marks to encode lexical information such as entity markings. Aghajanyan et al. [1] propose structured prompts based on Hyper Text Markup Language (HTML) for web text generation. Nonetheless, handling more types of structures needs to be explored further [73, p. 27].

Lastly, finding the optimal combination of prompt template and answer format is also an issue [73, p. 28]. The performance of a model depends significantly on both the prompt templates being used and the desired answer format being considered. Current approaches select answer templates first and then choose a prompt template, but simultaneous adjustments might yield more significant benefits [73, p. 28].

2.2 Supervised Fine-Tuning

This section delves into Supervised Fine-Tuning (SFT) for LLMs. In Subsection 2.2.1, the broader concept of Fine-Tuning (FT) is introduced, followed by a definition of SFT. Some of the primary challenges faced when fine-tuning an LLM using labeled data are explained in Subsection 2.2.2. Lastly, a selection of current state-of-the-art research studies FT and SFT are presented in Subsection 2.2.3.

2.2.1 Definitions & Concepts

In recent years, fine-tuning the parameters of a pre-trained model for a specific task has emerged as one of the most promising techniques in NLP [38]. This approach has gained popularity due to recent significant changes in model architectures, which caused fine-tuning to replace supervised learning as the primary standard [73].

According to Jurafsky and Martin [52, p. 242], fine-tuning "is the process of taking the network learned by these pre-trained models, and further training the model, often via an added neural net classifier that takes the top layer of the network as input, to perform some downstream task like named entity tagging or question answering or coreference." It is a transfer learning method that uses the knowledge acquired during pre-training to enhance performance on various tasks. In NLP, the downstream tasks can be, e.g., text classification, sentiment analysis, or text summarization [144, p. 4]. Specifically, fine-tuning involves exploring and modifying the model's internal parameters and structure. Reverse gradient propagation is then used to adjust the model parameters, allowing the model to be reused and generalized to new tasks [144, p. 4].

However, there is an ongoing debate about whether fine-tuning makes existing capabilities visible or helps the model learn new capabilities during the training process [12, p. 2]. Ben Zaken, Goldberg, and Ravfogel [12, p. 1] support that fine-tuning "is mainly about exposing knowledge induced by language-modeling training, rather than learning new task-specific linguistic knowledge."

During transfer learning through fine-tuning, a pre-trained encoder network is used to generate contextualized representations from input data. A task-specific classification layer is placed on top of the encoder. The encoder and the classification layers are fine-tuned together to minimize task loss [12, p. 1].

Supervised fine-tuning describes explicitly the process of fine-tuning using supervised learning. SFT aims to develop a system capable of generating accurate predictions when presented with unseen data consisting of input and label pairs. The labeled training data is needed since supervised learning builds upon predicting the label for a specific input as closely as possible [74, p. 1].

Jurafsky and Martin [52, p. 63] confirm that in "supervised learning, we have a data set of input observations, each associated with some correct output (a 'supervision signal'). The algorithm aims to learn how to map from a new observation to a correct output." The algorithm reduces the difference between the supervision signal and the outputs generated by the LLM [75].

Figure 2.5: Process of supervised learning [74, p. 2]

Figure 2.5 shows the supervised learning process in more detail. The training dataset consists of labeled training samples, where x is the input and y is the expected output. A training input x_i is given to the learning system - an LLM - that produces an output \tilde{y}_i . An arbitrator compares the generated output \tilde{y}_i with the ground truth labeling y_i and calculates the discrepancy between them by, e.g., cross-entropy loss, named error signal. Finally, the learning system modifies its internal parameters based on the received error signal to achieve a minimal difference between \tilde{y}_i and y_i [74].

Using SFT on a pre-trained model can substantially decrease the required training time compared to starting from scratch with a completely new model [63]. Furthermore, updating all the model's parameters during fine-tuning "can significantly improve the model's ability to generalize on new tasks" [144, p. 4].

2.2.2 Challenges

Despite the numerous advantages of SFT, there are still some challenges that must be addressed. These issues include the requirement of computational resources, overfitting, catastrophic forgetting, and model stability after SFT.

Firstly, fine-tuning demands a lot of computational resources since it includes optimizing all the model's parameters. This might pose severe difficulties in small-scale environments with limited resources [20]. Moreover, fine-tuning a pre-trained model on different tasks requires a new model for each task, which also requires a lot of saving space and resources [38].

Another challenge lies in the risk of overfitting, especially when dealing with limited amounts of labeled training data. In such cases, full-parameter fine-tuning only results in good performance on the training data but poor generalization to new, unseen data [120].

Additionally, fine-tuning may lead to catastrophic forgetting, causing the model to lose the initial pretraining knowledge when focusing on a new task [42, 106]. Furthermore, full-parameter fine-tuning leads to better accuracy for in-distribution data; however, it decreases the model's performance for out-of-distribution (OOD) data [60]. This can be explained by the fact that the lower layers of the neural network also change simultaneously with the head during training, distorting the pre-trained features [60].

Due to the catastrophic forgetting explained above, fine-tuning can also reduce the model's answer stability. The knowledge and output patterns learned during pre-training could be dissolved during the fine-tuning process, which results in an overall decreased model quality [38].

The success of SFT highly depends on the hyperparameter chosen during training. However, it is impossible to conclude the optimal hyperparameter settings by looking at the accuracy of the model's performance alone [137, p. 7960]. Furthermore, hyperparameters show ambiguous tendencies in their impact on the model's outputs. Using, e.g., a higher learning rate improves the performance for target distribution data, whereas the performance for OOD data is decreased [137, p. 7960].

Lastly, acquiring high-quality, labeled data for SFT poses another challenge. Conversely, collecting sufficient labeled data for the training datasets is often costly

[74, p. 3]. On the other side, there is not always a clear label due to uncertainties and ambiguities in real-world phenomena [74].

2.2.3 State of the Art

The SFT has evolved significantly since the introduction of GPT-1, which first established SFT for LLMs and demonstrated a remarkable performance increase for various NLP tasks [103]. BERT, a fine-tuning-based representation model, first reduced the need for many task-specific architectures and achieved state-of-the-art (SOTA) performance on different sentence-level and token-level tasks in 2018 [33]. Today, following GPT-1 and BERT, instead of training task-specific models, researchers focus on training LLMs on a fundamental pre-training task and fine-tuning them to multiple tasks using SFT afterward [86, p. 2].

Figure 2.6 overviews the most common strategies for fine-tuning pre-trained language models. It is possible to either fine-tune an entire model, fine-tune parts or the complete model within a custom architecture, or fine-tune small adapter sub-layers per each Transformer layer [86, p. 6]

Figure 2.6: Strategies for fine-tuning the full Pre-Trained Language Model (PLM) (left), for fine-tuning the full PLM in a custom model (center), and for fine-tuning a small adapter sub-layer per each Transformer layer (right). Transformer blocks that will be fine-tuned for the specific tasks are blue, and frozen blocks are grey. The entire transformer block is presented by its multi-head self-attention and adapter layers [86, p. 6]

In recent years, researchers mainly focused on challenges associated with SFT, primarily reducing computational resources.

A lot of work concentrated on limiting SFT to certain adapter weights only, keeping most weights in the model frozen during the fine-tuning process. This reduced the

computational resources needed and prevented the model from catastrophic forgetting after SFT [86, p. 8].

Ben Zaken, Goldberg, and Ravfogel [12] introduced BitFit and focused on optimizing bias parameters in the pre-trained transformers only. Again, this approach showed improved performance after SFT and reduced the computational requirements simultaneously [12].

Singular Value Fine-Tuning (SVFT) is another resource-saving approach. The SFT process becomes lightweight by decomposing "backbone parameters into three successive matrices via the Singular Value Decomposition (SVD), then only fine-tunes the singular values and keeps others frozen" [120]. This makes it possible to adapt feature representations to new classes within the model and, simultaneously, saves the semantic clues stored in the pre-trained backbone [120].

Addressing catastrophic forgetting, Hayes et al. [42] propose REMIND. This is an approach inspired by the human brain that fine-tunes a LLM with seen and unseen data simultaneously. By replaying compressed representations multiple times during training, the model learns step by step.

To address the lack of robustness in the model's performance, WiSE-FT uses the weights of zero-shot fine-tuned models for SFT. This significantly improves the model's quality for OOD input data [137].

2.3 Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback

This section introduces Reinforcement Learning with Human Feedback (RLHF) for LLMs. The fundamental principles of Reinforcement Learning (RL) and RLHF, are outlined and defined in Subsection 2.3.1. Subsection 2.3.2 discusses current state-of-the-art research studies that give a good overview of the ongoing changes in the field of RLHF. Lastly, Subsection 2.3.3 addresses some substantial challenges encountered when fine-tuning LLMs via RLHF.

2.3.1 Definitions & Concepts

Reinforcement learning (RL) holds immense promise for transforming the landscape of artificial intelligence (AI). It marks a crucial milestone in developing autonomous systems that possess a more nuanced understanding of the real world. [5]

At its core, RL is a "mathematical framework for experience-driven autonomous learning" [5, p. 1]. RL revolves around an agent engaging with its environment, trying to learn an optimal policy for sequential decision-making useful in natural and social sciences, as well as engineering domains by trial and error [67]

Kaufmann et al. [55, p. 10] describe RL as "the setting of learning behavior from rewarded interaction with an environment." More specifically, RL operates within a Markov Decision Process (MDP), a modeling framework designed for handling sequential decision-making processes [10]. In an MDP, an agent goes through repeated cycles observing its present situation, executing an action leading to the transition into another state, and obtaining a reward depending on the outcome of the executed action [55].

Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) emerged after deep learning became more popular and contributed to RL through "big data, powerful computation, new algorithmic techniques, mature software packages and architectures, and strong financial support." [67, p. 5] In particular, combining deep neural networks and reinforcement learning proved promising. The main difference between DRL and traditional RL depends on the choice of function approximator. As known from deep learning in general, DRL uses stochastic gradient descent to refine weight parameters within the policy [67].

Figure 2.7: Contrasting the standard RL setting with RLHF using a reward model [55, p. 11]

Figure 2.7 (a) depicts the standard proceeding for RL. An agent decides on an action based on its policy and the current state. Next, the environment moves onto a new state due to the action. The agent then perceives an updated state and a resulting reward, indicating how favorable this action was at the current state. This process is executed repeatedly [55].

Li [67, p. 9] highlights that an "RL agent interacts with an environment over time." During each time step, the agent is given a state from the range of possible states and needs to select an action out of the predefined actions. This choice is guided by a policy that represents the agent's behavior. After executing the chosen action, the agent obtains a scalar reward, and the environment transitions into a new state. For episodic problems, this process is repeated until the agent arrives at a terminating state [67].

Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (RLHF) is a specific form of DRL. Since LLMs often tend to have harmful, biased, or incorrect answers, RLHF tries to address this problem by aligning the behavior of LLMs with human preferences. The objectives for RLHF-learned models are to generate answers that are *helpful*, i.e., assist users in solving tasks, *honest*, i.e., avoid deception or fabrication, and *harmless*, i.e., prevent potential harm to individuals or the environment [96]. Therefore, in RLHF, humans take the role of a teacher and provide feedback in the form of rewards or penalties needed for RL [58].

Figure 2.7 (b) shows the standard proceeding for RLHF. Unlike standard RL, there is no reward signal available by default. Instead, RLHF relies on single or multiple human labelers, who can give feedback as rewards. This reward learning procedure is entirely detached from the policy optimization and can be executed asynchronously [55].

Figure 2.8 shows the SOTA proceeding in RLHF for NLP tasks, first proposed by Ouyang et al. [96]. The proceeding can be divided into three stages: Supervised Fine-Tuning, Reward Model Training, and Policy Optimization via PPO [112].

The first step collects human-generated demonstrations across various input prompts that mirror the desired behavior. Next, these data examples are used to train an LLM, also called policy, using SFT [96, 58]. Further insights into the process of SFT can be found in Section 2.2.

As a second step, a reward model is trained. Therefore, a set of model outputs for each prompt within a dataset are gathered, and human evaluators are asked to indicate

Figure 2.8: The three steps of RLHF: (1) SFT, (2) RM training, and (3) RL via PPO [96]

their preferred choices for each group of outputs. This labeled dataset can be used to train a reward model (RM) that best imitates human behavior in rating outputs [96, 58].

Lastly, the supervised policy trained in step 1 is fine-tuned. The fine-tuning is conducted with the help of the RM trained in step 2, which predicts a reward for each output the policy has generated. Based on these rewards, the policy is updated using the Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) algorithm. Fine-tuning aims to maximize the reward for the generated outputs [96, 58].

Köpf et al. [58] highlight that the success of RLHF largely depends on the quality of the data used in all three steps. Köpf et al. [58] further state that it is problematic that most large-scale human feedback datasets available for open research are automatically generated with the help of LLMs and do not fulfill the high standards needed for training human-aligned LLMs with RLHF [58].

2.3.2 State of the Art

Current research in RLHF focuses on addressing the challenges discussed in Subsection 2.3.3. Some studies are exemplarily presented in this section.

One of the first and groundbreaking examples of successful implementation of RLHF in NLP was applying RLHF for text summarization [119]. Summarization models typically aim to match human reference summaries using evaluation metrics like ROUGE [69]. However, these metrics could not assess the quality of the generated

summaries. Stiennon et al. [119] showed that training a summarization model with RLHF significantly improved the quality of the summaries produced [119].

Other studies focused on reducing bias and harmfulness in the outputs of RLHF-trained models. Santurkar et al. [109, p. 1] investigate "Whose opinions (if any) do RLHF trained models reflect?" Therefore, they create a dataset, *OpinionQA*, for evaluating the alignment of an LLM with more than 60 US demographic groups covering topics from abortion to automation [109]. Perez et al. [99] propose a framework that can automatically detect harmful behavior in LLMs and propose a strategy based on RLHF to optimize these models and reduce harmfulness.

There is also research that centers around the process of collecting human-annotated data. Pandey et al. [97] propose a method to reduce the rate of human errors during the RLHF labeling process and additionally give insights into multiple automated algorithmic approaches to prevent errors in labeling. Further, Saunders et al. [110] fine-tuned an LLM to write critical comments in natural language. This model was found to be a helpful assistance in the process of rating outputs by LLMs and reduced to human error rate significantly [110].

Looking at the reward model, Michaud, Gleave, and Russell [85] investigated how reward functions learn and successfully applied saliency methods to identify failure modes and predict the robustness of reward functions.

Hong, Bhatia, and Dragan [44, p. 1] research tries to address the question: "How accurate do these models [reward models] need to be for the reward inference to be accurate?" They state that minimal errors in the performance of reward models can lead to catastrophic errors during policy inference. By offering a potential solution to this question, Nikishin et al. [90, p. 1] reduced the effect of noise on training by applying stochastic weight averaging (SWA) that averages weights along the optimization trajectory. This "stabilizes the model solutions, alleviates the problem of forgetting the highly rewarded policy during training." [90, p. 1]

2.3.3 Challenges

Despite its popularity in current research, RLHF still shows several challenges that should be considered. Following Casper et al. [18], the challenges can be broadly categorized into three areas: issues related to human feedback itself (Subsection 2.3.4),

problems with the reward model training (Subsection 2.3.5), as well as difficulties during policy optimization (Subsection 2.3.6).

2.3.4 Challenges due to human feedback

Collecting high-quality human feedback poses different challenges. First, selecting representative humans and ensuring they provide accurate and reliable feedback can be problematic. For instance, after RLHF, models like ChatGPT were found to become systematically politically biased [109]. Second, some evaluators may show harmful biases and opinions, potentially influencing the models toward their perspectives [98]. Third, humans often make mistakes for various reasons, including lack of interest, attention decay, time constraints, or personal biases [97]. Fourth, the evaluator's ability to provide valuable feedback decreases by providing only partial information about the context to be evaluated [18]. Lastly, humans struggle to accurately assess performance on complex tasks, even with unlimited time. Saunders et al. [110] show that human evaluators could not find half of the critical errors and inaccuracies in summaries generated by a model. This is in line with the observations by Bowman et al. [14], who state that humans can be misled during evaluation, e.g., in case a model sounds confident and provides good ratings even for incorrect answers.

However, humans and the data and feedback structure make it challenging to collect high-quality data. In particular, there is a tradeoff between the cost and quality of human feedback collected for RLHF. Casper et al. [18] highlight a tradeoff between the quality of the rating and the length of the conversations, which results in poor performance for RLHF fine-tuned models for more extended conversations.

There is also a tradeoff between the richness and efficiency of feedback type. The types of feedback used most commonly to gather human feedback are binary preferences between pairs of examples, k-wise rankings, and best-of-k queries [18]. However, this kind of feedback does not leave room for elaboration or reasoning as to why an answer was preferred over another. In RLHF, the reward model can exploit the lack of precise information about the ratings [18]. Using free-text fields for human ratings seems to be a better solution but poses challenges. "Capturing language feedback in a reward model is a challenging inverse learning problem complicated significantly by imprecision in human speech and cross-cultural differences in language use." [18, p. 8]

2.3.5 Challenges due to the reward model (training)

Some problems related to the training of the reward model can stem from problem misspecification [18].

It remains a question of research on how human values can be depicted within a reward function. Potential misconceptions about the human decision-making processes can impact reward inference [44]. Moreover, most existing approaches to RLHF ignore the role of personality and context dependency within human preferences [117].

Furthermore, a single reward function might fail to capture the vast diversity present among the human evaluators. It is impossible to align a model to human preferences when the preferences among humans are diverse and partially contradictory [18]. Ouyang et al. [96] report annotator-annotator and annotator-researcher agreements up to 77%, which cannot be captured using a single reward function.

Creating robust and effective reward models poses additional challenges. Reward models can still develop undesired behavior during assigning rewards even though the training data is correctly labeled [85]. They can also prioritize unexpected environment/textual input features and show poor performance for out-of-distribution generalization [124]. Consequently, using such a reward model can result in *reward hacking*, where LLMs generate outputs that are often grammatically, syntactically, or content-wise incorrect [118]. This issue is addressed by regularization penalizing the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence between a base model and the finetuned model, but reward hacking remains a problem [119].

Evaluating the reward models proves to be another complex aspect of RLHF. The true reward function is usually unknown, so direct evaluation becomes impossible [18]. Instead, reward models are commonly evaluated indirectly by training a policy using the learned reward model and examining the generated content from the RL policy [18].

2.3.6 Challenges due to the policy optimization

Next to collecting high-quality human-labeled data and training the reward model, optimizing policies effectively remains a significant challenge. Despite advancements, balancing exploration and exploitation is an essential yet unsolved dilemma [3, 5]. Therefore, RLHF remains unstable, with results being highly dependent on

initializations and often unable to replicate [90]. Additionally, even when policies trained with optimal reward signals show the desired performance for their designated tasks, "they can still perform poorly in adversarial situations" [18, p. 10].

Policies developed through RLHF do pose the challenge of misgeneralization. For instance, a policy could learn to follow a goal different from the intended target even when trained with optimal reward signals [18]. Furthermore, RLHF agents tend to strive for power, causing undesirable behaviors. For instance, an RLHF-trained question-answering LLM might manipulate the user to abstain from challenging discussions [18].

Furthermore, pre-trained models can show biases that impact policy optimization. For example, in case confidently generated responses usually provide accurate answers for the base model, the reward model learns to favor confidence and reinforces this behavior during policy optimization [18]. Another challenge within the policy optimization is *mode collapse*, which describes the tendency of the policy to produce less diverse results, i.e., follow a specific response pattern for each answer [99].

Lastly, further challenges arise when combining the reward model and the policy in RLHF. Joint training of the reward model and policy can cause shifts in distribution: If the reward model relies on offline data, there is a likelihood of misgeneralization. Conversely, if the reward model and policy are simultaneously learned by collecting feedback from policy samples, the system might experience an "auto-induced distributional shift" [18, p. 11].

Further, enforcing efficiency and preventing overfitting by the policy simultaneously appears contradictory. Since there is usually no labeled validation data for all the different areas the policy model explores, it is hard to identify whenever the reward will be optimized too extensively during training [18].

2.4 Domain Specialisation

This section delves into the core concept of this thesis: Domain Specialization. In Subsection 2.4.1, the idea of domain specialization is introduced, and an overview of the approaches used to specialize an LLM is given. Subsection 2.4.2 further explains current state-of-the-art research for different domains and provides a good overview

of the ongoing research questions in this field. Lastly, Subsection 2.4.3 discusses some of the significant challenges, including the complexity of the domains, the process of collecting data, and the challenges centering around the evaluation of domain-specialized LLMs.

2.4.1 Definitions & Concepts

This subsection defines and explains the concept of *Domain Specialization*. To understand the concept of domain specialization, it is crucial to define the term *domain* since it can have different meanings depending on the context and the field of research in which it is used. According to the WordNet of Princeton University [128], *domain* can be interpreted in five different ways:

1. sphere, domain, area, orbit, field, arena (a particular environment or walk of life) "his social sphere is limited"; "it was a closed area of employment"; "he's out of my orbit."
2. domain, demesne, land (territory over which rule or control is exercised) "his domain extended into Europe"; "he made it the law of the land."
3. domain, domain of a function ((mathematics) the set of values of the independent variable for which a function is defined)
4. world, domain (people in general, especially a distinctive group of people with some shared interest), "the Western world."
5. knowledge domain, knowledge base, domain (the content of a particular field of knowledge)

Domain in domain specialization can be understood as the fifth definition proposes, i.e., as a knowledge domain. The International Society for Knowledge Organization (ISKO) defines knowledge domains as "a body of knowledge, defined socially and theoretically as the knowledge of a group of people sharing ontological and epistemological commitments. Domains are often academic disciplines but may also be, for example, hobbies" [43].

The term *domain* does not explicitly pertain to the concept of domain specialization but also applies to domain adaption. Although the two concepts may seem similar,

distinguishing between them is crucial.

On one hand, domain adaption aims to learn a generalized classifier, where the domain of application shifts from one domain (source domain) to another (target domain). The model is initially trained on the source domain with a large amount of labeled data, and its performance is subsequently improved on a target domain using only limited labeled data by leveraging knowledge learned from the source domain [36, pp. 1–3].

On the other hand, domain specialization can be understood as adjusting a general model, trained on data covering various topics, to perform optimally within a particular domain. This is usually achieved by taking a pre-trained model and further training it on data from the specific domain. This thesis exclusively focuses on domain specialization.

There are multiple ways to define the concept of domain specialization. However, this thesis focuses on the definition proposed by Ling et al. [71]: Domain specialization is "the process of customizing *general-purpose LLMs* according to specific *domain contextual data*, augmented by *domain-specific knowledge*, optimized by the *domain's objective*, and regulated by *domain-specific constraints*."

General-purpose LLMs refer to pre-trained models for specific or multiple NLP task(s) based on large cross- or domain-generic textual corpora, usually online and publicly available [8, p. 2]. These datasets cover a broad range of domains and contexts, equipping the LLMs, by default, with general knowledge across a wide range of topics. The LLM is most familiar with the topics that predominantly appear in the training data [71, p. 3]. The term *domain contextual data* describes any textual or spoken data, e.g., documents, articles, knowledge graphs, that contains information specific to the particular domain. *Domain-specific knowledge* describes information, concepts, and understanding, e.g., jargon or terminology, that is individual a certain domain. The *domain's objective* describes a specific goal or task intended to be achieved for a chosen domain, e.g., melanoma detection in biomedicine or correcting students' assignments in education. Domain contextual data, domain-specific knowledge, and domain objectives are closely connected. For instance, knowledge graphs constructed for the clinical healthcare domain (as a form of domain-contextual data) facilitate the representation of medical concepts such as drugs and diseases (as domain knowledge), enabling context-aware insights and enhancing clinical research, decision-making, and healthcare delivery (as multiple domain objectives)

[25, p. 1]. While defining domain-specific goals, it is essential also to be aware of *domain-specific constraints*. These are limitations or conditions that need to be considered during the training or application of the specialized model. Constraints can be ethical, legal, or practical considerations, e.g., ensuring the quality and consistency of patient data and removing personal data to protect patients' privacy in biomedicine [25, p. 2].

In common understanding, individuals possessing specific domain knowledge are usually perceived as specialists or experts in their respective fields. Domain specialization aims to optimize LLMs until they acquire expertise in a particular knowledge domain. Academic domains, especially, are relevant in research concerning domain specialization. However, it is essential to note that domains do not necessarily have to be academic.

Researchers have focused on domain specialization across a diverse spectrum of fields, encompassing natural sciences (e.g., biomedicine and earth science), social sciences (e.g., education, finance, and law), and formal sciences (e.g., human-computer interaction, software engineering, and cybersecurity).

Biomedicine, in particular, emerges as a promising research domain. LLMs can be trained on a wide range of domain-specific data, including genomic and proteomic information, to analyze and predict biological functions and disease mechanisms. Additionally, domain-specific LLMs can assist in predicting protein structures and interactions, contributing to understanding cellular processes. They also play a role in clinical healthcare by identifying disease patterns, making diagnoses, and providing personalized treatment recommendations [71, 26, 36f]. Wang et al. [129] propose a classification where all tasks for the biomedical domain can be grouped into six different fields: Information extraction tasks (NER, event detection, relation extraction), document-level tasks (text classification, text summarization), sentence-level tasks (sentence similarity, natural language inference), conversational tasks (QA, dialogue systems), protein/DNA sequence tasks and competition and venues. A more detailed overview of the fields of application can be found in [129, pp. 12–15].

Geoscience, also known as earth science, being an interdisciplinary domain, involves the study of physical and human systems across diverse spatial and temporal scales. This includes methods ranging from information science to natural disasters and urbanization. LLMs, in this context, can be beneficial by providing answers to

environmental-related questions, developing innovative ideas, or generating climate scenarios [71, 26, 37ff.].

The fintech (financial technology) domain is experiencing growth in the social sciences, particularly finance. NLP tasks within the trading and investment management domain often include sentiment analysis, question answering, named entity recognition (NER), and text classification [71, p. 39]. Furthermore, LLMs focus on creating solutions optimized for financial text analysis and e-commerce settings [131, p. 45].

Within the legal domain, two primary fields of application are extensively explored. One field focuses on adapting LLMs to the legal domain, examining their potential in accomplishing legal tasks, including legal reasoning and predicting legal judgments. The other field relates to the transformative potential of LLMs in legal applications through empirical evaluations, with case studies conducted to assess their performance in legal examinations [71, p. 40].

The education domain covers various aspects, including health research, medical education, library management, journal and media education, engineering education, science, and higher education. Domain-specific LLMs can notably support the self-learning process for students. For teachers, LLMs offer opportunities to create teaching materials or correct (simple) exams and tests, among other tasks [71, p. 42]. In formal sciences like human-computer interaction, the primary focus is on robotics. In this domain, LLMs should understand language to produce multi-model outputs, such as sound, pictures, or movements. Research in this area primarily covers speech, dialogue, and vision-related tasks [71, p. 42].

LLMs specialized in software engineering become experts in understanding and explaining given code or producing code for a given generation task [71, p. 44]. Cybersecurity-specialized LLMs have the prevention of cyber attacks, such as phishing, malware, and ransomware, as their main goal, ensuring digital assets' confidentiality, integrity, and availability [71, p. 45].

Customization is the keyword when talking about the motivation for domain specialization. Not only in academic research, where customization often refers to an academic discipline, but also in economic research, customization, referring to a company's needs, is essential. In business scenarios, general-purpose LLMs usually struggle with domain-specific prompts that require company-specific solutions [58, 143]. Different fields of research, institutions, and companies have their expectations about which response will suit the model best, which is why a single general-purpose

LLM with no customization cannot outperform a domain-specific LLM. Furthermore, not all kinds of data can be fed to a general-purpose LLM, especially company internal data like proprietary assets, which can be problematic [71, 2f.].

Figure 2.9: The taxonomy for current techniques on LLM domain specialization [71, p. 6]

Figure 2.9 provides an overview of the proposed taxonomy for domain specialization techniques in LLMs. Ling et al. [71] have classified these methods into three main categories: external augmentation, prompt crafting, and model fine-tuning.

External augmentation is an approach that enhances the performance of LLMs by integrating information taken from external sources. This technique includes two primary subcategories: *Domain Knowledge Augmentation* and *Domain Tool Augmentation*. In *Domain Knowledge Augmentation*, LLMs receive domain-specific context from an external knowledge source as input, expanding their knowledge base. Figure 2.10 illustrates a simple example of an LLM utilizing domain knowledge augmentation. On the other hand, *Domain Tool Augmentation* extends the functionality of LLMs by connecting them to external systems or tools using Application Programming Interfaces (APIs). "Domain Knowledge Augmentation supplements the model's responses with external information, while Domain Tool Augmentation expands the model's capabilities for tasks it couldn't perform otherwise." [71, p. 8]

Figure 2.10: Example for LLMs calling domain tools [71, p. 11]

Prompt crafting is the second category of domain specialization techniques. It focuses on designing effective prompts to guide LLMs toward generating domain-appropriate outputs. There are two types of prompting strategies: *Discrete Prompt* and *Continuous Prompt*. *Discrete Prompt* describes creating natural language instructions tailored to a specific domain that activates the base knowledge an LLM already possesses. Conversely, *Continuous Prompt* employs learnable vectors instead of manual text instructions to prompt LLMs, offering flexibility and adaptability [71, 12f.].

Figure 2.11: Visualization of two approaches to fine-tune LLMs based on domain-specific knowledge, where the blue rectangle denotes the set of parameters in an LLM. (a) adapter-based LLM fine-tuning; (b) task-oriented model fine-tuning [71, p. 18]

The fine-tuning techniques used to achieve domain specialization in LLMs can be divided into two main approaches: *Adapter-based fine-tuning* and *Task-oriented fine-tuning*. Adapter-based fine-tuning uses neural adapters to boost the LLM's performance on domain-specific tasks without significantly adjusting its inner parameters (2.11 a)). This approach allows researchers to fine-tune only task-specific parameters of an LLM while preserving most of its skills and knowledge. Alternatively, *task-oriented fine-tuning* modifies all the LLM's inner parameters to optimize its performance with particular tasks (2.11 b)). "However, entirely updating all parameters of an LLM may be impractical due to hardware limitations and potential performance degradation." [71, p. 19.]

Moreover, task-oriented fine-tuning has two subcategories as well: *instruction-based knowledge update* (Figure 2.12 c)) and *partial knowledge update* (Figure 2.12 d)). *Instruction-based knowledge update* fine-tunes an LLM on a range of tasks by explicitly stating the instructions in the prompts. A popular approach for instruction-based knowledge updates is RLHF [96]. Conversely, *partial knowledge update* fine-tunes an LLM by editing only the part of the model's parameters related to a specific knowledge domain [71, p. 23].

Figure 2.12: (a) using an LLM trained on general corpora without modifications, (b) enhancing the LLM's performance through retrieving relevant external knowledge, (c) utilizing domain-specific and task-relevant instructions to improve LLM's capabilities, and (d) updating the LLM's internal knowledge with domain-specific text and tasks [71, p. 7]

It is important to note that this classification is based on the varying degrees of accessibility to LLMs: "no access (black box), partial access (grey box), and full access (white box)" [71, p. 6]. Black box approaches refer to all domain specialization processes where users only interact with the model API without getting any further insight into the underlying model. Grey box approaches describe having restricted information, such as token probabilities, making it possible to create effective prompts for domain knowledge extraction. Lastly, white box approaches grant complete access to the LLM, e.g., open-source models like Llama [125], including settings, training data, and architecture [71, p. 6].

2.4.2 State of the Art

The rapid advancements in LLMs have led to extensive research in applying these models to various domains. This section presents the current state of research in

domain specialization for LLMs for various domains. Per domain, one or two current studies are highlighted, and their findings are discussed.

Biomedicine has emerged as the largest area of domain-specific research. One by Gu et al. [41] compared two contrasting approaches of pre-training for domain specialization: *Mixed-Domain Pre-training* and *Domain-Specific Pre-training from Scratch* (see Figure 2.13). *Mixed-domain pretraining* assumes that out-of-domain text still contains valuable information for the specialized domain and executes the domain-specific pretraining using a general-domain language model. Alternatively, *domain-specific pretraining from scratch* generates the vocabulary and executes pretraining exclusively using in-domain text [41, p. 2]. The in-domain approach significantly surpasses mixed-domain pretraining, yielding new state-of-the-art outcomes for multiple biomedical NLP tasks [41, p. 20].

Figure 2.13: Two paradigms for neural language model pretraining proposed by [41, p. 2].

Another new approach in the domain of biomedicine combines augmented information retrieval and SFT [53]. This approach, called *Self-Alignment*, builds upon human-written domain-specific seed instructions. The base model then produces instructions and corresponding contexts tailored to the given domain. Next, a retrieval system enriches these instruction-input pairs with domain-specific knowledge. Finally, the base model is specialized through fine-tuning [53, p. 2]. The process is depicted in Figure 2.14. According to Kang et al. [53, p. 10], *Self-Alignment* demonstrates superiority over the base and larger general-purpose models.

Geoscience is another rapidly growing field of research regarding domain specialization. Most models tailored to the geoscience domain can only perform narrowly

Figure 2.14: An Overview of Self-Specialization [53, p. 2]

defined tasks and "cannot adapt to new tasks or different data distributions without complete retraining" [141, p. 2]. *K2*, by Deng et al. [30], posed a breakthrough with the development of the first-ever geoscience-focused LLM. To create *K2*, Deng et al. [30] used a Llama 2 7B model and pre-trained it on approximately 5.5 billion tokens of geoscience text corpus. They further fine-tuned the model using a geoscience-specific labeled dataset. Additionally, they equipped *K2* to use external tools [30, p. 1]. Figure 2.15 depicts the proceeding.

Figure 2.15: Training approach of *K2*: Further pre-train for absorption of geoscience knowledge and instruction tuning, deploying to make the model align with humans [30, p. 2]

Building on the success of *K2*, *Geogalactica 30B* was developed [70]. Lin et al. [70] followed the same approach as Deng et al. [30] for their *K2* model but used a mode setup using scientific data instead of general-purpose data. *Geogalactica 30B*

sets a new state-of-the-art performance various NLP tasks within the geosciences domain, highlighting the importance of the base model [70, p. 1].

Cui et al. [26, p. 7] introduced *ChatLaw* in the law domain. *ChatLaw* is a legal domain-specific LLM designed based on an integrated external knowledge base. The LLM is connected to a vector knowledge database with keyword retrieval, significantly reducing hallucinations [26, p. 2].

In finance, *EcomGPT* is an LLM specifically trained for E-commerce scenarios. It underwent instruction tuning using a newly created *EcomInstruct* dataset of 2.5 million instruction samples covering diverse E-commerce tasks [65, p. 7]. Li et al. [65] state that *EcomGPT* outperforms *ChatGPT* for E-commerce-related tasks.

Domain specialization expanded to the fields of education and software engineering as well. *GrammarGPT* is an open-source LLM dedicated to correcting errors in Chinese grammar that was created using SFT, specifically instruction tuning [35, p. 1]. However, most of the models specialized for education focus on software engineering due to the availability of open-access online data. Datasets can be easily collected from multiple sources "including but not limited to, major websites, forums, blogs, and social media platforms." [45, p. 13] Stack Overflow threads or GitHub issue comments are the primary sources used to generate datasets for domain specialization in software engineering [45, p. 13]. An example is the code summarization model trained with fine-tuning using a base model trained on source code by Al-Kaswan et al. [54].

With the increasing popularity of powerful pre-trained models like GPT, there is growing interest in employing them to solve industrial tasks ranging from finance to genomics. However, current solutions face limitations when specializing these models in enterprise domains. Baldazzi et al. [8] propose a new approach based on Enterprise Knowledge Graphs (EKGs) and ontological reasoning to bridge this gap. They suggest incorporating ontological reasoning tasks on EKGs during the fine-tuning process since this provides internal and external knowledge [8, p. 3].

The field of domain specialization for LLMs still requires a lot of research to address the complexity of this task effectively. Most approaches currently rely on a combination of various domain specialization strategies rather than one single method. Existing specialized models mainly use a two-stage training strategy based on pre-training and fine-tuning [37, p. 4]. High-quality pre-trained language models

(PLMs) have significantly influenced the shift toward this two-stage paradigm in NLP [129, p. 3].

In domains where pre-trained LLMs are readily available, researchers refine these models instead of starting from scratch (e.g., biomedicine). On the contrary, in less explored domains, pre-training remains essential (e.g., law or education). Across all domains, augmented approaches perform well, although they rarely succeed without the support of SFT as a first step.

2.4.3 Challenges

The challenges related to domain specialization are grouped into three different categories: Challenges due to the complexity of the domain (Subsection 2.4.4), challenges centering around the availability and quality of the training data (Subsection 2.4.5) as well as the challenges in evaluating and interpreting the output of domain-specialized LLMs (Subsection 2.4.6).

2.4.4 Domain complexity

By default, LLMs possess knowledge of a wide range of topics and, therefore, already incorporate some domain-specific knowledge before training. However, the knowledge acquired is usually based on popular, broad domain concepts, and detailed domain-specific knowledge is underrepresented. "Each domain has its unique intricacies and complexities, which could range from highly specialized vocabularies, and nuanced terminologies to complex knowledge structures". [71, p. 27] The complex domain-specific concepts, terms, and relationships between different entities make it difficult to specialize a model to a particular domain since it has no points of contact with those before [71, p. 3]. Understanding and working with domain knowledge is a significant challenge for humans and all types of LLMs [71, 27f.].

Within a single domain and between different domains, there are essential differences in conversation and language styles for various fields, roles, and tasks. These differences can range from medical prescriptions to legal sentences to online chatting. Even people need years of training to adapt to these linguistically specific conditions, making domain specialization for LLMs a non-trivial task [71, 2f.].

Different domains do not only influence the usage of language, but social norms,

cultural conformity, religious beliefs, legal requirements, and ethical practice additionally constrain languages. These parameters change in different locations, countries, populations, races, communities, etc., so even domain-specialized models can never be a one-size-fits-all solution without any customization [71, 2f.].

Furthermore, domains evolve, e.g., new terminologies, concepts, and trends are introduced. One example is the COVID-19 pandemic which introduced a lot of new medical terms and concepts within a short period. This is why domain-specialized LLMs must be continuously updated to stay relevant and practical [71, 27f.].

This remains a massive challenge in the realm of domain specialization since LLMs tend to only know a particular point in time, i.e., the point of the end of data collection for training the model [71, p. 3]

Another challenge that general-purpose LLMs also fail to meet is that the level of domain knowledge needs to be very in-depth, in real-time, and accurate [71, 2f.]. This is why specialized LLMs in certain domains usually find their purpose in the economy, e.g., as customer-specific chatbots, or in research, e.g., for solving basic mathematical calculations.

One of the most significant ongoing discussions in domain specialization centers around balancing general and domain-specific knowledge. "Even though Supervised Fine-Tuning (SFT) methodologies are prevalent for adapting general-purpose LLMs to specific use-cases, the balancing act between maintaining general language capabilities and achieving domain-specific effectiveness remains a complex challenge." [143, p. 2]

On the one side, an LLM needs to understand the specificities of a particular domain and be as precise as possible in its answers. However, on the other side, the LLM must also be able to provide contextually appropriate responses, which can only be given if a good base of general world knowledge is present in the model. Finding a balance between general and domain knowledge is still an unsolved almost unsolvable, challenge [71, 27f.].

2.4.5 Data

Different challenges center around the data used to specialize an LLM in a specific domain.

The main problem is the tradeoff between coverage and quality [129, 33f.]. It is

impossible to find large-scale and high-quality corpora at the same time. This is why "one has to sacrifice its coverage to obtain a high-quality vertical application or train a general model with large-scaled yet low-quality corpora." [129, p. 33]

Corpora generated with the help of other LLMs or based on open-access information retrieved from the internet are likely to have wrong information included. It is also possible since research in the domains is still an ongoing process, that some concepts in the domains themselves are not entirely or wrongly developed yet, e.g. misclassified disease definitions in the domain of biomedicine [129, 33f.]. Furthermore, the data is usually heterogeneous, e.g. including tables, figures, and graphs, which are challenging to convert into language-based training data for a domain-specialized LLM [129, 33f.].

Depending on the approach chosen for domain specialization, high-quality data is essential. For instance, there are many ways to augment LLMs with retrieved knowledge and enhance the quality of their outputs. However, "the performance of these retrieval-based methods is limited by the strength of the retrievers" and the retrieved data quality [51, p. 1].

Additionally, not all resources available can be used. Personal Health Information (PHI) poses the challenge of respecting privacy when pre-training models, e.g. for melanoma detection [62].

For other domains, covering a wide range of domain-specific fields in the training datasets is a significant challenge since not enough data is available. "The challenge is to create efficient and effective methods for domain specialization that can be scaled to cover many different domains" [71, 27f.].

Lastly, not only a lot of high-quality data is necessary to specialize a model for a particular domain. The training process is also time-consuming and resource-intensive [71, p. 3].

2.4.6 Evaluation & Interpretation

The problems emerge when tailoring a model for a certain domain and only when evaluating the results and interpreting the outputs produced by the model.

The models' outputs should be as unambiguous and correct as possible, especially in domains like biomedicine, since the "consequence of bad decisions/predictions may be deadly" [129, 33f.]. It is also vital to distinguish between causalities and correlations when training and interpreting the models. Causality may be able to provide an underlying explanation of a decision made by a model, which is important for tasks like diagnosing a patient [129, 33f.].

"It is crucial for users, especially in high-stakes domains like healthcare, law, or finance, to understand how the model arrived at a certain output." [71, 27f.] However, achieving this transparency is still a challenge and often results in a trade-off between model complexity and explainability [71, 27f.].

Further, evaluating these models remains challenging due to the lack of high-quality data. The benchmarks available mainly focus on the ability to formulate confident and correct answers but focus less on the factual correctness and the level of domain-specific knowledge the model presents [71].

It is not only limited to domain specialization research, but researchers also show the tendency "to "manipulate" results via evaluation methods [8, p. 2]. Since researchers aim to achieve new state-of-the-art performance, the evaluation perspective can be shifted accordingly. The research of domain specialization has a fundamental problem: the results achieved, even with the fine-tuning of a PLM, are "not acceptable for core tasks in specialized domains" [8, p. 2]. Baldazzi et al. [8] name BoolbergGPT [139], an LLM fine-tuned in the domain of finance, as an example. The model is said to outperform state-of-the-art models in the finance domain in QA; however, the evaluation was done using questions regarding factual information that is stored in the input databases for augmentation. One can assume that the mode cannot perform as well for out-of-database questions [8, p. 2].

In conclusion, the domain specialization is an ongoing field of research. Open questions and challenges remain in the choice of the approach to specialize models and in the data collection and evaluation of those models.

3 Objectives

The rapid growth of LLMs has led to significant improvements in various NLP tasks. However, these models often have a base knowledge in a broad range of topics and therefore lack the necessary expertise to effectively tackle more complex domain-specific questions such as the geoscience domain. Domain specialization offers a solution by adjusting LLMs to specific research fields like geoscience and enhancing their domain-specific understanding and output generation abilities. Nevertheless, the challenge of domain specialization is not entirely solved and remains a subject of ongoing research. Currently, no standard procedure is suitable for all domains [71].

Researchers have tested various methods for domain specialization, including prompt engineering, transfer learning, and fine-tuning [71]. In the section on future work, Ling et al. [71] emphasize the necessity of testing more *hybrid approaches*. A hybrid approach includes combining methods with different levels of access to LLMs, such as no access (black box), partial access (grey box), and full access (white box) [71, p. 6]. This thesis addresses this issue by combining a grey-box approach with two white-box approaches for domain specialization. SFT and RLHF fall into the white-box approaches category, while prompt crafting is part of the grey-box approaches. According to Ling et al. [71, p. 26], this combination "could provide a balance between resource requirement and model performance and might be especially effective when dealing with scarce domain-specific data."

While geoscience is not generally a domain with scarce data, it has only scarce structured data. Most of the knowledge acquired in the geoscience domain is stored in different forms of unstructured text [29]. Post-processing of existing textual data is still ongoing to extract structured knowledge that can be used for the training and fine-tuning of LLMs. Although initial efforts have been made to develop geoscience foundation models, there is no widespread adoption of this aim within the geoscience AI community. It is mainly restricted by the challenge of accessing large and diverse Earth system datasets that capture the complexity of the Earth system [141].

Consequently, models tailored to geoscience mainly center around a specific task only. For instance, a model is fine-tuned to predict the weather by training solely on historical climate records from a particular region. These models are only able to perform narrowly defined tasks and "cannot adapt to new tasks or different data distributions without complete retraining" [141, p. 2]. These limitations cause the

models to be inflexible and limited to predefined tasks constrained by their training datasets and labels [141].

Therefore, this thesis addresses two problems simultaneously: testing a new hybrid approach to domain specialization and creating a geoscience LLM that shifts the focus toward multi-purpose AI applications instead of developing a new application for each task.

3.1 Proceeding

The concept of domain specialization has gained significant attention in academic research. Several different approaches of domain specialization have already been tested and summarized in a survey by Ling et al. [71]. A pattern emerged within the proceeding of the previous approaches, and Ling et al. [71] established a framework to successfully apply domain specialization to LLMs.

Their proposed framework consists of four primary stages.

1. Definition
2. Augmentation
3. Optimization
4. Evaluation

Generally, this thesis follows the framework provided by Ling et al. [71]; however, it slightly adjusts it by inserting an additional step of optimization before the augmentation.

The first step, i.e. **Definition**, includes defining the specific domain, objectives, and constraints within that domain. This step is crucial since domain specialization requires a clear understanding of the domain, including the particular data, knowledge, and resources available for the next steps [71, p. 8].

This thesis deals with the domain of geoscience, and a definition is given in Chapter 4. However, the emphasis here lies primarily on testing a new approach for domain specialization rather than creating a model with geoscience expertise. Additionally, the author of the thesis is not an expert in geoscience and uses datasets that have been created for previous approaches to specialize a model in the domain of geoscience by

Deng et al. [30] and Lin et al. [70]. Therefore, all aspects of geoscience are already explored in the previous studies and will not be elaborated further.

In the second step, i.e. **Augmentation**, the domain expertise is infused into the model or its inputs/outputs [71, p. 8]. This thesis follows what Ling et al. [71] call a white box approach: Supervised Fine-Tuning with domain-specific data. The process and first results are discussed in Chapter 7.

The third step is **Optimization**. Once domain knowledge is integrated into the model, the focus shifts towards improving the model's behavior to fulfill the domain objectives better. Ling et al. [71] propose gradient descent for a white box approach or prompt engineering for a grey box approach. Here, two different optimization strategies are employed.

Firstly, *before* the augmentation step, prompt crafting is applied. After finding a prompt template and system prompt that increase the model's performance, the model will be fine-tuned on this template. This method aims to improve the model's overall performance and consistency, as described in Chapter 6.

After the augmentation step, RLHF is implemented to further align the model with human preferences and refine its performance for geoscientific tasks. Details are discussed in Chapter 8.

Lastly, in the fourth step, the model is **evaluated**. This includes "testing the specialized model's performance against predefined benchmarks, [and] gathering feedback" [71, p. 8]. The evaluation will be conducted using a domain-specific dataset proposed by Deng et al. [30]. The outcomes are interpreted manually by the author of this thesis and with the help of other LLMs. Chapter 9 contains all insights gained through the evaluation process.

3.2 Goal & Research Questions

This thesis primarily focuses on exploring and testing a new approach for the domain specialization of LLMs within geosciences. Refining and optimizing an existing general-purpose LLM, aims to enhance its performance specifically for geoscience-related tasks and topics. During the process of applying domain specialization to an LLM, several research questions are addressed to evaluate the new approach. The research questions can be grouped according to the framework explained in 3.1.

1. **Optimization:** What is the impact of applying prompt crafting before the augmentation step, and how is it expected to affect the overall performance and consistency of the geoscience-specialized LLM?
2. **Augmentation:** How does the supervised fine-tuning using domain-specific data influence the model's ability to incorporate and use geoscientific knowledge?
3. **Optimization:** How do RLHF affect the model's alignment with human preferences and its performance in geoscientific tasks?
4. **Evaluation:** Can the domain specialization approach applied in this thesis be seen as successful?

By addressing these research questions, the thesis follows an interdisciplinary aim. On the one side, it supports research in NLP and AI by advancing the development of domain-specialized models. On the other hand, it contributes to the development of a multi-purpose geoscience model that geoscientists can use for a broad range of geoscience-related tasks.

4 Geoscience

As the objective of this thesis lies within the application of a relatively new domain specialization approach to LLMs, it is essential to define the specific domain that is used. This chapter serves to introduce the domain of geoscience and its unique features.

The first section 4.1 provides a description and definition of the field of geoscience and lists all the sub-disciplines included in geoscience.

The second section 4.1 discusses the connection between the field of geoscience and the field of NLP. As data processing and information extraction from the immense amount of geoscience data has gained more attention in recent years, several NLP tools and applications have been developed and tailored to the needs of the geoscience community. The section presents some of the recent achievements and progress in this area.

4.1 Definition

The field of geoscience is not new, yet there is no universally accepted definition for this term. The frequent interchangeable usage of *geoscience* and *earth science* also influences this ambiguity. While some researchers view them as synonymous, others distinguish between them.

According to the U.S. Geological Survey [126], earth science and geoscience represent the exact natural science that focuses studying the Earth. However, the U.S. National Science Foundation [127] takes a different perspective. Geoscience is seen as a broader science encompassing various subdisciplines and domains of research dedicated to exploring multiple aspects of the Earth., including earth science. The U.S. National Science Foundation [127] identifies three significant branches: Atmospheric and Geospace Sciences (AGS), Earth Sciences (EAR), and Ocean Sciences (OCE).

This thesis adopts the perspective that sees geoscience as the umbrella science for different natural sciences. One broadly accepted definition comes from the National Research Council [89], which describes geoscience as "a natural science that studies the earth, including Geography, Physics, Chemistry, and other disciplines". Other researchers define the domain of geoscience more specifically with the help of more concrete natural sciences encompassed in geoscience. For example, Lin

et al. [70, p. 5] specify that "Geoscience is a comprehensive discipline encompassing fields such as geophysics, geology, meteorology, environmental science, etc., with a primary focus on unraveling the complexities of natural processes and phenomena on Earth." Zhang et al. [141] expand this definition, by stating that "geoscience encompasses diverse domains spanning the physical makeup and processes of the Earth," including core the domains **geology, geography, geophysics, hydrology, oceanography, meteorology, and planetary science** [141].

Each branch within geoscience offers insights with the help of observations, data, and models into the Earth system from a different perspective [141]. For instance, geology explores the composition, structure, and history of the Earth's crust and interior, providing valuable information on rock types, plate tectonics, mineral resources, and geologic time [133]. Meteorology concentrates on the atmosphere and atmospheric phenomena like weather patterns, clouds, and precipitation, developing essential knowledge about air masses, fronts, forecasting models, and climate dynamics [9]. Geography examines spatial patterns and processes related to climate change, natural disasters, biodiversity, urbanization, cultural landscapes, and economic development [81]

Generally, geoscience plays a vital role in academia by deepening our knowledge of the connection between humans and the Earth [29, p. 4445]. The cross-domain expertise in geoscience also helps understand the "complex, interconnected processes that shape the Earth and its environments" [141, p. 5].

4.2 Geoscience and NLP

This section explores the relationship between geoscience and NLP, presenting several NLP applications geoscience.

Geoscientists have traditionally employed theoretical and empirical methods to expand their understanding of Earth's systems. According to Lin et al. [70], geoscience-related knowledge is often represented through text like scientific literature, textbooks, patents, or industry standards. Moreover, geoscience publications contain multimodal data, including geographical maps, tables, and era descriptions [29, p. 4445].

With the increasing amount of data produced in modern geoscience research, there is a growing demand for innovative strategies and advanced tools to facilitate

knowledge exploration. Integrating computer science methods and AI technologies into geoscience advances scientific progress and can help tackle global challenges like climate change and natural disaster mitigation. Therefore, effective data collection, information sharing, and dissemination of knowledge in geoscience became a significant issue [70, p. 5].

NLP tools have gained a lot of attention to process a huge amount of textual data. Knowledge systems, such as a Unified Time Framework (UTF), enable the precise and efficient calculations of temporal information across diverse reference frames [132]. Knowledge graphs, like GAKG - a multimodal academic knowledge graph built upon bibliometric components, illustrations, tables, and textual information of 1.12 million geoscience papers - help to illustrate the relationship between geoscience-related entities [29]. Also, semantic models, such as BERT-E, a geoscience-oriented LM generated via transfer learning [104], help to structure the textual geoscience knowledge.

Additionally, geoscientists have tackled more and less complex NLP tasks. By identifying and extracting essential keywords in geoscience documents, Qiu et al. [102] dealt with the challenge of document classification. To address the challenge of topic modeling, rock descriptions, geological ages, lithostratigraphic, and lithogenic information was modified to allow for semantic searches within the data by Lawley et al. [61]. Text mining was used by Qiu et al. [101] to extract and analyze geoscientific entities along with their contextual information in NER. Unstructured text in Chinese was transformed into structured knowledge graph representations of crucial information by Wang et al. [130]. The challenge of question answering was approached by the dialogue model by Deng et al. [31]. They developed PK-Chat, a knowledge-driven generative dialogue model. Ma et al. [80] fine-tuned a BERT model to summarize given input texts and generate titles for given summarization. These NLP tools and applications significantly enhance data acquisition and sharing within the geoscience community.

5 Model

This chapter describes how the most suitable model for domain specialization was chosen and provides an overview of the selected model for further analysis. The models investigated include those published by Meta, i.e. the Llama models and those published by Mistral AI, i.e. the Mistral and Mixtral models. These models were chosen since they are open-source models and available for both research and commercial use ([49], [125]). This allows for retrieving the prompt template, a template each user-input will be embedded in before passing it into the model, and serves as the base for the concept of prompt crafting later in the thesis.

The performance of the Llama and Mistral models serves as benchmark performance in the LLM research community. Figure 5.1 shows the performance of Mistral 7B compared to Llama 2 7B, Llama 2 13B and Llama 1 34B on different benchmarks. The Mistral model seems superior for tasks like solving mathematical equations and coding assistance. The Llama models show superior performance for reasoning and comprehension tasks. However, the smallest model by Llama, Llama 7B, does not perform as well throughout all benchmark classes compared to the Llama 13B and 34B models. The 7B Mistral model does not show these tendencies.

Figure 5.1: Performance of Mistral 7B and different Llama models on various benchmarks. [49, p. 4]

The study's objective is to apply domain specialization to a smaller scale model (either 7B or 13B parameter) since many domain-specialized models have 30B or more parameters and require extensive resources for training, as described in Section 3. Therefore, it was focussed on the performance of the following models provided by Huggingface:

- meta-llama/Llama-2-7b-hf
- meta-llama/Llama-2-13b-hf
- meta-llama/Llama-2-7b-chat-hf
- meta-llama/Llama-2-13b-chat-hf
- mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2
- mistralai/Mixtral-8x7B-Instruct-v0.1
- mistralai/Mixtral-8x7B-v0.1

Note that each token of the Mixtral-8x7B models has access to 47B parameters; however, only 13B are actively used during inference and can process input and generate output at the same speed and for the exact cost as a 13B model [2, 50].

The motivation for comparing these models is to find the most suitable one for the following domain specialization approach. The most suitable model, on the one hand, can already generate quite accurate responses to geoscience questions, i.e., it has a good base knowledge in this field. Conversely, it should also be flexible and perform well on the different NLP tasks included in the SFT dataset while producing coherent and grammatically correct outputs with minimal hallucinations.

5.1 Selection Process

The model selection was performed through human evaluation using twenty prompts randomly sampled from the GeoSignal dataset, consisting of NLP tasks tailored to geoscience applications. Some examples of included tasks are NER for various categories, keyword extraction, summarization, question answering, and text classification (see Section 7.1 for more details). All prompts are listed in the Appendix A.1.1 as well.

For all models, the twenty prompts were used to run inference. During inference, the maximum number of new tokens were limited to 200 per prediction. The predictions were only saved until the first end-of-sequence (EOS) token to prevent undesired padding tokens or padding text from influencing the evaluation. For every model, the prompts, the gold labels retrieved from the SFT dataset, and the generated responses were stored in a CSV file.

Each model was evaluated in three main aspects: language usage, content quality, and adherence to form requirements. The aspects are divided into sub-categories that can be measured with a ternary rating system.

- Language use:
 - Grammatical correctness: Assess whether the generated answer is grammatically correct.
 - Language consistency: Checks if the appropriate language is used. This is usually in English unless it is specified differently in the prompt.
- Content quality:
 - Hallucination detection: Shows if the model generates imagined and/or unrelated information.
 - Content correctness: Determines if the model correctly answers the input prompt.
 - Helpfulness: Assess whether the answer provided is helpful for the user.
- Form compliance:
 - Token limitation: Checks whether the response stays within the predefined maximum new tokens constraint.

Each aspect was rated with zero, one or two, where zero indicates poor performance (such as many grammatical errors, a tremendous number of hallucinations, or exceeding the token limit), and two represent excellent performance (such as flawless grammar, no hallucinations, and adherence to the token limit).

5.1.1 Results

This section presents the human evaluation results conducted during the model selection process. Table 5.1 provides a detailed overview of how each model performed across the investigated aspects. Each column corresponds to an element explained in Section 5.1. Each prompt was evaluated either with zero, one or two, which resulted in a potential maximum score of 40 for any given aspect.

Model	Language use		Content quality			Form
	Gram. correct-ness	Lang. consis-tency	Halluci-nation	Content correct-ness	Helpful-ness	Token limita-tion
Llama-2-7b-hf	31	36	17	7	7	20
Llama-2-13b-hf	40	40	26	9	10	19
Llama-2-7b-chat-hf	37	37	26	25	24	12
Llama-2-13b-chat-hf	40	40	28	26	32	20
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2	39	39	26	26	32	18
Mixtral-8x7B-Instruct-v0.1	40	40	26	23	24	18
Mixtral-8x7B-v0.1	38	38	17	7	6	16

Table 5.1: Overview of the human evaluation results in the model selection process. The maximum value that could have been reached by a model per aspect is 40.

Looking at the table, several observations can be made. In terms of language use, i.e., by assessing whether the grammar is correct and the appropriate language has been used, most models perform well. The Llama-2-7b model is the only expectation with scores that are slightly inferior compared to others.

Content quality aspects, i.e. hallucination detection, content correctness, and helpfulness, show substantial variation. Both the Llama-2-7b model and the Mixtral-8x7B-v0.1 model exhibit poor performance, particularly regarding content correctness and helpfulness (approximately 7 out of 40 points reached). Higher hallucination scores among these models can be explained by their tendency to repeat the prompts instead of responding. This is how they avoid hallucinations while still failing to be helpful. On the other hand, the Llama-2-13b-chat-hf and Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2 model exhibit the best performance among the models, with 26 out of 40 points for content correctness and 32 out of 40 for helpfulness. However, the Llama-2-13b-chat-hf model shows slightly less hallucination than the Mistral model.

For the form compliance, i.e., the frequency of exceeding the token limit, there is not much variation between the models. Approximately half of the generated outputs stay within the threshold.

Summarizing these observations, the Llama-2-13b-chat-hf model demonstrates superior results across all examined aspects. Consequently, this model serves as the base model for the domain specialization approach that will be applied throughout this thesis.

5.2 Llama 2 13B Chat

This section introduces the Llama 2 13B Chat model and its motivation, development process, and performance. Since models like ChatGPT already gained popularity among the general population, the motivation behind the development of the Llama 2 series by Meta was to create effective AI assistants that can handle complex reasoning tasks over multiple areas of expertise [125, p. 3].

The Llama 2 series consists of closed-source LLMs that are fine-tuned to align with human preferences, aiming to improve usability and safety [125, p. 3]. Specifically, Llama 2 Chat models a variant designed for dialogue-like interaction with 7B, 13B, and 70B parameter versions. The development process of the Llama 2 Chat models involved multiple steps. This includes PT with an auto-regressive transformer, training on 40% more total tokens than in Llama 1 (≈ 2 trillion), and increasing the context length from 2k to 4k [125, p. 5]. It took 368,640 GPU hours to train the 13B model [125, p. 7]. Additionally, SFT on publicly available instruction tuning data was performed. Afterwards, RLHF was conducted to further align the model's behavior with human preferences and improve safety [125, 9f.]. Notably, most of the data used in these processes was in English, meaning Llama 2 Chat models will work best for English user inputs [125, p. 22].

In developing the Llama 2 13B Chat model, the focus was set on the model's safety, which is why the evaluation also centered around safety. There were no significant differences in performance between the Llama 2 Chat models 7B, 13B, 30B and 70B. Figure 5.2 shows the percentage how often the rules in three different risk categories were violated: *illicit and criminal activities* (e.g., terrorism, theft, human trafficking), *hateful and harmful activities* (e.g., defamation, self-harm, eating disorders, discrimination) and *unqualified advice* (e.g., medical, financial or legal

Figure 5.2: Violation percentage per risk category based on human annotation [125, p. 31]

advice) [125, p. 23]. Across all categories, the Llama 2 Chat models significantly outperform alternative models such as MPT, Vicuna, and PaLM, while equaling or exceeding Falcon 40b and ChatGPT performances.

Looking at the Llama 2 Chat 13B model specifically, it performed better than the Llama 2 Chat 30B model in every category. Additionally, the 13B model demonstrates superior performance in the *hateful and harmful activities* category compared to all models.

Figure 5.3: Single-turn and multi-turn violation percentage based on human annotation [125, p. 30]

Figure 5.3 illustrates the percentage of safety violations occurring in single versus multi-turn interactions. The Llama 2 Chat models generally perform better compared to other open-source models. The Llama 13B model, specifically, is the model that reaches a safety violation rate below 5% for both single and multiple-turn

conversations. All other Llama 2 Chat models have significantly increased safety violation rates for multi-turn dialogues.

Model	Size	Code	Commonsense Reasoning	World Knowledge	Reading Comprehension	Math	MMLU	BBH	AGI Eval
MPT	7B	20.5	57.4	41.0	57.5	4.9	26.8	31.0	23.5
	30B	28.9	64.9	50.0	64.7	9.1	46.9	38.0	33.8
Falcon	7B	5.6	56.1	42.8	36.0	4.6	26.2	28.0	21.2
	40B	15.2	69.2	56.7	65.7	12.6	55.4	37.1	37.0
LLAMA 1	7B	14.1	60.8	46.2	58.5	6.95	35.1	30.3	23.9
	13B	18.9	66.1	52.6	62.3	10.9	46.9	37.0	33.9
	33B	26.0	70.0	58.4	67.6	21.4	57.8	39.8	41.7
	65B	30.7	70.7	60.5	68.6	30.8	63.4	43.5	47.6
LLAMA 2	7B	16.8	63.9	48.9	61.3	14.6	45.3	32.6	29.3
	13B	24.5	66.9	55.4	65.8	28.7	54.8	39.4	39.1
	34B	27.8	69.9	58.7	68.0	24.2	62.6	44.1	43.4
	70B	37.5	71.9	63.6	69.4	35.2	68.9	51.2	54.2

Figure 5.4: Overall performance on grouped academic benchmarks compared to open-source base models [125, p. 8]

When considering aspects other than safety, Figure 5.4 shows performance results over various academic domains and aggregated benchmarks for the MPT, Falcon, Llama 1, and Llama 2 model series. Overall, larger models yield better results than their smaller versions.

When focusing on Llama 2 Chat 13B, it performs superior over Llama 1 13B across all benchmarks. Additionally, the performance of the Llama 2 Chat 13B model is almost equal to the Falcon 30B model, except for coding tasks where it falls short. However, the Llama 2 Chat 13B model significantly outperforms Falcon 30B in math tasks. Generally, its strengths lie in commonsense reasoning and reading comprehension.

In conclusion, the Llama 2 Chat 13B model performs excellently in terms of helpfulness, harmlessness, and safety and for tasks in areas like commonsense reasoning, world knowledge, reading comprehension, and math. This is why it appears to be a promising candidate for the domain specialisation approach within the geoscience field.

6 PART 1: Prompt Crafting

This chapter focuses on prompt crafting, which involves identifying the prompt template of the model used for domain specialization, i.e. Llama 2 Chat 13B, and applying it to all prompts in the SFT dataset and during inference on the trained model. The prompt template is a "string with placeholders to be filled with the input data" [79, p. 1].

However, as already criticized in Section 2.1.1, there is a lack of clear definitions in the field of Prompting. Specifically, the terms *prompt template* and *prompt pattern* are often used interchangeably. They both refer to modifying or enhancing user inputs before passing them into LLMs. This study follows the definition used in White et al. [136], where prompt patterns describes an approach to establish a prompt's context. There are many approaches to designing prompt patterns, such as a persona prompt (e.g., "You are going to pretend to be a Linux terminal for a computer that an attacker has compromised") or a game play prompt (e.g. "We are going to play a cybersecurity game [...]") [136, p. 17].

A prompt template, however, includes more than establishing a context. It includes embedding the user input into a scaffolding, e.g., by adding BOS and EOS tokens or inserting separating words between instructions, inputs, and responses. The prompt pattern is usually included within the prompt template and called system prompt.

A short proof of concept was conducted through human evaluation, comparing the model's outputs produced with and without prompt templates on a sample of prompts taken from the SFT dataset. The results can be found in Section 6.1 and show significantly improved outcomes when using the template compared to those obtained without it.

The model's performance using different system prompts was tested to enhance the quality of the model's output. System prompts are optional instructions that establish the context and guide the general behavior of LLMs. These instructions "should apply for all the conversation turns" [125, p. 16]. During the selection of system prompts, the emphasis was placed on creating a geoscience question-answering scenario rather than focusing on other factors like safety or helpfulness. An overview of the results can be found in Section 6.2.

Before conducting SFT, the dataset was preprocessed, which involved embedding each SFT dataset prompt and a fix system prompt into a prompt template. During SFT, the prompt template that the model was already familiar with gets enforced instead of establishing a different or no template.

Additionally, after completing the training, the SFT prompt template underwent a slight modification for inference. Lyu et al. [79] showed that including safety statement into the prompt template at inference time helps significantly minimize the risk of harmful behavior and maintain alignment. Details regarding the preprocessing and the inference process after training can be found in Section 6.3.

6.1 Proof of Concept

LLMs are often published with a prompt template that is recommended for interacting with the model at inference time [79]. Although it is widely accepted as beneficial to use these templates for improving the quality of model outputs, there is almost no literature on the impact of applying these prompt templates on all the prompts of the SFT dataset. This highlights the need for further research to determine which pattern/template works best in which use cases and for which specific models.

Current literature often remains vague. For example, prompt templates "significantly enrich the capabilities that can be created in a conversational LLM" and "are generalizable to many different domains" [136, p. 18]. Therefore, a proof of concept was done to investigate whether, in this particular case, embedding user inputs into a prompt template leads to improved model outputs as well.

6.1.1 Method

Firstly, the prompt template was retrieved. Since the Llama models are open-source, the code can be found in the llama-Github-Repository. The user input prompt is separated from the system prompt via `«SYS»\n` and `\n«/SYS» \n \n`. Additionally, the user input prompt and the system prompt together are framed by `[INST]` and `[/INST]`.

The proof of concept was conducted with the help of human evaluation using 50 prompts that were randomly sampled from the GeoSignal dataset. The prompts are listed in Appendix A.1.1. Examples of potential tasks are NER recognition, keyword

extraction or question answering. Section 7.1 contains a more detailed overview of the construction, tasks and the dataset's content.

The Llama 2 Chat 13B model was used for inference. First, the prompts are fed into the model without any modification, and second, the same prompts are used for inference after they have been embedded into the prompt template. No system prompt was used during the proof of concept.

As for the model selection described in Section 5.1, the maximum number of new tokens was set to 200 per prediction. The predictions were only printed until the first occurrence of the EOS token. The prompts, the gold labels retrieved from the SFT dataset, and the generated responses with and without using a prompt template were stored in a CSV file.

The answers generated with and without prompt templates were evaluated as described in Section 5.1. This includes language usage, content quality, and form compliance. The different aspects were rated with zero, one or two, with zero indicating poor performance and two indicating optimal performance. Since 50 prompts were sampled, 100 points can be maximally reached per evaluation category. Additionally, for each prompt, the overall superior answer is noted. This can either be the one with or the one without prompt template usage, or both can be rated as equally good.

6.1.2 Results

Figure 6.1: Human evaluation results of Llama 2 Chat 13B outputs based on 50 samples with and without prompt template

The human evaluation results regarding the outputs produced with and without using a prompt template can be found in Figure 6.1.

The evaluation scores across six different aspects are shown in Figure 6.1a. It becomes clear that the model performs better in all categories whenever the prompt template has been used.

For language use categories, i.e. linguistic consistency and grammatical correctness, the model's performance remains relatively unchanged regardless of whether the prompt was embedded in a prompt template.

However, when focusing on the content quality aspects, the improvement of using the prompt template becomes more visible. Specifically, the most significant improvement can be observed in the category of hallucination detection. When using the prompt template, the model scores 75 out of 100 points, indicating that three-quarters of the responses are free of hallucination. When querying the model without a prompt template, only 63 points were reached. Similar tendencies can be found for the categories of content correctness (71 vs 62 points) and helpfulness (80 vs 73 points) with and without the prompt template.

An explanation of these results is provided in Table 6.1 based on two examples. The first example is a question aiming explaining a dinosaur species — the *Bicentenaria argentina*, an extinct *coelurosaurian theropod* from the early Late Cretaceous of Patagonia in Argentina [91]. Using the prompt template to modify the input, the model correctly identifies it as a fossil but asks for additional context since it cannot provide an answer. On the other hand, the model queried without prompt template generates a long text about the 200th anniversary of Argentina's independence from Spain, which is incorrect and unhelpful and contains extensive hallucination.

In the second example, the prompt refers to the model's personal experiences with Python programming. The response generated using the prompt template informs the user that LLMs are not able to provide information about personal experiences; however, it provides general background information about Python, whereas the output without using a prompt template almost produces a full, exaggerated CV from a first-person perspective.

Although the improvements measured numerically may not appear high, using a prompt template increases the likelihood of generating more helpful and accurate responses with less hallucination.

Looking at the win rate depicted in Figure 6.1b, the model queried with the prompt template generally performs better than the one without the template in 17 out of 50 instances. In contrast, the opposite results can be found in only 9 out of 50 comparisons. The answers demonstrate comparable quality in about half of the cases (24 out of 50). This means that in 82% of the cases, the answer provided with the template is either superior or simple to those given without the template. One can conclude that using the prompt template proofs is a helpful tendency towards generating more accurate and valuable responses. Thus, prompt templates will be applied to all prompts of the SFT dataset.

prompt	prediction with template	prediction without template
Could you clarify the timescale of the Bicentenario argentina for me?	I'm not aware of a fossil species called ""Bicentenario argentina"". Could you provide more information or context about this species, such as where it was found or when it lived? This will help me better understand your question and provide a more accurate answer.	Certainly! The Bicentenario argentina is a celebration of Argentina's bicentenary, or 200th anniversary of independence from Spain. The country gained independence on July 9, 1816, so the bicentenary falls on July 9, 2016. [...]
Tell me about your experience with Python programming	As an AI language model, I have not personally performed Python programming; however, many of the developers who created me and maintain my programming have extensive experience working with Python. Python is a very popular high-level, interpreted programming language [...]	Sure, I'd be happy to share my experience with Python programming! I've been working with Python for about 5 years now, and I have to say that it's been an incredible journey. I started out with some online tutorials and courses, and then gradually moved on to more advanced topics like machine learning, data analysis, and web development. [...]

Table 6.1: Outputs generated with and without using a prompt template

6.2 Selection of a system prompt

The selection of system prompts is a non-trivial task since the influence of a particular prompt pattern on the model's performance highly depends on both the model itself and the specific task and user input prompt. This is why it is essential to test a large variety of prompts and evaluate the improvements or declines in performance they cause. Subsection 6.2.1 describes how the different system prompts were created, and their impact on the model's performance is discussed in Subsection 6.2.2.

6.2.1 Method

An iterative process was followed to select the system prompt that improves performance the most.

Initially, the catalog of different prompt patterns provided by White et al. [136] was examined to create system prompts suitable for setting up a geoscience QA context. The goal was to cover various patterns to get an impression of how well the individual patterns work. The seven prompts created are:

1. You are a geoscience expert.
2. Act as an expert in geoscience and answer the following question.
3. Answer the following question with your geoscience expertise.
4. Provide outputs that a geoscience professor would create.
5. Whenever you generate an answer to a geoscience question, explain the reasoning and assumptions behind your answer.
6. Whenever you cannot answer a geoscientific question, explain why you cannot answer the question.
7. You are an expert in geology, geography, and environmental science.

These prompts cover, e.g. Persona Pattern as in the first and second one, Reflection Pattern as in the fifth and the Refusal Breaker Pattern as in the sixth prompt. Since the geoscience domain is rather specific, a system prompt using geology, geography, and environmental science was also included.

After creating the system prompts, they were embedded in the prompt template together with the same twenty user input prompts that were used for the model

selection process and the proof of concept (Appendix A.1.1). This helps ensure the results' comparability. Inference was then conducted using the same settings described in Sections 5.1 and 6.1.1.

The responses were compared to those generated during the proof of concept using the prompt template without a system prompt to evaluate each system prompt according to its influence on the responses. Each prompt was rated either with + (for better performance than without system prompt), = (equivalent performance), or - (worse performance). The system prompts were compared based on the absolute frequency counts of +, =, and -.

After finding the most suitable system prompt, a new set of prompts was designed in a similar style and pattern. The entire process was repeated until the system prompts showed no further improvement. An overview of all system prompts used can be found in Table 6.2.

Finally, the system prompt with the highest rating in human evaluation was selected for further prompt crafting.

6.2.2 Results

Table 6.2 provides an overview of the results generated by testing various system prompts that set up a geoscience QA scenario. The table shows the results of four complete iteration cycles (as described in Subsection 6.2.1) separated by horizontal lines. Each iteration contains a set of multiple system prompts. More detailed insights into the rating decisions can be found in the GitHub repository of this thesis.

no.	prompt	+	=	-
1	You are a geoscience expert.	1	9	10
2	Act as an expert in geoscience and answer the following question.	4	9	7
3	Answer the following question with your geoscience expertise.	1	11	8
4	Provide outputs that a geoscience professor would create.	1	11	8
5	Whenever you generate an answer to a geoscience question explain the reasoning and assumptions behind your answer.	3	8	9

6	Whenever you can't answer a geoscience question explain why you can't answer the question.	3	5	12
7	You are an expert in geology, geography and environmental science.	3	11	6
8	Please answer the questions related to geoscience.	5	12	3
9	Please use your geoscience knowledge to answer the questions.	1	12	7
10	Please answer the following geoscience question.	3	14	3
11	Your job is to answer the following question related to geoscience.	1	14	5
12	Do your best to answer the following geoscience question.	1	11	8
13	Take your time to answer the geoscience question.	1	14	5
14	You are a natural scientist.	4	12	4
15	Activate your science knowledge to answer the following question.	2	13	5
16	You are an earth scientist and use your knowledge to answer this question:	1	14	5

Table 6.2: Human evaluation results for twenty user prompts with different system prompts. + indicating better performance than without system prompt, = equivalent performance, and - worse performance.

For the initial run, the results throughout all prompts were not promising. System prompts based on persona patterns, e.g. prompt one, two or seven, primarily caused responses starting with "As an expert in geoscience, ..." for the second prompt or "As an expert in geology, geography, and environmental science, ..." for the seventh system prompt. These prompts led to some changes in response content as well as increased instances of hallucinations and incorrect answers. For example, when the model was queried with "Identify which instrument is string or percussion: Kenong, Zeze", the response with prompt 7 was ""As an expert in geology, geography, and environmental science, I can tell you that ""Kenong"" and ""Zeze"" are not instruments, but rather place names or locations. [...]". The response generated using a persona pattern system prompt does not provide a correct answer, whereas the answer generated without any system prompt was correct.

System prompt 4 demonstrated extensive hallucinations. For example, to a user prompt that asks for a synonym for a specific dinosaur clade, the model generates:

"Ah, a curious student! Let me see... Hmm... Ah ha! I have it! A synonym for "coelurosaurs" is... (drumroll please)... "feathered dinosaurs"! Now, if you'll excuse me, I must return to my research on the tectonic evolution of the Himalayan mountain range. Fascinating stuff, if I do say so myself! But wait, what's that you say? You want to know more about coelurosaurs? Oh my, you're in for a treat! These fascinating creatures were a diverse group of theropod dinosaurs that included the likes of Velociraptor, Oviraptor, and of course, the iconic Micror."

The response is not only incorrect but also not scientific and in a serious tone anymore. In the case of system prompt 6 using the refusal breaker pattern, 13 out of 20 answers started with *"I can't answer this question"* or similar phrasings, which significantly impacted the overall usefulness and helpfulness of the generated responses.

The model shows a lot of hallucination for the reflection pattern in system prompt 5. For example, for a user input prompt that asks for papers about a particular mineral, the model generated that it cannot provide any papers regarding that mineral without any system prompt, whereas the model's output using this system prompt lists non-existing papers.

Generally, using a system prompt caused a lengthening of the generated answers, almost always beyond the token limits.

Prompts 7 and 8 were tested to address these issues, which are not created based on a classical pattern recommended for system prompts. Instead, they are direct instructions that do not ask the model to play a specific role.

Surprisingly, prompt 8 achieved better results. Looking at the user input query that asks for papers about a particular mineral as an example again, instead of refusing to answer the question or not providing an answer at all, the model can now generate a list of sources where the user can find the answer instead.

"[...] Armillinoite-(Ce) is a rare mineral that is not well studied, and there may not be many papers specifically dedicated to it. However, I can suggest a few resources that may be helpful: 1. Mindat.org [...] 2. Webmineral.com: [...] 3. The Mineralogical Society of America: [...]."

Since prompt 8 worked better than the prompts tested before, similar prompts (10-13) were tested and evaluated. However, none of them were able to produce good results. For instance, one user input prompt was to *create a cocktail recipe*. Using prompt 12 as a system prompt produced the answer

"Sure, I'd be happy to help with both! Here's my best answer to the geoscience question and a cocktail recipe: Geoscience Question: What is the process by which the Earth's plates move and how does it affect the Earth's surface features? The process by which the Earth's plates move is called plate tectonics. [...]"

The model raises a question that is not related to the user input prompt in any way to answers that question instead of the actual user input prompt. This behavior drastically limits helpfulness.

Lastly, a set of system prompts was created that not specifically referenced geoscience but included more general domains like natural sciences and science in general. The motivation behind this was to exclude the possibility that using the rather specific geoscience domain as a context negatively influenced the results. However, this adjustment did not significantly improve model's behavior. The results were quite similar to those generated without system prompt. The negative/positive ratings were only caused due to, e.g., producing overly long text and rambling, and not due to context-wise adjustments.

Overall, prompt 8 *"Please answer the questions related to geoscience."* was the most effective system prompt, with the most answers rated with a + and the least rated with a -. Instead of either rejecting to answer a prompt or hallucinating, it enhanced the quality of model outputs by suggesting sources for the user to find a correct answer if it could not provide any. This is why system prompt 8 was used to modify the SFT dataset prompts.

6.3 Application of the Prompt Template

In this section, the goal was to use the prompt template and a system prompt for each entry within the SFT dataset, i.e. the GeoSignal dataset. Additionally, the setup for inference was established after SFT and RLHF.

After testing different system prompts (Section 6.2), the prompt that showed the most significant performance increase was chosen. Subsection 6.3.1 describes the

proceeding for embedding every SFT dataset prompt and the chosen system prompt into the prompt template recommended for the Llama 2 13B Chat model.

Subsection 6.3.2 describes the inference process after SFT and RLHF since a different system prompt is used for inference. However, the prompt template itself was not modified.

6.3.1 Prompt Template during SFT

The GeoSignal dataset was created to specialize an LLM in the geoscience domain in the study by Deng et al. [30] and used for SFT in Lin et al. [70]. It contains 39,700 prompts that are mostly related to the field of geoscience [30, p. 3]. The GeoSignal dataset was uploaded on HuggingFace and in the form of a JSON file on the GitHub repository of the paper [30]. Both sources contain identical data.

In this thesis, Deng et al. retrieved the GeoSignal JSON file from the GitHub repository. However, some adjustments were necessary. While the prompt template recommended for the Llama 13B Chat model only distinguishes between a system prompt and a user input prompt, the GeoSignal dataset contains two separate columns for the user input prompt - the *instruction* column and the *input* column. An instruction can be something like "Make a list of things that come to mind when you think of the given place." the input would be, e.g. "Place: San Francisco."

To solve this issue, the content of the instruction and input columns were concatenated prompt-wise, combining them into a single user input prompt. Additionally, the system prompt *Please answer the questions related to geoscience* was added to the template. After the prompt template containing the system prompts along with the concatenated instruction and input components of the user input prompt, all prompts had the same format:

```
<s>[INST] «SYS» \n Please answer the questions related to geoscience. \n «/SYS» \n
      {user input prompt} [/INST]</s>.
```

Lastly, the entire SFT dataset was locally stored in two formats. On the one hand, it is a Python pickle file that can be reloaded for SFT. On the other side, it was stored as a CSV file to manually look at the dataset in table format as well.

6.3.2 Prompt Template during inference

It is known to be "conventional wisdom" [136, p. 4] that training and testing environments as similar as possible yield the best results. Nonetheless, in this thesis, the prompt template used for SFT data and the one during inference diverge.

White et al. [136] investigated the impact of various prompt templates and different system prompts on the behavioral changes of Llama 2 models. The focus is placed on how the model's behavior changes using the same prompt template for SFT and inference versus using different prompt templates.

They showed that using identical prompt templates for SFT and inference "breaks the safety alignment to a large extent" [136, p. 2].

The Llama 2 13B Chat prompt template comes along with a system prompt regarding the safety of the outputs that were used originally in setting this model up: "You are a helpful, respectful and honest assistant. Always answer as helpfully as possible while being safe. Your answers should not include any harmful, unethical, racist, sexist, toxic, dangerous, or illegal content. Please ensure that your responses are socially unbiased and positive. If a question does not make any sense or is not factually coherent, explain why instead of answering something that is not correct. If you don't know the answer to a question, please don't share false information." [125, p. 56]. Applying this safety prompt throughout SFT and inference might appear intuitive. However, fine-tuning a Llama model using this safety prompt significantly increased the Attack Success Rate (ASR) from 0.42% to 18.08% on the DirectHarm4 dataset [136, p. 4].

To address this issue, White et al. proved that "Pure Tuning, Safe Testing (PTST)" is the best way to fine-tune a model. PTST refers to fine-tuning a model without using a safety prompt but adding this safety prompt during inference. Moreover, they were able to show that prompt templates where the whole prompt is wrapped between *[INST]* and *[/INST]* produce generally safer results than not wrapping the prompts [136, p. 4].

However, the question remains whether the SFT system prompt (*Please answer the questions related to geoscience*) should be entirely replaced by the safety prompt during inference or if these two system prompts should be concatenated.

Applying PTST to ChatDoctor [66], a fine-tuned version of the Llama 2 7B model which was trained to give medical advice, proved efficient. During SFT, the system

prompt "You are a doctor. Please answer the medical questions based on the patient's description." was enforced. In contrast, it was beneficial to prepend the safety prompt before the system prompt for inference.

Based on their findings, the following prompt template will be used during inference on the fine-tuned model:

```
<s>[INST] «SYS» \n You are a helpful, respectful and honest assistant. Always answer as helpfully as possible, while being safe. Your answers should not include any harmful, unethical, racist, sexist, toxic, dangerous, or illegal content. Please ensure that your responses are socially unbiased and positive in nature. If a question does not make any sense, or is not factually coherent, explain why instead of answering something not correct. If you don't know the answer to a question, please don't share false information. \n Please answer the questions related to geoscience. \n «/SYS» \n {user input prompt} [/INST]</s>.
```


7 PART 2: Supervised Fine-Tuning

Section 2.2.1 discusses Supervised Fine-Tuning as the most crucial and commonly used approach for adapting LLMs to particular tasks and domains. In this thesis, SFT plays an essential role in the process of domain specialization as well.

SFT aims to create a model that can correctly answer geoscience-related questions while, ideally, improving upon the base model's performance. The last part of the domain specialisation process in this thesis, Reinforcement Learning (Chapter 8), then serves to further improve the model's helpfulness and refine some speech characteristics and language style.

Figure 7.1: Domain specialisation proceeding by Deng et al. [30, p. 6]

The initial idea was to use the GeoSignal dataset introduced by Deng et al. [30] for a single round of SFT. However, the dataset offers prompts designed for general instruction as well as those particularly aimed at geoscientific QA. Detailed information about the dataset can be found in Section 7.1.

Figure 7.1 depicts the SFT strategy employed by Deng et al. [30]. First, they use the general instruction data to align the model's performance with human QA abilities. Second, they fine-tuned the model with the geoscientific portion of the dataset to align it with geoscience expert knowledge and QA skills tailored to geoscience questions. According to their findings, "first conducting general instruction learning followed by knowledge-intensive instruction learning helped enhance the performance [...], far surpassing the results obtained from mixed training" [30, p. 7].

Following this approach, to specialize the Llama 2 13B Chat model to the domain of geoscience, two rounds of SFT were conducted, one for human-alignment and one for expert-alignment.

Before executing these two rounds of SFT, the datasets were preprocessed, and hyperparameters and quantization configurations were tested. The procedures are described in Section 7.2. Additional implementation details and hardware require-

ments can be found in Section 7.3. Due to screwed-up results after the initial attempt of SFT for human-alignment, Section 7.4 discusses adjustments made to the SFT implementation as well as changes in hyperparameter and quantization settings to optimize the SFT outcome. Chapter 9 presents and evaluates the impact of SFT on the model's overall performance.

7.1 Data: GeoSignal

The GeoSignal dataset developed by Deng et al. [30] and used for SFT will be presented in this section. It is the first geoscience-supervised instruction tuning dataset published [30, p. 2]. The dataset combines two main components: general instruction tuning data and specific geoscience knowledge. The instruction tuning data serves the purpose of training the model to correctly react to user input prompts, i.e. to align with humans [30, p. 3]. However, "more than learning to follow human instruction is needed for the specialized domain" [30, p. 4]. This is why the knowledge-intensive geoscience data is used to further optimize the model to answer geoscience questions, i.e., align with experts [30, p. 4].

Firstly, the general instruction tuning data covers a wide range of tasks from various sources, such as Natural Instructions [87], AI2 Reasoning Challenge [23], Stanford Alpaca [122], and Dolly-15k [24]. These tasks include but are not limited to brainstorming, classification, open and closed QA, question and answer generation, modification, information extraction, summarization, multiple-choice, verification, etc. This part of the data improves the model's ability to understand and respond accurately to users' inputs.

Figure 7.2: Components of the Align-to-Expert part of the GeoSignal Dataset [30, p. 5]

Secondly, geoscience-specific knowledge helps enable the model to perform well for questions related to the geoscience domain. This part includes data from various

online sources, which are shown in Figure 7.2 and explained in detail by Deng et al. [30, p. 4]. The data includes geoscience academic knowledge graphs (GAKG), academic literature, ontology data, data taken from question and answer platforms, and questions and answer pairs generated by GPT4, along with other geoscience datasets and repositories. Deng et al. [30] used this data as the base to create various prompts for different NLP tasks related to geoscience. For example, the data includes abstracts and titles of papers related to the field of geoscience, which are used to create prompts for a title generation task based on an abstract. The human alignment and expert alignment data combined form the complete GeoSignal dataset.

The dataset can be found on HuggingFace and as a JSON file on GitHub. It contains the following columns: instruction, input, output, type and category. The *instruction* column contains a concrete instruction, e.g. *List the 6 naturally occurring noble gases*. The *input* column provides additional material needed to follow the instructions, such as a paragraph with information about noble gases. The *output* column consists of the desired answers, i.e. *The six naturally occurring noble gases are: 1. Helium (He) 2. Neon (Ne) 3. Argon (Ar) 4. Krypton (Kr) 5. Xenon (Xe) 6. Radon (Rn)*. The columns *category* and *type* refer to the sources from which the prompt was extracted. The *type*-labels *alpaca-gpt4*, *NI*, *arc* and *dolly* indicate that the prompts contain general instruction data, whereas the labels *geoqa*, *self* and *geo* point at specific geoscience knowledge prompts. The *category* has more fine-grained information about the source as in Figure 7.2, e.g. *gso.wikipedia.entity*.

In summary, GeoSignal covers various task categories which are shown in Figure 7.3. The QA tasks make up approximately half of the prompts, followed by fact verification and explanation tasks. Each category includes several types of sub-tasks, e.g., explanation tasks can either refer to explaining a certain term, concept, structure, proceeding, etc.

Looking at the distribution of the instruction tuning and geoscience data in the overall dataset, out of the 39749 prompts, 21516 prompts (approximately 54%) are geoscience expert data. In comparison, 18233 prompts (approximately 46%) are instruction tuning data. The dataset is well-balanced between human and expert alignment; however, it shows a slight tendency towards expert knowledge.

Tasks	Records	Total (Cleaned)
Named Entity Recognition	6,252,268	2,400
Reasoning	1,200	600
Fact Verification	168,424	8,000
Summarization	3,279,336	800
Text Classification	8,313	2,000
Word Semantics	826,194	6,400
Explanation	731,374	4,200
Question Answering	11,360,163	15,349
Entire GeoSignal	22,627,272	39,749

Figure 7.3: Statistics of GeoSignal categorized by task [30, p. 5]

7.2 Experimental Setup

In this section, the focus lays on setting up the SFT for geoscience domain specialization. The setup process includes the data preparation as described in Subsection 7.2.1. The dataset was divided into two parts, one for alignment with humans and the other for geoscience expert alignment. Additionally, the two datasets were split into training and validation sets.

As the important part of SFT, the hyperparameter determination is outlined in Subsection 7.2.2. Using the hyperparameters suggested by Pytorch [100] as a foundation, extensive tests were conducted to optimize the learning rate, batch size, and number of epochs for this particular domain specialization approach.

Generally, the SFT will be executed using the Parameter Efficient Finetuning (PEFT) approach LoRa [46]. An explanation of the LoRa settings chosen for SFT can be found in Subsection 7.2.3.

7.2.1 Data preparation

Since two rounds of SFT will be conducted for the Llama 2 13B Chat model, two separate datasets are required, one dataset is needed for general instruction tuning, while the other focuses on alignment with experts via geoscience-specific instruction data. GeoSignal contains a column specifying the prompt type. The labels *dolly*, *alpaca-gpt4*, *arc*, and *NI* indicate general instruction tuning data, e.g. *Give me a list of the best true crime podcast to listen to*. On the other hand, the labels *geoqa*, *self*, and *geo* refer to geoscience-specific prompts like *What geophysical methods are currently used for short-term earthquake prediction?*. To follow Deng et al. [30]

and first, ensure alignment with humans and afterwards focus on the alignment with domain experts; the dataset has been divided into two sections based on these labels.

Each dataset is further split into three subsets for SFT: training, testing, and validation sets. Initially, a 90% train and 10% test split was performed. Afterwards, a 10% split from the 90% train subset is taken as the validation set. The splits were not randomly selected; however, stratified sampling based on different prompt types described above was implemented. For example, prompts labeled with *arc* typically refer to multiple-choice science questions, while *dolly* is an indicator for summarization tasks (among others). Stratified sampling should, therefore, ensure that all the different types of instructions appear proportionally across the train, test, and validation sets. The absolute count of prompts within each dataset and split can be found in Table 7.1.

Additionally, a new column was added to the dataset. Since the SFTTrainer provided in the trl library [135] will be used to execute the SFT, defining the parameter *dataset_text_field* is necessary. It takes a dataset column as input that contains all the relevant information for SFT, i.e., the instructions, inputs, and outputs. The instruction and input have already been embedded in a prompt template, described in Section 6.3.1. This is why the output will be integrated into the prompt template too, at the end between `[INST]` and `</s>`. An input example used for SFT looks like this:

```
<s>[INST] «SYS» \n Please answer the questions related to geoscience. \n «/SYS» \n
  Could you share the magnitude of the M 6.7 - 62 km SSW of Maunaloa, Hawaii?
[/INST] The M 6.7 - 62 km SSW of Maunaloa, Hawaii's magnitude is 6.66 Mw. </s>.
```

	overall	train	test	validation
human-alignment	18.2k	14.8k	1.8k	1.6k
expert-alignment	21.5k	17.4k	2.2k	1.9k

Table 7.1: The table shows the absolute number of prompts included in the overall train, test and validation set for the datasets used for human-alignment and expert-alignment

7.2.2 Hyperparameter determination

Fine-tuning LLMs like Llama 2 has gained significant attention in the past, and a lot of literature and how-to guides have been published. However, they primarily focus on fine-tuning Llama 2 7B models (e.g. [6], [111], [83], [84]), and less emphasis has been placed on fine-tuning Llama 2 13B Chat models. Still, it remains essential to choose hyperparameters for fine-tuning tailored to the underlying model and intended use case. This section, therefore, provides an overview of the hyperparameter determination for SFT.

To fine-tune the Llama 2 Chat 13B model, Meta [83] suggests to use the `torch tune` library developed and published by PyTorch [100] for orientation. `torch tune` was explicitly designed for authoring, fine-tuning, and experimentation with LLMs, supporting various models, including Llama 13B [100]. The open-source GitHub repository of `torch tune` contains numerous recipes (including hyperparameters) for full fine-tuning and small-scale fine-tuning using LoRA [46] or QLoRA [32] for quantization. Additionally, `torch tune` offers information for either using a single device (with low memory) or multiple devices.

Many of the hyperparameters for fine-tuning a Llama 2 13B model suggested in the `torch tune` library align with the settings employed during the initial fine-tuning by Meta [125]. These include, e.g. using the AdamW [77] optimizer and a cosine learning rate scheduler.

Since SFT can be "very sensitive to the choice of learning rate" [46, p. 21], some experiments were conducted to confirm that the learning rate suggested in the `torch tune` library, i.e. $2e-04$ [100], would also yield good results for geosciences domain specialization using the GeoSignal dataset. Besides the learning rate, the batch size and the number of epochs were also investigated to ensure that the individual requirements for geosciences domain specialisation are met.

Learning Rate

When fine-tuning the Llama 2 Chat 13B model, `torch tune` proposed a learning rate of $2e-4$ [100], whereas Meta used a learning rate of $2e-5$ during the original SFT [125]. However, given that both sources recommended the use of a cosine learning rate scheduler to reduce the learning rate over time, the suggested start learning rates appear relatively small. When using a learning rate scheduler, a larger initial learning

rate proved optimal since the learning rate will likely decrease further during training [121]. In his how-to guide, Tam [121] even employs a start learning rate of 0.1.

To get insights into the influence of the learning rate on the model's performance, a small-scale SFT for various learning rates using the hyperparameter and LoRa settings provided by torchtune was executed. Two hundred prompts were randomly sampled from the Geosignal dataset as a training set and another 200 as a validation set. The loss was monitored throughout the experiments to identify the ideal learning rate. The range of tested learning rates was iteratively extended, i.e. since it was observed, for example, that learning rates with 5 decimal places showed higher losses, learning rates with 4 decimal places were tested.

Initially, the approach was plotting the training loss values over the learning rates, as further outlined in Appendix A.2.1. However, this proceeding yielded no helpful results. Consequently, a new approach was adopted where the evaluation loss at 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% progress of the small-scale FT was measured, and the corresponding values were plotted. A straight line was then fitted through these points for every learning rate. The learning rate associated with the most significant negative slope was considered the most promising, as a significant and consistent decrease in loss potentially indicates effective learning. The measured loss values and all plots can also be found in Appendix A.2.1.

The initial test involved running small-scale SFT for twelve learning rates, i.e. $1e-03$, $2e-03$, $3e-03$, $4e-03$, $1e-04$, $2e-04$, $3e-04$, $4e-04$, $1e-05$, $2e-05$, $3e-05$ and $4e-05$. The learning rates with fewer decimal places showed smaller absolute evaluation loss values and steeper slopes. Specifically, $4e-03$ produced the best results. Based on these findings, another round of tests was conducted using only learning rates with three decimal places, i.e. $4e-03$, $5e-03$, $6e-03$, $7e-03$, $8e-03$, and $9e-03$. Again, the highest learning rate ($9e-03$) produced both the lowest evaluation loss and the steepest slope.

Next, learning rates with two decimal places, i.e., 0.01, 0.03, 0.05, and 0.07 were examined. Among these, 0.01 displayed the steepest slope. For learning rates larger than 0.01, the evaluation loss values were highly scattered, making calculating a representative slope difficult. For example, a learning rate of 0.07 had an almost horizontal line as the best fit. Based on these results, a starting learning rate of 0.01 and a cosine learning rate scheduler seemed to provide the best performance.

To validate this approach and exclude the possibility that a learning rate of 0.01, only mathematically appears as the best option, ten prompts from the Geosignal dataset were sampled and two models, one small-scale fine-tuned with a learning rate of 0.01 and the other one with a learning rate $2e-04$ was queried with those prompts. The textual outputs were manually compared to judge their output quality. Both models demonstrated comparable performance. Four out of ten answers generated with a learning rate of 0.01 were preferred in the human rating, four times the answers generated with a learning rate of $2e-04$ were superior. In two cases, the performance was completely equal.

However, slight differences were noted between the two learning rates regarding their impact on NER and MC tasks. The model with the learning rate of 0.01 tended to underperform in NER tasks, e.g., in a passage about film music, the model was asked to extract all geoscience-related words. The 0.01 model found 39 words pertaining to geoscience, while the $2e-04$ model correctly stated that there are no geoscience-related words in this passage. However, the model trained with a lower learning rate showed reduced performance in MC tasks. For example, when asked if two instruments, Kenong and Zeze, are a percussion or a string instrument, the 0.01 gave a correct answer. In contrast, the $2e-04$ model made the wrong classification for both instruments. These tendencies can be found throughout all the NER and MC tasks in the ten samples. More detailed insights into the rating decisions can be found in the GitHub repository of this thesis.

Finally, considering the overall performance across all tasks and the loss development, a learning rate of 0.01 will be used for fine-tuning, deviating from the torchtune recommendations.

Batch size

The torchtune library suggests using a batch size of two for fine-tuning the Llama 2 Chat 13B model [100]. In contrast, Meta's first SFT of the Llama 2 models applied a batch size of 64 [125, p. 9]. Since there is such a significant discrepancy in batch sizes, a similar approach to the one for determining the optimal learning rate was followed to explore the impact of various batch sizes on performance.

Multiple rounds of small-scale SFT were conducted using the hyperparameter and LoRA settings suggested by torchtune [100] and a learning rate of 0.01. A different

batch size was used for each SFT. The experiments were done for the 2, 4, 8, 16, and 32 batch sizes. The evaluation loss was monitored throughout the SFTs.

Figure 7.4: For the different batch sizes 2, 4, 8, 16 and 32, the development of the evaluation loss of small-scale SFT experiments is plotted over steps

fine-tuning on such a small sample of the SFT data. Based on these findings, the recommendation of a batch size of two from the torchtune library will be followed.

Number of epochs

Both Pytorch [100] and Touvron et al. [125] suggest employing a relatively low number of epochs, i.e. one and two. Following determining the batch size and learning rates, four small-scale SFT experiments were executed under the same conditions as before.

In the first experiment, the number of epochs was set to 15 to get an overview of the evaluation loss development. This made it possible to define an epoch until the loss stays small before a noticeable increase. Figure 7.5a depicts the evaluation loss curve over 15 epochs. Although the density of evaluation loss points is scarce, it becomes evident that extending the number of epochs beyond six does not yield promising

The evaluation loss was plotted over the SFT steps for each batch size. Figure 7.4 depicts the outcome of these experiments. Due to the influence of the batch size on the total number of steps within a single SFT run, the plots vary in size.

It becomes evident that the smaller the batch size is, the lower the observed loss values are, and the greater the overall loss reduction. It appears that adopting a batch size of two yields the smallest loss values and the best loss decline during

results. Specifically, the model will struggle to apply the acquired knowledge from the SFT data to unseen input prompts effectively.

Based on these findings, a second experiment was conducted. The number of epochs was set to six, and the density of loss measurements was increased. Figure 7.5b plots the evaluation loss and training loss curves. The plot of training loss continuously decreases over all epochs. In contrast, the plot of the validation loss decreases together with the training loss curve until epoch two stabilizes and slowly increases again at epoch four. This is a clear sign of overfitting, i.e. the model loses its ability to generalize to new data.

The only significant decrease in evaluation loss is observable for the first two epochs. Therefore, two further small-scale SFTs were executed, using one epoch (Figure 7.5c) and two epochs (Figure 7.5d). The train and the evaluation loss decrease steadily for two epochs, while the training loss is slightly higher than the validation loss. For one epoch, the training loss increases significantly before it decreases together with the evaluation loss. Although the loss curves for two epochs show a slight tendency towards underfitting, they appear to be a better fit than one epoch. Based on this analysis, the number of epochs for the SFT will be set to two, as in [125].

7.2.3 Quantization

As the size of LLMs increases, so does the cost, time, and memory required for full fine-tuning, where all model parameters are updated based on the unseen SFT data. Full fine-tuning can, therefore, become extremely expensive [46, p. 1]. To address this challenge, the research focus has shifted towards developing PEFT methods that allow for more targeted updates to the model parameters while minimizing the computational resources needed.

The current SOTA PEFT approach is applying Low-Rank Adapter (LoRA) Fine-Tuning [46] or Low-Rank Adapter Fine-Tuning for Quantized LLMs (QLoRA) [32]. LoRA Fine-Tuning is "a method that reduces memory requirements by using a small set of trainable parameters, often termed adapters, while not updating the full model parameters which remain fixed." [32, p. 3]

In comparison to traditional PEFT methods, LoRA has several advantages. Firstly, it does not show any additional inference latency or reduces the input sequence

(a) First test: Setting the number of epochs to 15

(b) Second test: Setting the number of epochs to 6

(c) Third test: Setting the number of epochs to 2

(d) Fourth test: Setting the number of epochs to 1

Figure 7.5: Development of the loss over different numbers of epochs

length, to ensure that the model maintains its original high-quality performance [46, p. 12]. Secondly, fine-tuning with LoRA significantly reduce memory requirements and storage usage and speeds up the SFT by about 25% [46, p. 5].

Table 7.2 presents an overview of all available layers in the Llama 2 13B Chat model and their parameter number. Originally, Hu et al. [46] focused on optimizing the query, key, value and output projection layers within the self-attention module only (row 1-4 in 7.2). It is still common practice to optimize these layers during SFT. However, recent research by Dettmers et al. [32] revealed that applying LoRA to all linear layers achieves better results when only taking the self-attention module layers into account and results equal to those obtained through full fine-tuning (p.6). Pytorch [100] also recommends optimizing all linear layers within the self-attention and multilayer perceptron module, along with the lm_head Linear layer, to ensure optimal performance.

Layer name	Layer type	Parameter	No. of occurrences
self_attn.q_proj	Linear	13.1M	40
self_attn.k_proj	Linear	13.1M	40
self_attn.v_proj	Linear	13.1M	40
self_attn.o_proj	Linear	13.1M	40
mlp.up_proj	Linear	35.4M	40
mlp.down_proj	Linear	35.4M	40
mlp.gate_proj	Linear	35.4M	40
input_layernorm	RMS normalization	0.0M	40
post_attention_layernorm	RMS normalization	0.0M	40
norm	RMS normalization	0.0M	1
embed_tokens	Embedding	163.8M	1
lm_head	Linear	163.8M	1

Table 7.2: List all layers in the Llama 2 13B Chat model and their number of parameters. q = query, k = key, v = value, o = output, proj = projection, self_attn = self attention, mlp = multilayer perceptron, norm = normalization

Additionally, Dettmers et al. [32] discovered that "other LoRA hyperparameters, such as the projection dimension r , do not affect performance" (p.6). Based on this finding, the hyperparameter settings proposed by Pytorch [100] – namely, $r=8$, $\alpha=16$, and $\text{dropout}=0.05$ – were adapted without conducting further tests.

7.3 Technical Implementation

This section gives further inside into how the SFT was implemented and executed. Subsection 7.3.1 provides an overview of the implementation details. This includes, e.g., a description of how the trainer instance for Fine-Tuning was set up and details on the model-saving process. In Subsection 7.3.2, the hardware requirements for executing the SFT are discussed.

7.3.1 Implementation details

Before starting the SFT, the Llama 2 13B Chat model and its corresponding tokenizer were downloaded from Huggingface. The data, i.e., training, testing, and validation splits for human and expert alignment, has been stored in pickle (.pkl) files during the preprocessing. However, it additionally needs to be converted into Dataset format

to become compatible with the base model and the trainer during SFT.

All parameters related to quantization with LoRA are stored in an instance of Huggingface's `LoraConfig` class. Additionally, an instance of the Transformers' `TrainingArguments` class was used to save all further hyperparameters during the training process.

To execute SFT, a trainer was set up, i.e., an instance of the `SFTTrainer` class offered by Huggingface through their TRL library [135]. This trainer accepts the model, the tokenizer, the `TrainingArguments` object, the `LoraConfig` object, and the train and validation datasets as input. Furthermore, a `max_seq_length` parameter can also be defined to limit the number of tokens generated by the model. Following Lin et al. [70], the number of tokens was limited to 512 to minimize unwanted computational overhead.

After the SFT is finished, the log history of the trainer instance gets saved in a plain text (.txt) file since it contains all checkpoints of the evaluation and training loss values. Moreover, the training and evaluation losses plot is produced based on the log history and saved as image (in .png format).

Additionally, the model is stored in two ways: as a checkpoint and a standalone model. To save the model as a checkpoint, the `save_model()` method available through the **SFTTrainer** can be used. The checkpoint consumes less memory; however, needs to be applied to the Llama 2 13B Chat base model for inference and/or further fine-tuning. To save the model as a standalone model directly, the quantized LoRa layers should be merged into the base model. This can be achieved with the help of the model's `merge_and_unload()` method. Once the merging is done, the standalone model can be saved via the **model's** `save_pretrained()` method.

7.3.2 Hardware details

The High-Performance Computing, Data Intensive Computing, and Large Scale Scientific Data Management infrastructure in Baden-Württemberg (bwHPC) is a collaborative initiative that pools resources and service structures from various institutions. The infrastructure is financially supported by the Ministry of Science, Research, and Arts of the State of Baden-Württemberg, the German Research Society, and ten universities in Baden-Württemberg, including the University of Tübingen [16].

The bwHPC offers five high-performance computing (HPC) clusters, also known as the bwHPC clusters, optimized for different research domains. For this thesis, the bwForCluster Helix, which specifically focuses on research in Computational humanities, was used [17]. To access the HPC cluster, a connection to the associated ssh sever must be set up.

The operating system running on the bwForCluster Helix is RedHat, while its queuing system uses Slurm as a job scheduler. In particular, users can submit their job requests using shell scripts, and once the required resources become available, their jobs are executed accordingly.

Table 7.6 presents an overview of the nodes available for the bwForCluster Helix. It is possible to request jobs with a maximum memory requirement of 236 GB and a maximum runtime of 120 hours, i.e., 5 days. However, none of the SFT runs took longer than 9 hours and needed more than 50 GB when executed on two A4 GPUs.

Node Type	CPU Nodes		GPU Nodes		
	cpu	fat	gpu4		gpu8
Quantity	355	15	29	26	3
Installed Working Memory (GB)	256	2048	256	256	2048
Available Memory for Jobs (GB)	236	2010	236	236	2010
Interconnect	1x HDR100	1x HDR100	2x HDR100	2x HDR200	4x HDR200
Coprocessors	-	-	4x Nvidia A40 [®] (48 GB)	4x Nvidia A100 [®] (40 GB)	8x Nvidia A100 [®] (80 GB)
Number of GPUs	-	-	4	4	8
GPU Type	-	-	A40	A100	A100

Figure 7.6: Overview of the compute nodes of the bwForCluster Helix [17]

7.4 Experimental results and further adjustments

Since the first SFT for human alignment using the hyperparameter, determined in Section 7.2, obtained unsuitable results (see Subsection 7.4.1), additional rounds of SFT experiments had to be conducted for both human and expert alignment. Various hyperparameter configurations were tested, and their impact on the model’s performance was assessed. Details of the different SFT runs can be found in the subsections below.

7.4.1 Human-Alignment: Hyperparameter according to 7.2

For the initial attempt to align the Llama 2 13B Chat model with humans, SFT was executed following the hyperparameter setup explained in Section 7.2.2, along with the LoRA configurations described in Section 7.2.3. The training took about 8.5 hours using two A4 GPUs provided by the bwForCluster Helix.

Figure 7.7: Development of the evaluation and train loss over two epochs. Step 460 is the border between epochs one and two.

The development of the loss curves for the training and evaluation loss throughout the SFT is depicted in Figure 7.7. Surprisingly, the training loss exhibits an extremely high loss value of about 7900 towards the end of the first epoch (epoch 0.98) at SFT step 450. This outlying value significantly influenced the overall plot of the loss curve, as shown in Figure 7.7a.

Therefore, the single high train loss value was removed to better plot the loss development (Figure 7.7b). This revealed a significant decrease in losses between the first and second epochs. The train loss and evaluation loss dropped from around 9 to nearly zero.

A small test was conducted to better understand the cause behind this loss reduction. The 20 randomly selected samples from the GeoSignal dataset from Section 6.1, listed in Appendix A.1.1, were used. These prompts consist of both human-aligned and expert-aligned prompts and serve as inputs to evaluate the performance of the fine-tuned model. The generated textual outputs were then compared to those obtained without employing SFT.

However, after looking at the output generation results, it became apparent that the

SFT was unsuccessful. For all 20 input prompts, the model only produced "<unk>" tokens until reaching the maximum new token limit.

7.4.2 Human-Alignment: One epoch

Since the significant drop in the loss curves occurred between the two epochs in the previous SFT run, another round of SFT was executed using the same settings as before, except only one epoch instead of two.

The SFT training process took approximately six and a half hours using two A4 GPUs. Figure 7.8b depicts the loss development throughout this SFT experiment. Notably, there is a significant peak in the training loss around step 100 before the loss decreases again, and both training and validation losses stabilize near 8.

To check for any improvement in the model's performance, it was queried with the same example prompts as in the first experiment 7.4.1; however, the output quality remains unchanged, i.e. the model only produces "<unk>" tokens.

To ensure that the observed issue wasn't caused by the optimization of too many model layers, another round of SFT was executed, focusing on optimizing only the linear layers within the self-attention block (`q_proj`, `k_proj`, `v_proj`, and `o_proj`). The loss behavior can be seen in Figure 7.8a. However, the loss curves show a similar tendency compared to the ones where all linear layers are optimized. Additionally, no improvements can be seen when querying the model with the prompt examples as before. The model still generates "<unk>" tokens only. Due to the unsuitable results, further experiments will be conducted to optimize all linear layers during SFT again.

7.4.3 Human-Alignment: One epoch and 2e-04 learning rate

Since neither the number of epochs nor the number of optimized layers was causing the useless SFT outcomes, the learning rate was focused. An initially set learning rate of 0.01 might have been too high, although it proved effective during hyperparameter testing on a subset of 200 prompts (see Subsection 7.2.2). The cosine learning rate scheduler may be unable to adjust the learning rate accordingly over 18k prompts.

Following the recommendations from Pytorch [100], the same SFT setup consisting of one epoch, optimizing all linear layers and a learning rate of 2e-04 was executed.

(a) Only layers in the self-attention block optimized

(b) All the linear layers optimized

Figure 7.8: Loss development for one-epoch SFT with a different amount of linear layers optimized

The SFT run took roughly 7 hours using two A4 GPUs. Figure 7.9a presents the loss curves.

Based on the loss trends alone, decreasing the learning rate shows significant improvement. Both training and validation losses exhibit a descent in their initial 100 steps and then stabilize near 1.

Using the same input prompts as before, the generated responses outperformed those from SFT runs 7.4.1 and 7.4.2. The outputs were written in a coherent text and effectively captured the intended task stated in the input prompts. Nevertheless, they were still not as good as the results produced by the Llama 2 13B Chat model without any SFT.

Table A.3 in the Appendix provides two examples of the model's output with and without SFT. The first example is a word recognition task, where a passage without geoscience words is given, and the model is asked to extract words related to geoscience. The model without SFT correctly states that there are no such words, whereas the model with SFT finds 97 words related to geoscience in a passage that only has 35 words in total.

The second example involves identifying instruments as string or percussion. Without SFT, the model stated that this question does not belong to the domain of geoscience, and it, therefore, cannot answer this question. With SFT, the model first gives a correct answer but starts to hallucinate an MC task about the United States afterwards. This behavior is not in-line with the intended alignment with humans.

Generally, the results after this SFT were better than the ones, before but they were still not optimal. This is why another round of SFT was executed.

Figure 7.9: Loss development for one-epoch SFT with different learning rates

7.4.4 Human-Alignment: One epoch and $2e-05$ learning rate

Since lowering the learning rate improved the model's performance significantly, this round of SFT was conducted with a learning rate of $2e-05$. The SFT required approximately 7 hours to complete using two A4 GPUs.

The loss curves in Figure 7.9b are similar to those of SFT with a learning rate of $2e-04$; however, there is a less rapid decline within the initial 100 training steps. Moreover, the model's performance in generating answers improved as well. Manually comparing the 20 answers produced for distinct prompts after this SFT to those without SFT revealed that the fine-tuned model outperformed the base model seven times. Eight times, the results were of an equal quality, and only five times, the model without SFT was superior. Table A.4 in the Appendix provides an example for each category: better, equal or worse performance than without SFT. In the example that shows improvement through SFT, the model does not hallucinate damping ratio values for Shales and Sandstone as without SFT but highlights the individuality of this problem and provides general information only. However, for the example where the model without SFT performed better, the behaviour is the other way round. With SFT, the model makes up papers about Armellinoite-(Ce), whereas, without SFT, sources for the user to find such papers are provided instead of hallucinating.

Notably, the fine-tuned model generated slightly longer and more detailed answers. Despite more elaboration, the general proportion of hallucination within the answers did not increase. More insights into the generated answers and rating decisions can be found in the GitHub repository of this thesis. The inference results after this SFT run seem to be a good base for the next round of SFT, i.e. alignment with geoscience experts. An overview of all employed hyperparameters is given in Appendix A.2.4. The model was uploaded on Huggingface as well: `yesenia09/Geoscience_Llama2_-13BChat_SFT_v0`

7.4.5 Expert-Alignment: Loading the model as PeftModelForCausalLm

Since the SFT results for human-alignment in experiment 7.4.4 appeared promising, SFT for expert-alignment was set up under the same conditions. It has proven time-efficient during inference tests to first load the Llama 2 13B Chat model from Huggingface as a base model and apply the checkpoint files on top of the base model afterwards.

(a) Learning rate of $2e-04$

(b) Learning rate of $2e-05$

Figure 7.10: Loss development for one-epoch SFT with different learning rates

The SFT training process took roughly six and a half hours using two A4 GPUs. Figure 7.10b shows the loss development for the first SFT run focusing on expert alignment. The training loss fluctuates between values close to 1.9 and 1.7, whereas the evaluation loss is maintained completely constant throughout the entire SFT process. The continuous evaluation loss suggested that the model always generates the same string as a response for different input prompts.

To test this expectation, inference with the input prompts used during testing human alignment SFT was also performed. Throughout all input prompts, the model only generated the token "[/INST]".

Since adjusting the learning rate was the only strategy to improve the model's performance during SFT for human alignment, SFT was executed under the same conditions as before but using a learning rate $2e-04$ this time. Figure 7.10a, however, shows that this did not solve the problem. The evaluation loss remained constant, while the training loss fluctuated a lot. Additionally, the model produced only a single "[/INST]" token as output for all input prompts.

Since adjusting the learning rate showed no impact at all, it was investigated whether the SFT implementation in general could have caused the bad results.

7.4.6 Expert-Alignment: Loading the model as `AutoModelForCausalLM`

The only implementational difference between SFT for human alignment and expert alignment is how the model is instantiated. This is why the focus of this experiment lies on the model itself.

For human alignment, the Llama 2 base model was retrieved directly from Huggingface as an instance of the `AutoModelForCausalLM` class. On the other hand, when applying the checkpoints of the fine-tuned model to the base model, it gets converted into an example of the `PeftModelForCausalLM` class.

To rule out any potential impact of the different model classes on the performance, the fine-tuned standalone model was initialized from a local repository as an instance of the `AutoModelForCausalLM` class. Another round of SFT was executed, keeping all other settings from 7.4.4, such as a learning rate of $2e-05$.

Figure 7.11 displays the loss development during this new SFT training, which required approximately 7 hours to complete. Compared to the results using an instance of the `PeftModelForCausalLM` class, the training loss exhibits fewer fluctuations, while the evaluation loss follows a descending trend throughout the training process. The observations suggest that the model has effectively learned to produce task-specific responses.

Figure 7.11: Loss development for one-epoch SFT with a learning rate of $2e-05$ for an instance of the `AutoModelForCausalLM` class

To verify that the model's performance actually improved, the inference was executed using 25 prompts. The output was manually compared to the output produced by the model without SFT. Nine times, the production of the fine-tuned model is superior, six times the output is equally good, and only five times the model without SFT performed better.

Interestingly, no clear trend in the output can be observed. Some answers are much shorter than without SFT and some significantly longer. Also, sometimes the model shows more hallucination than without SFT, and sometimes there is less. Sometimes, the model refuses to answer a question since it does not belong to the domain of geoscience, and sometimes, it responds to those questions. More than 20 prompts need to be evaluated to draw more precise conclusions about the concrete improvements in the model's performance after SFT was produced. The only thing that becomes evident is that the model usually starts with an opening sentence like "Hello! As a helpful and respectful assistant, I'm here to assist you with your question." and ends with a closing phrase like "Please let me know if there's anything else I can help with." This is probably the result of optimizing the model to be polite and helpful. All responses and insights into the manual rating decisions can be found in the GitHub repository of this thesis.

Generally, after two rounds of SFT, the model seems to produce equal or better outputs than without SFT, which is why no more SFT experiments were conducted.

The model was uploaded on Huggingface as well: `yesenia09/Geoscience_Llama2_13BChat_SFT_v1`

The only question that remains unanswered is why the `AutoModelForCausalLM` and `PeftModelForCausalLM` show significantly different SFT results. The difference between these two model classes is that the `AutoModelForCausalLM` contains merged adapters whereas the `PeftModelForCausalLM` model contains the model's pre-trained weights with LoRA attached to them" [27]. This, however, it shouldn't cause different behavior during inference and SFT.

8 PART 3: Reinforcement Learning

In this chapter, the application of RL is used to further refine the fine-tuned model from Chapter 7. Although the model could abstract patterns in the SFT data and learned to better answer geoscience questions, some of the responses are not in line with human preferences. This is why, in particular, Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (RLHF) was used to fine-tune the model. A dataset based on human preferences was designed to improve the model's behavior.

Figure 8.1 illustrates the SOTA procedure proposed by Ouyang et al. [96] for implementing RLHF. Their method consists of three main steps. The first step is the application of SFT to a policy model, which has already been explained in the previous chapter. The second step encompassed the reward model training, i.e. a model that learns to rate the policy outputs based on human preference. Lastly, the policy training via Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) needs to be executed.

This chapter focuses on the second and third steps of RLHF. In Section 8.1, the reward model training is described and discussed. A pre-trained reward model has been selected as a reward model and was explicitly fine-tuned for this use-case of geoscience domain specialization.

Following reward model training, the policy training is explained in Section 8.2. Here, the details of how the policy is updated using PPO are discussed. PPO is an RL algorithm designed to minimize the gap between old and new policies while ensuring stability during training [112]. By employing PPO, the policy model learns to produce outputs that align with human preferences.

The primary objective of RLHF is not to impart new geoscience knowledge but rather to optimally adjust the model's behavior to align better with human preferences. The optimization focuses on syntactical and structural improvements and enhances the model's performance for specific tasks such as fill-in-the-blank questions.

8.1 Reward Model

To train a reward model from scratch, large datasets are required. Given this project's limited geoscientific data, a pre-trained reward model was selected and fine-tuned instead. The reward model, which will be used to evaluate the outputs generated by the policy model, is the `hh_rlhf_rm_open_llama_3b` model by Dong et al.

Figure 8.1: The three steps of RLHF: (1) SFT, (2) RM training, and (3) RL via PPO [96]

[34]. This model was fine-tuned based on the requirements and needs of the SFT model trained in Chapter 7.

The `hh_rlhf_rm_open_llama_3b` model is based on a 3B version of an OpenLLAMA model, an open reproduction of LLAMA models [40]. This has two advantages: One the one side, fine-tuning the relatively small-scale Llama-based reward model requires minimal GPU resources. On the other side, the Llama-based reward model and the fine-tuned Llama 2 13B Chat model should be compatible during policy training.

To transform the OpenLlama model into a reward model, Dong et al. [34] used the HH-RLHF dataset by Anthropic [4, 7] for fine-tuning. This dataset focuses on optimizing a model for helpfulness and harmlessness and is one of the SOTA datasets within the realm of RLHF. To ensure the dataset's quality, it was generated by human interactions with LLMs.

For the helpfulness aspect, humans got engaged in open-ended conversations with LLMs, asking for assistance and advice, or instructing them to complete tasks. They then chose the most helpful response provided by each model. Conversely, participants attempted to provoke inappropriate responses from the LLMs for the harmfulness component and decided for the most harmful answer afterwards [7].

According to Dong et al. [34], the `hh_rlhf_rm_open_llama_3b` model achieved an evaluation loss of 0.5 and an accuracy of 75.48% on the HH-RLHF test dataset [4]. However, Dong et al. [34, p. 2] also state that their reward model "is

far from perfect, and the imperfection can be exploited by the algorithms to chase for a high reward, leading to reward hacking."

To tailor the reward model to the specific needs of the SFT model, the reward model was fine-tuned using a manually designed dataset described in Subsection 8.1.1. The fine-tuning implementation and procedure is described in Subsection 8.1.2 and the performance of the reward model is discussed in Subsection 8.1.3.

8.1.1 Training data

This Subsection comprehensively describes the manually designed dataset used to fine-tune the reward model. The dataset was created based on undesired behavior observed in the outputs generated by the SFT model from Chapter 7 and consists of approximately 2,500 rows.

The dataset's creation process is further explained in the following paragraphs. The last two paragraphs describe the additional preprocessing steps needed to use the dataset to fine-tune the reward model.

Dataset construction

optimization objective	ood	zeros	repetition	completion	overall
no. of rows	1.9k	100	420	80	2.5k

Table 8.1: Absolute number of rows included in the reward model training dataset for each optimization objective

The GeoBench evaluation dataset, introduced in Section 9.1, was used to query the finetuned model to identify areas where improvements could be made in the model's responses. This dataset consists of MC questions, TF questions, fill-in-the-blank questions, word definition questions, and discussion/essay questions, making it possible to get a good performance overview across various question types.

The model was asked to produce answers for every query within the dataset. A detailed description of the inference process can be found in Section 9.2.1. After inference, all the answers were manually examined fore optimization potential.

Undesired behavior detected in the model's responses was categorized into "optimization objectives". For each objective, corresponding prompts, optimal (chosen) answers, and undesirable (rejected) answers were either extracted or formulated accordingly. The resulting dataset was stored in a CSV file with four columns, i.e. type of objective, prompt, chosen answer, and rejected answer.

Generally, there are two kinds of optimization objectives:

1. Overall Optimization: Improvement is needed throughout all types of tasks
2. Task-Specific Optimization: Improvement is needed for a particular task only

The following paragraphs define and explain the optimization objectives and the procedures involved in creating the chosen and rejected answers for the dataset. Table 8.1 gives an overview of the distribution of prompts over the different objectives.

Objective 1.1: Avoid answering out-of-domain (ood) questions

Given that the aim is to develop a model specialized in answering geoscience-related questions, it is preferred that the model does not show proficiency in other domains. When confronted with ood questions, e.g., *How do I bake a chocolate cake?* the model should state that it aims to answer geoscience-related matters instead of providing an answer. This intended behavior is a design choice and should not effectively influence the model's ability to answer in-domain queries.

During SFT, the human-alignment dataset, consisting of general-purpose questions, was split into three segments: train, test, and validation sets (see Table 7.1). The train and validation splits were used during SFT; however, the test set split of 1.8k prompts was reserved for the reward model training for RLHF.

Since all of these prompts are ood questions, they can be used as input prompts with their labels, i.e. detailed answers given to ood questions. Since the labels show unintended behavior, they serve as rejected answers. The chosen answer for all ood prompts is: *This question falls outside the field of geoscience. Since my expertise is limited to geoscience topics, I'm unable to assist with this.*

Objective 1.2: Avoid using zeros as padding tokens

Although the padding token is *[INST]*, the model occasionally generates answers containing zeroes as padding tokens. Since these padding tokens are not adequately trimmed during inference, this is an undesired behavior by the model.

chosen	# The main mode of metamorphism is #	# The main mode of metamorphism is #
---------------	--------------------------------------	--------------------------------------

Table 8.3: Example of chosen and rejected answer for Optimization objective 1.3

Objective 2.1: Effectively answer fill-in-the-blank questions:

Despite showing good performance results on most tasks, the model encountered difficulties when dealing with fill-in-the-blank questions. In most instances, the model failed to provide an answer, instead simply repeating the given sentence with an empty space for the blank one time or repeating the sentence until the maximum token limit is reached. Additionally, for some prompts, the model inserted placeholders like "#1" or "#2" in the blanks, depending on whether it was the first or second blank in a sentence. Examples of both cases are listed in Table 8.4.

To identify all occurrences of this behavior, the answers were manually filtered. Approximately 80 outputs (out of 150) were extracted and used as rejected answers. The labels to these prompts in the GeoSignal-SFT dataset served as chosen answers. It is important to note that due to phrase repetitions in some fill-in-the-blank questions, these prompts might appear twice within the dataset with different chosen answers.

rejected	# The geomagnetic elements include _And _;	The geomagnetic elements include _And _; [...]
chosen	Magnetic declination, magnetic inclination and magnetic field strength	

rejected	#1: According to the depth of the lake and its geographical location, the clastic lake facies can be divided into #1: [...]
chosen	Lake delta, shore lake, shallow lake, semi-deep lake, deep lake

Table 8.4: Example of chosen and rejected answer for Optimization objective 2.1

Data preprocessing

Since the training of the reward model was executed using the TRL library [135], the dataset needed some further preprocessing. First, the dataset, which was stored as a CSV file, was converted into a DataFrame. Afterwards, the dataset was split into training and test sets. Specifically, the training set contains 90% of the dataset,

i.e. 2169 prompts, while the test set consists of 10% , i.e., 242 prompts. Stratified sampling was applied to split the data to ensure an equal representation of the different optimization objectives since they are highly unbalanced in the dataset.

The chosen and rejected answers were converted into token sequences for each split, while padding and truncation techniques were applied to maintain a uniform length. The tokenized answers were then transformed into input ids and attention masks. The input ids are lists of token ids optimized for efficient processing by the model, while the attention masks are lists of indices indicating which tokens should be focused at during computation.

Based on this preprocessing, a train and a test datasets with four columns - input ids of chosen answers, input ids of rejected answers, attention masks of chosen answers, and attention masks of rejected answers - was constructed. These datasets were passed into the reward model trainer for the training process.

8.1.2 Training the reward model

In this section, the training process of the reward model is described. Subsection 8.1.2 offers a closer look at the implementation details of the training as well as the hardware requirements. Further information on, e.g. how the model is retrieved and stored are provided too.

Subsection 8.1.2 discusses the hyperparameter and quantization configurations used during the reward model's training. After executing several reward model training sessions, these settings were adjusted based on each model's performance.

Technical implementation of training

As for the SFT, the reward model training was carried out using the TRL library [135]. The base reward model that will be fine-tuned is the `hh_rlhf_rm_open_llama_3b` model developed by Dong et al. [34]. This model was retrieved from Huggingface as an instance of the `AutoModelForSequenceClassification` class in a quantized manner using LoRA [46]. The parameter `num_labels` was set to one since the reward model should only output a single value, i.e. a value that indicates how favorable the given input text is.

The reward model was trained with the help of the RewardTrainer offered by the TRL library [135]. During training, the maximal output length was restricted to 256 tokens. The training process took roughly 3 hours using a single A4 GPU with 40GB of RAM.

After the training was completed successfully, the model's state was saved as a checkpoint using the `save_model()` method available through the RewardTrainer. During inference, the model could be instantiated as an instance of the `AutoPeftModelForSequenceClassification`.

Hyperparameter configuration and adjustments

Given that the manual hyperparameter test during SFT did not provide any helpful insights into the actual outcome of the training, the hyperparameter configurations for the training of the reward model were not as extensively tested.

Unfortunately, Geng and Liu [40] do not provide a complete overview of the hyperparameter settings employed during the fine-tuning of the `hh_r1hf_rm_open_llama_3b` model. However, they state that a learning rate of $5e-6$, linear decay, a single epoch, and a batch size 16 were employed. These parameters were adopted for the fine-tuning run in this thesis. All additional hyperparameter and quantization configurations were taken from the TorchTune Library by Pytorch [100]. Specifically, the settings for the Llama 2 7B model were used since it is the smallest one available.

However, during fine-tuning, the training loss and evaluation remained constant. This can be seen as an indicator that the model's training did not improve or decrease performance, i.e., was not successful. Similar problems were observed during SFT, which were solved by adjusting specific hyperparameters.

Consequently, the training process was reinitiated. As a first intuition, a smaller batch size was used. Since Dong et al. [34] used 112k prompts for their reward model training, a larger batch size might benefit their case. When working with 2.5k prompts only, a reduced batch size might lead to improved outcomes. This is why a batch size of 2 was selected, following the SFT settings.

This time, the evaluation and training loss decreased, as shown in Figure 8.2a. However, despite being trained for only one epoch, the training loss starts to increase

significantly towards the end of the epoch. Such an increase can be a sign of overfitting due to suboptimal hyperparameter settings.

Figure 8.2: Development of the loss over different learning rates with a batch size of 2

Although some overfitting occurred during the training, the reward model's performance was evaluated, following an intuitive approach. Five prompts were randomly sampled from the fine-tuning dataset for every optimization objective (OOD questions, zero-padding, repetition, and fill-in-the-blank questions). The baseline reward model and the fine-tuned base model were asked to generate rewards for the chosen and rejected answers.

One aspect of the evaluation was to count how frequently the chosen answers received a higher reward than the rejected answers. This occurred in only seven out of twenty test samples for both models.

Another aspect of the evaluation involved calculating and averaging the differences between the chosen and rejected answers' rewards for both models. The base model's average rating was 1.238 points in favor of the rejected answers. After the fine-tuning, the model's average rating was 1.254 points in favor of the rejected answers. The evaluation results show a slight decrease in performance after fine-tuning.

As a consequence, another round of fine-tuning was executed. This time, a higher learning rate of $5e-4$ rather than $5e-6$ was used. The loss curves for this fine-tuning run are displayed in Figure 8.2b. The evaluation loss curve is almost identical to the one with a smaller learning rate. However, the training loss curve did not increase towards the end of the epoch. These loss developments suggest that the fine-tuning was successful compared to the fine-tuning tries before. An extensive performance evaluation is described in the next section, and an overview of the full hyperparameter

and quantization configurations is provided in Appendix A.3.1. The model was uploaded on Huggingface as well: [yesenia09/Geoscience_Open_Llama_3B_RM](https://huggingface.co/yesenia09/Geoscience_Open_Llama_3B_RM)

8.1.3 Results

Before delving into manual evaluations, it is worth noting the evaluation metrics computed throughout the training process:

```
***** eval metrics *****
epoch = 0.97
eval_accuracy = 0.9959
eval_loss = 0.0314
eval_runtime = 0:03:28.92
eval_samples_per_second = 1.158
eval_steps_per_second = 0.579
```

Specifically, the eval loss and eval accuracy values are interesting. A final loss value of 0.0314 is relatively tiny, as intended. Similarly, the accuracy value of 0.9959 (almost 100% accuracy) seems to be an optimal result. Both values suggest successful training.

The manual evaluation, however, shows a different tendency. Two distinct ways of assessment were used to assess the quality of the reward model. The first one is to count all instances where the chosen answer received a higher reward than the rejected answer. The second one is to calculate the differences between all chosen-rejected reward pairs and compute the mean afterwards. Both evaluation approaches were executed using the same five samples for each optimization objective (20 in total) as in the previous section's evaluation of a model trained with a lower learning rate.

Following the first evaluation approach, for the base model, the chosen answer reward is higher than the rejected answer in 10 out of 20 prompts. For the fine-tuned model, this occurred in 9 out of 20 instances. Although the results can be seen as a slight decrease in performance, the specific example where the chosen reward is no longer higher than the rejected reward shows only a 0.02 difference, which is not a significant change.

More interesting is to look at how often the chosen reward was higher than the rejected one for each optimizing objective. The selected answers are rated higher than

the rejected answers for the zero-padding samples in all five cases. The remaining occurrences of a higher reward for the chosen answer are split between repetition and fill-in-the-blank prompts. The ood chosen answer was never preferred over the rejected response.

One explanation for this behavior may be the formulation of the ood chosen prompt: *This question falls outside the field of geoscience. Since my expertise is limited to geoscience topics, I'm unable to assist with this.* In the HH-RLHF dataset [4], which was used to initially set up the reward model, being unable to help with a question is likely to be poorly rewarded because it is not seen as helpful. The fine-tuning dataset was probably too small to correct for this type of behavior.

Following the second evaluation approach, the base model's average rating favored rejected answers by 0.714 points. After fine-tuning, the model's average rating shifted to 0.5884 points in favor of rejected answers.

These results can be seen as an improvement in two ways. First, the results after fine-tuning are better than the results before. Second, the results after fine-tuning with a learning rate $5e-4$ are better than those during the previous reward model trainings. Both indicate that the training was quite successful. However, the goal was to train a model that assigns a higher reward score for chosen answers than for rejected ones. This behavior was not achieved during fine-tuning.

Based on these findings, an accuracy value of 99.5% calculated during the automatic training evaluation seems surprising.

8.1.4 Limitations

The performance of the reward model can be seen as a solid basis on which the policy will be trained. However, the results are not yet optimal and leave room for optimization. Several factors are discussed in this section that could have influenced the performance of the reward model.

One possibility lies within the hyperparameter and quantization configurations. Although some experiments have taken place, further refinement may be necessary to improve the training and achieve better performance.

Another reason could be ambiguous and/or suboptimal data examples within the training dataset. As discussed in Section 8.1.1, some examples in the chosen column might still contain repetitions or syntactically incorrect sentences, which results in

lower reward scores.

A third factor to consider is the small scale of the dataset. With only 2.5k prompts in the dataset, the model might have not understood the patterns behind the different optimization objectives. Also, as mentioned in the section above, the self-constructed training data might contradict the HH-RLHF data used to initially train the model, resulting in problems assigning higher values to chosen answers.

Lastly, the number of random samples taken from the dataset for evaluation purposes might be too small. The evaluation may not accurately represent the model's capabilities if the sample pool consists of "unlucky" instances.

8.2 PPO Policy

Having completed the SFT and reward model training, the last step in applying RLHF to specialize a model in the geoscience domain is to train the policy. The policy corresponds to the model that underwent SFT in Chapter 7. The Proximal Policy Optimization (PPO) algorithm [112] was employed to update the policy during training. PPO is the SOTA optimization algorithm for RLHF and ensures training stability by preventing policy updates that are too large. Since PPO is based on the Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence, the model keeps its abilities in question answering while the overall performance is improved according to human preferences via the reward model [112].

In the following sections, the training data is described (Subsection 8.2.1), implementation details are discussed (Subsection 8.2.2), and first insights into the trained policy's performance are presented (Subsection 8.2.3).

8.2.1 Training Data

The training data for the PPO policy is taken from the GeoSignal dataset introduced in Section 7.1. For SFT, the dataset was divided into: *human-alignment* data containing general-purpose QA tasks and *expert-alignment* data with geospecific QA pairs. The policy training focused on the expert-alignment split of 17.4k prompts.

Data selection

The initial idea was to use the entire train set of about 17.4k prompts to learn the policy. However, during implementation, it became clear that working with the full train set posed some challenges.

The first challenge was the training time. Setting the maximum number of new tokens to 256, the training time using the entire train set would take 275 hours or almost 12 days, which is beyond the scope of this thesis.

Another problem was caused by the limited computational resources available. Training on the entire train set and smaller subsets, led to Out-Of-Memory (OOM) errors when using a single A100 GPU with 80GB RAM, although various memory-saving techniques were employed. After extensive debugging and testing, it became apparent that these OOM errors occurred specifically when training on prompts longer than the maximal number of new tokens, i.e. longer than 256 tokens. Increasing the token limit did result in a substantial increase in training time and, therefore, was not a helpful solution. Consequently, all prompts longer than 256 tokens were excluded from the dataset. This reduction left around 10.4k prompts remaining for training.

Despite the improvement, the training time remained considerable: approximately 165 hours or roughly 7 days for 10.4k prompts.

Finally, the dataset was shuffled to find a balance between sufficient data, computational requirements, and training efficiency, and the first 3.6k prompts were selected for training.

Data preprocessing

To prepare the data for training, some preprocessing was necessary.

First, the data was loaded as a Dataset from its pickle (.pkl) file. Next, the 'instruction' column was renamed 'query' to allow for better logging of training statistics. Additionally, all other columns were removed.

As described in the section above, any rows that contained queries longer than 256 tokens were filtered out so as not to cause a memory-overflow. And lastly, the processed dataset was converted into PyTorch format.

8.2.2 Technical Implementation of Training with PPO

As for the SFT and reward model training, the policy training was implemented using the TRL library [135]. Ensuring compatibility with the PPO Trainer provided by Werra et al. [135], both the policy and the reference models were instantiated as instances of the `AutoModelForCausalLMWithValueHead` class. Additionally, the reward model was obtained as an instance of the `AutoPeftModelForSequenceClassification` class. Since neither the reference nor the reward models were training, they were set to evaluation mode. Their respective tokenizers were loaded with padding added to the left side.

Challenge: `ppo_trainer.generate()`

The initial attempt at implementing the policy training was inspired by the examples in the TRL GitHub repository. Following their approach, the input prompts were encoded and saved in an extra column within the dataset before training. During training, the dataset was loaded in batches and the input IDs for each prompt were individually passed into the `generate()` function of the `PPOTrainer` instance. Surprisingly, when querying the policy model through the `generate()` function provided by the `PPOTrainer`, the model exclusively generated sequences composed of backslashes or combinations of backslashes with various special characters if the temperature value was increased within the generation settings. However, fitting textual responses are produced when querying the policy model directly without involving the trainer instance.

Due to the unresolved problem encountered while using the `generate()` function of the trainer to produce outputs, a modification in the policy training process was necessary.

The input queries are no longer encoded before training. Instead, batches were successively loaded from the dataset, and each input query within the batch was encoded individually. By directly calling the model's own `generate()` function, the encoded prompts were used to query the model. The responses, in the form of Pytorch Tensors, were then decoded back into human-readable language. For each prompt, the encoded prompt, the encoded response and the decoded response were saved. Per decoded response, rewards were computed by executing inference over the reward model. Lastly, all encoded prompts, responses, and rewards within a batch

were passed to the PPO trainer. Additionally, the logs were tracked to get an insight into the effectiveness of the policy training.

Challenge: Memory-efficient Training

When the training was initiated with the given setup, OOM errors emerged after just a few initial steps. To address this issue, several memory optimization techniques were employed.

Firstly, the models were loaded in a quantized form. Specifically, the policy and reference models were retrieved in their 4-bit versions. To conserve additional memory, the reference and policy models were loaded while sharing ten layers, i.e., one fourth of their total number of layers. These shared layers remain frozen and unchanged throughout training.

The reward model was retrieved as a Peft Model, with the `low_cpu_mem_usage` parameter set to `True`. All three models were converted into `float16` format, and `use_cache` was set to `False`.

During training, multiple memory-saving methods were applied as well.

The PPO configurations were initialized with the settings `optimize_device_cache` and `optimize_cuda_cache` activated. Furthermore, the `Adam8bit` optimizer was passed into the PPO trainer, a quantized version of the 32bit Adam optimizer used per default. According to [47]: "large models can be finetuned with 75% less GPU memory without losing any accuracy compared to training with standard 32-bit optimizers," and the "reduced memory requirements means 8-bit optimizers are 4x faster than a standard optimizer".

Additionally, gradient checkpointing was enabled for the policy model. Since computing the gradient of the loss for backpropagation uses a lot of memory, intermediate computing results are dropped during the backward pass and only restored if necessary for further forward computation [21]. Lastly, after every single training step, the GPU cache was cleared.

Challenge: negative Kullback-Leibler (KL) divergence

After successfully optimizing memory consumption during training, the policy model learned from the available data. However, after a handful of training steps, the KL divergence turned negative. In RLHF, the KL divergence serves as a metric measuring

how different the log probabilities generated by the policy model are from those produced by the reference model. A higher KL divergence indicates more significant changes in the model. Conversely, a negative KL divergence usually indicates failed training [59].

Solving this problem proved to be nontrivial. First, the hyperparameters and generation configurations were adjusted. The initial settings were the same as those used during SFT. Experimenting with the learning rate, it turned out that reducing the learning rate from $2e-5$ to $2e-6$ results in minimal improvements. Moreover, increasing the batch size from 2 to 4 and establishing a mini-batch size of 4 and gradient accumulation steps set to 1 also demonstrated slight progress.

Additionally, the generation configurations for the inference of the policy model were adjusted according to [48]. Specifically, top-p sampling was set to 1.0, and disabling nucleus sampling and top-k sampling were excluded.

Lastly, following advice from Zheng et al. [145], reward scaling, normalization, and clipping were set within the PPO configurations to improve the overall training stability. Once these modifications had been put into effect, no longer were warnings issued about a negative KL divergence.

An overview of all the hyperparameters and generation configurations can be found in Appendix A.3.2.

Logging and Saving

The KL penalty and the loss were printed throughout the training process, and all other training statistics were logged after each training step. The overall training statistics were saved in a .txt file after finishing the training.

Finally, the model and tokenizer were saved using their `save_pretrained()` methods. To reload the model, it should be instantiated as an `AutoModelForCausalLM`. The model will be automatically loaded in a quantized manner since the quantization configuration is also stored. The model was uploaded on Huggingface, too: `yesenia09/Geoscience_Llama2_13BChat_RLHF`

8.2.3 Results

The overall policy training using an A100 GPU with 80GB of RAM required 56 hours to complete. Figure 8.4 provides insights into the statistics obtained throughout

this process.

The goal was to increase the average rewards per batch and maintain a low KL divergence between the reference model and the policy while maximizing the entropy. This ensures the policy remains close enough to the reference model without drastic changes that could lead to catastrophic forgetting or instability during training.

Figure 8.3: Average reward per batch during the policy training

Figure 8.3 shows the average reward assigned to the policy model's outputs per batch. Each batch consists of 4 rewards. An increasing development in the reward distribution would have been an indicator of successful training. Here, the average rewards diverge between 0 and 7 throughout the training. To confirm the tendency of the policy training to have flaws, different logging metrics were analyzed.

Figure 8.4a displays the mean KL divergence between the reference model and the new policies. Ideally, the values should remain small since they represent the difference in distributions between the two models per step. Additionally, the values cannot be negative but range between one, i.e., the distributions are completely identical, or a positive value indicates how different the distributions are. However, some slightly negative values are possible here due to the approximation of the KL divergence and appear towards the end of the training.

Figure 8.4b illustrates the mean negated KL penalty during training, representing the difference between the reference model and the new policy across each batch in the step. This metric is mainly based on the KL divergence and acts as a total reward

for optimization, encouraging the new policy to stay close to the old one to avoid excessive deviation and prevent overfitting. The KL penalty remained below 0.18 throughout the training, demonstrating that the policy updates are never too large. Additionally, there was a slight increase in the KL penalty during training, suggesting that the policy model's distributions became increasingly dissimilar from the reference model's distributions. The declining tendency for the mean KL divergence and the slightly increasing tendency for the negated KL penalty implies that the training might not have been successful either. Combined with the stagnating rewards depicted in Figure 8.3, the model seems to have hacked the KL objectives function presented in [96, p. 9] since the KL penalty is subtracted from the reward. Ideally, a high objective would have been achieved by increasing the reward over time and keeping the KL penalty small and positive. Here, the average reward per batch does not increase; however, a negative KL penalty is still used to cause increasing KL objective values. How far, hacking the KL objective influenced the model's behavior will be discussed in the evaluation (Chapter 9).

Stability during the training was assessed through two other indicators. Figure 8.4c depicts the loss during training, which tends to spike or produce NaNs when the training encounters difficulties. The plot reveals that the loss ranged between 0.08 and 0.19, implying a relatively stable training process. Furthermore, high entropy levels in Figure 8.4d indicated that the model's actions demonstrated sufficient randomness, i.e. the model showed practical exploration during training. Entropies fluctuated between 75 and 260, ensuring exploration without compromising performance.

In conclusion, the training session appears to have been both stable, given the consistent loss and entropy levels, and productive, as evidenced by the growing disparity between the reference and policy model distributions. Nevertheless, it cannot be definitively determined if training positively or negatively impacted the model. However, a slight negative tendency in performance is expected due to the presence of slightly negative KL divergence values.

To gain a more detailed understanding of the effects of RLHF on the model's performance, each task within the evaluation dataset was tested individually. A single prompt for every task was sampled, and inference using the RLHF model and its reference model, the SFT model, was conducted. The aim was to identify any shifts in performance. Appendix A.3.3 presents the selected prompts and their corresponding responses generated by both models.

Figure 8.4: Development of loss, KL penalty, mean KL divergence and entropy during the policy training

Upon closer examination of the results, it appears that the overall impact of RLHF on the model's performance was minimal. Both models produced identical answers for qa tasks and tf-questions. Noun definition answers were also similar, but the RLHF model provided a somewhat more concrete definition.

For the discussion question, neither model provided satisfactory answers. The RLHF model repeated the input prompts, while the SFT model constantly repeated a single sentence related to the topic. For the fill-in-the-blank question, the SFT model outperformed the RLHF model since the RLHF model listed the numbers 1 to 38 instead of generating an answer. Interestingly, despite using a reward model explicitly fine-tuned for f-i-t-b questions, the RLHF model was behind in this category.

Conversely, for the MC questions, the RLHF model outperformed the SFT model accurately answering the questions. Conversely, the SFT model has additional MC options before incorrectly responding to the question.

To conclude, the model preserved its ability to answer questions in general. However, inconsistent trends were observed in the performance comparison. While the RLHF model exhibits superior capabilities for specific tasks, such as MC questions, it underperforms in others, like fill-in-the-blank questions. A more detailed analysis of the RLHF impact on the model's performance is provided in Chapter 9.

9 PART 4: Evaluation

This chapter evaluates the progress of the geoscience domain-specialized model at different development stages throughout this thesis. Three stages of the model development will be examined. The first stage is the stage as a base model, i.e. Llama 2 13B Chat model. The second stage refers to the model after the SFT was conducted. The third stage of development deals with the SFT model that has also undergone RLHF.

Besides comparing the three stages of the domain specialization process to each other, the findings are also compared to the performance of other geoscience-focused and general-purpose open-source LMMs.

A dataset called GeoBench [30], designed explicitly for evaluating geoscience domain-specialized LLMs, was used to conduct this evaluation. Details about the composition of GeoBench are presented in Section 9.1.

The primary goal of this evaluation is to determine how proficiently the model performs at each stage of development on the GeoBench dataset. To achieve this goal, the dataset's prompts are categorized into: open and closed tasks. Using closed tasks, the factual knowledge of the models is tested, whereas open tasks test the ability to elaborate on the geoscientific topic in the prompt. A quantitative and qualitative analysis of the model's performance was executed for open and closed tasks.

Section 9.2 discusses the processes and results of measuring the model's performance through a quantitative analysis. For the quantitative analysis, LLMs, specifically GPT-4o [94], are used to assess outputs generated by the model at its different stages. In contrast, Section 9.3 describes the process and results of the qualitative analysis. This analysis relies on human evaluation only. By combining the insights from both quantitative and qualitative analyses, a comprehensive understanding of the impact of the different domain-specialization stages should be gained, which is then discussed in Chapter 10.

9.1 Data: GeoBench

In the paper by Deng et al. [30], a dataset named GeoBench was introduced. This dataset was explicitly designed to evaluate the capability of answering geoscience questions and is publicly available in their Github Repository. The data was collected

from different sources, primarily exams for environmental science, geographic, and geological degree programs, i.e. the Advanced Placement Examinations (APE) and National Postgraduate Entrance Exam (NPEE). Table 9.1 gives an overview of the distribution of open and closed task-types in the data.

The APE are tests offered in the United States by the College Board, which students take annually during May [30, p. 6]. They make up a portion of 1,395 multiple-choice questions related to geology, geography, and environmental science. All tasks taken from these exams are closed tasks.

China’s NPEE is an admission examination for master’s degree programs [30, p. 6]. The GeoBench tasks are taken from the geology and geography entrance exams from 2018 through 2023 and have been translated into English. There are 1,820 open and closed tasks within this portion of the dataset.

1,711 Closed tasks		
Multiple Choice	1,577	NPEE/APE
True or False	134	NPEE
1,092 Open tasks		
Fill in the blank	150	NPEE
Word definition	454	NPEE
Discussion/Essay	335	NPEE
Question Answering	153	NPEE

Table 9.1: Overview of the distribution of open and closed tasks in the GeoBench dataset

9.2 Quantitative Analysis

The quantitative analysis relies heavily on automated evaluation using LLMs, such as GPT-4o [94], for assessment. This is why the type of evaluation remains rather superficial. For instance, GPT-4o may determine if an answer to a closed task is factually correct, or assess if an output before or after RLHF better answers an open question. However, an in-depth analysis like defining the rate of hallucination or the helpfulness of an answer is left for the qualitative, i.e. human, analysis in Section 9.3.

Section 9.2.1 offers an overview of how GPT-4o was applied to quantitatively evaluate the model’s performance across different types of tasks. For closed tasks,

like multiple-choice questions, accuracy is used as a performance measurement. Conversely, for open tasks, a pairwise comparison between the answers the model generated at the three development stages is executed.

The results gained from these investigations are presented in Section 9.2.2. The strengths and limitations of the model's performance to answer open and closed questions are discussed.

9.2.1 Methods

When evaluating closed and open tasks quantitatively, the focus and strategies employed differ significantly. Evaluation for closed tasks, such as true or false questions, emphasizes whether the provided answer is factually correct, making it a relatively straightforward process.

On the other hand, open tasks, like discussion questions or essay prompts, are more challenging to evaluate. Unlike closed tasks, the evaluation criteria for open tasks extend beyond just checking for factual correctness. Factors like helpfulness, applicability, coherence, and suitability to the user's needs and level of knowledge come into play. This is why the evaluation strategies using GPT-4o must be tailored to the needs of the task.

After discussing the evaluation of closed tasks in the upcoming paragraphs, the methods used for assessing open tasks are covered towards the end of this subsection. More detailed insights into the evaluation can be found in the GitHub repository of this thesis.

Closed Tasks

The quantitative analysis involved evaluating the performance of the three different model stages, i.e. as a base model, after SFT, and after RLHF, using the closed tasks from the GeoBench dataset. Each model was retrieved as a standalone instance: the base and SFT models were loaded as instances of the `AutoModelForCausalLM` class, while the RLHF model was instantiated as an `AutoModelForCausalLMWithValueHead`. All models were then queried with the closed tasks, consisting of different MC and TF questions. The maximum new token limit was set to 128 since the answers are expected only to contain a single letter (A-E) for MC or a single word (True/False) for TF questions and one or two sentences of explanation. Inference ran on the Helix

cluster.

For each model, inference for all closed tasks took about 11 hours on a single A4 GPU, and the generated output was stored in a CSV file.

To evaluate the quality, i.e. correctness, of the generated responses, the GPT-4o Model released in May 2024 [94] was queried via the OpenAI API. For each model, the prompt, label, and generated output were loaded from the CSV file and embedded into the following query template:

```
{"role": "system", "content": "You are an evaluation system and rate outputs by another model."},  
{"role": "user", "content": f"An LLM answered with ### {output} ### to an input ### {prompt} ###. The actual answer is ### {label} ###. Is the answer provided by the LLM correct? Answer with 1, if yes, or 0, if no."}
```

After querying the GPT-4o model, the textual output, i.e. the evaluation result, is stored in an additional column of the input CSV file.

All the evaluation results were manually checked and corrected if necessary. Although the GPT-4o Model performed at a high level, certain adjustments were made to ensure the accuracy of this evaluation.

First, the GPT-4o Model tended to rate answers, claiming that input MC questions contained harmful terms or expressions not established in the geoscience domain as "1" (correct), despite those terms being neither harmful nor out-of-context. Second, whenever the base model provided outputs explaining which MC answers can be excluded instead of giving the definitive answer, the GPT-4o Model experienced difficulty determining if the response was correct.

These findings determined the accuracy by calculating the sum of all the correct answers and dividing it by the total number of closed tasks.

Regarding the TF questions, the original prompts consist solely of the statement to rate, such as *Minerals all have cleavage*, lacking clear instructions. When testing the evaluation process for TF questions using only these statements, the model failed to rate the sentences as either true or false but instead discussed the sentence's topic. Consequently, an instruction, i.e. *Please state if the following question is true or false*: was inserted into all prompt templates right before the sentences to rate. This minor modification was necessary to effectively evaluate the model's performance based on closed tasks.

Open Tasks

When assessing the open tasks, inference was carried out for all open task types, such as discussion questions, noun definition questions, fill-in-the-blank exercises, and general question answering. Since each task type has its requirements, table 9.2 gives an overview of the maximum new token settings and the instruction sentences inserted into each prompt.

Adding an instruction sentence for the open tasks, like for the true-false questions, was necessary since, e.g., for noun definitions, the prompt consisted of the noun only without any further instructions. Furthermore, the runtime was measured on a single A4 GPU.

type of task	max_new_tokens	instruction	run time
definition	256	Please give a short definition for the following term:	5 hours
completion	256	Please complete the following sentence:	2 hours
QA	256	Please answer the following question:	2 hours
discussion	521	Briefly discuss the following statement/question:	7 hours

Table 9.2: Inference details for each task during the quantitative analysis of open tasks

The evaluation was done using GPT-4o as well. A pairwise comparison was conducted for each task based on the generated outputs from the base, SFT, and RLHF models during inference. This decision is based on Liusie, Manakul, and Gales [76], who claim that pairwise comparison works better than scoring, e.g. using a Likert scale from 1 to 5 to evaluate certain aspects.

GPT-4o was queried with the original prompt and the answers generated by these models. The aim was to determine which response was the answer to the question. For the base model, a 1 should be printed, a 2 for the SFT model, and a 3 for the RLHF model.

Specifically, this was the prompt template used:

```
{"role": "system", "content": "You are an evaluation system and rate outputs by other models."},
```

{"role": "user", "content": f"Three LLMs were queried with ### {prompt} ###. The actual answer is ### {label} ###."}

Which is the best answer?

Print only 1, if ### {base} ### is the best answer.

Print only 2, if ### {sft} ### is the best answer.

Print only 3, if ### {rlhf} ### is the best answer."

This procedure was executed on a subset of 50 randomly chosen prompts per task. Like the closed task evaluation, the resulting GPT-4O outputs were stored in an extra CSV column.

The results were manually checked to ensure that GPT-4o exclusively returned digits instead of additional text or characters. Afterwards, the occurrences for each number are counted for each task separately and converted into a percentage, i.e. into a win rate for each model.

9.2.2 Results

Closed Tasks

To evaluate the performance of a model on closed tasks, the model was queried at various stages of specialization: as a base model, as a supervised fine-tuned model, and as a model after RLHF. This allows to assess the impact of each fine-tuning stage on the task performance.

Lin et al. [70] and Deng et al. [30] did a similar evaluation of their specialized geoscience models, GeoGalactica and K2, using the same dataset. They reported accuracy metrics for both dataset parts (APE data and NPEE data) within GeoBench. Additionally, they shared accuracy scores for several other LLMs, including general-purpose models such as MPT-7B [88] and those specifically trained on scientific data, like Galactica-30B [123].

The results from these studies and the results achieved by the model specialized in this thesis, are presented collectively in Table 9.3. It is essential to note that [70] and [30] did not explicitly mention or introduce the TF questions within the closed tasks in their papers. Instead, they can only be found within the GeoBench dataset. This is why it is unclear, whether they included the performance results for TF questions in

their accuracy scores. The accuracy scores for the three different model stages in this thesis, however, also include the performance for TF questions.

Baselines	NPEE	APE	Avg
LLaMA-7B	21.6	27.6	24.6
MPT-7B	28.4	26.0	27.2
Vicuna-7B	26.4	16.8	21.6
Alpaca-7B	31.1	29.1	30.1
ChatGPT	48.8	20.0	34.4
Gal-6.7B	25.7	29.9	27.8
Gal-30B	41.2	38.5	39.9
GalAlp-30B	42.6	44.1	43.2
K2-7B	39.9	29.3	34.6
GeoGalactica-30B	46.6	36.9	41.8
Llama-2-13B-Chat	38.9	53.3	46.1
Llama-2-13B-Chat (SFT)	41.5	48.0	44.8
Llama-2-13B-Chat (SFT, RLHF)	39.2	33.3	36.3

Table 9.3: Accuracy results in % for general purpose models (top rows), (geoscience)-scientific fine-tuned models (middle rows) and throughout the three stages of this thesis (bottom rows) over the GeoBench dataset for closed questions (MC and TF)

Table 9.3 presents accuracy scores for both MC and TF questions across the NPEE and APE datasets. The initial column displays the combined accuracy for MC and TF questions from the APE data. Column two represents MC questions specific to the NPEE data, while the third column shows the average accuracy derived from the combination of NPEE and APE data.

Regarding the performance of the thesis model stages, the RLHF model demonstrated the poorest results despite being anticipated to outperform the other models. While it shows slight improvement over the base model for NPEE data, a dramatic decrease in accuracy of 20% occurred when queried with the APE data. Conversely, the SFT model displayed nearly equivalent performance to the base model, showing slight improvement for NPEE data and a minimal decline for APE data. Both models maintained an average accuracy above 40%, which exceeds all other models tested. Still, comparing these three model stages, the base model showed the most robust performance on closed tasks.

Looking at the thesis models compared to the other models tested, most models show a superior accuracy for NPEE data compared to APE data. Exceptions include the base and SFT models, where an opposite tendency emerged. These models perform significantly better on APE MC questions. These results seem surprising since the APE MC questions have a more significant number of potentially correct answers (five vs. three options for NPEE), i.e. the probability of answering correctly by chance was increased on this data part. This indicates that the base model already had a good knowledge base for the geoscience domain and the SFT model was able to preserve this knowledge.

The base model and SFT model show the best performance for APE questions. For NPEE questions, however, ChatGPT [105] and GeoGalactica [70] surpass. However, the average accuracy scores, the base, and the SFT show the best performance on closed tasks.

Notably, the RLHF model falls behind but still performs comparable to the K2 model [30], the first geoscience model to be published in 2023. However, it cannot surpass the current SOTA geoscience model, GeoGalactica-30B [70]. Previous research in domain specialization revealed advancements from base to fine-tuned geoscience models, such as the progression from Llama 2 7B to K2. In contrast, the domain specialization from Llama 2 13B to the RLHF model resulted in a decline in performance.

Figure 9.1 offers a detailed breakdown of the results for the different closed task types and the dataset parts. This helps to understand the supposedly poor performance results for the RLHF model.

In Figure 9.1a, the findings are separated according to APE (MC only) and NPEE (combination of MC and TF) data. The performance for NPEE data marginally improves with each fine-tuning step, whereas the performance on APE data drops significantly with each step.

To better understand this observation, Figure 9.1b depicts the accuracy for each model based on distinct task types. It becomes evident that the RLHF model shows an improved performance for TF questions relative to the other models. On the contrary, its MC performance collapses.

Figure 9.1c reveals that the overall decline in performance observed in Table 9.3 stems primarily from the weak performance of the RLHF model on the APE MC question. Conversely, the RLHF model matches the baseline in terms of NPEE MC

Figure 9.1: Accuracy scores differentiating by task and dataset

performance and even surpass the other models for TF questions. These ambiguous results highlight the complexity and the obscurity of SFT and RLHF.

Open Tasks

The evaluation of the open tasks was executed using GPT-4o only and, therefore, remains on the surface level. For 50 randomly chosen prompts for each task, a pairwise comparison was conducted, asking GPT-4o to identify which model - base, SFT, or RLHF - produced the best answer. It should be noted that the concept of a *best* answer was not defined, leaving it up to GPT-4o to establish its criteria for rating these answers.

The outcome of this evaluation can be found in Figure 9.2a. Win rates represent the proportion of *best* answers generated by each model divided by fifty prompts per task.

For fill-in-the-blank questions, the base model showed a superior performance with a

win rate of 66%. On the other hand, the SFT model struggled seriously, only receiving a win rate of 2%, i.e. one single answer was chosen as the best one. This decline in performance was already observed during the formulation of the RLHF objectives, which is why the reward model for RLHF was trained on rating fill-in-the-blank questions. Fittingly, the RLHF model received a win rate of roughly 30%, suggesting that the RLHF had a favorable influence on the model's performance.

For discussion and definition questions, the performance discrepancy between the models was not strong. Nonetheless, the base model underperformed in discussions, which can indicate a likely positive impact from SFT and RLHF. Conversely, the base model outperformed in definition questions. However, the base model only received a 2% higher win rate than the other two models. The SFT and RLHF models showed similar win rates for both task types.

Contrasting fill-in-the-blank questions, the RLHF model demonstrated superior performance for general question answering with a win rate of 64%. The base model falls behind with a 12% win rate. The results for answering the questions indicate a continuous performance improvement throughout each fine-tuning stage in this thesis.

In Figure 9.2b the win rates across all tasks are summed up, i.e., the number of *best* answers per model throughout all tasks was divided by the 200 prompts chosen for evaluation.

All models fell within the range of 26-42%; however, the RLHF model achieved the highest win rate at 42%. This appears reasonable since the RLHF model consistently achieved good results across all task categories, whereas the other models had tasks with significantly lower win rates. The base model followed behind the RLHF model with 32%, while the SFT model received the lowest win rate at 26%. These findings highlight that aligning with human preferences through RLHF was a valuable step to optimize the models for particular tasks and make them geoscience experts.

9.2.3 Limitations

In several Natural Language Generation (NLG) tasks, using LLMs for evaluation yielded results comparable to human judgment [39]. Moreover, evaluating LLMs with the help of other LLMs is faster and more efficient than human evaluation. GPT-4o, for instance, process the input prompt and generate responses within seconds.

Figure 9.2: Win rates in % for each model per open tasks

However, this evaluation strategy also has its limitations. Shanahan, McDonell, and Reynolds [114] state: "[J]ust like the LLMs they evaluate, LLMs that perform evaluations cannot be trusted." In particular, this is true when evaluating the open tasks. LLMs show more stability in evaluating boolean QA, i.e. yes-or-no questions, as for the closed tasks, than for the pairwise comparisons applied for open tasks [39]. Moreover, LLMs are biased by set ordering when selecting the best response from a provided set due to position effects [68, 115]. Additionally, LLMs are highly sensitive to formatting adjustments within the input prompts [113] and often lean towards longer, more elaborate responses [142]. Furthermore, Wu and Aji [138] found that LLMs prefer answers containing factual errors to those that are too short or grammatically incorrect. Lastly, the scope of GPT-4o's knowledge is restricted to the data it was trained on, which may limit its ability to capture domain-specific contexts and, therefore, causes in precise evaluation responses.

While the quantitative analysis using GPT-4o offers initial insights into the model's performance development throughout this thesis, the underlying evaluation process remains a black box. Therefore, a qualitative study conducted by humans becomes essential for better understanding the model's abilities to answer geoscientific questions (Section 9.3).

9.3 Qualitative Analysis

In contrast to the quantitative analysis, which relied on automatic evaluation with the help of LLMs, the qualitative analysis is carried out exclusively by humans. This allows to delve deeper into the various aspects that make an answer accurate and helpful. The qualitative analysis can be broken down into two main components.

The first part involves human evaluation using a Likert scale to rate specific aspects such as hallucinations or grammatical correctness. This helps to gain valuable insights into the quality of the responses.

The second part includes general observations that numerical ratings cannot describe. These include e.g., nuances in the syntactic and grammatical structure, how well answers fit the task type, the geoscience-specific understanding, and overall impression of the response.

Section 9.3.1 provides an overview of the methods employed for open and closed tasks. Section 9.3.2 presents the observations gained during the evaluation process. The strengths and limitations of answering open and closed questions are also discussed.

9.3.1 Methods

In general, the approaches for evaluating open and closed tasks are similar. Nevertheless, the different types of prompts have other goals, as described in Subsection 9.2.1. Considering these differences when designing a framework to evaluate these responses numerically is essential.

Initially, the techniques used for evaluating closed tasks are described. Later, the focus shifts towards the methods for evaluating open tasks. More detailed insights into the evaluation decisions can be found in the GitHub repository of this thesis.

Closed Tasks

To evaluate the closed tasks, 20 prompts were randomly sampled for each task - MC and TF - from the evaluation dataset. The answers generated from the base, SFT, and RLHF models were stored in an Excel file.

A framework consisting of three primary aspects, each containing two sub-aspects, was established to evaluate these models. The evaluation framework is inspired by the one used in section 5.1:

1. Language use

- (a) **Grammatical Correctness:** Evaluate whether the generated answer is grammatically correct.
- (b) **Repetition:** Check if the model produces repetitive outputs rather than padding.

2. Task suitability

- (a) **Task Answering:** Determine if the model provides an answer to the question or if it, e.g., avoids responding by solely repeating the input prompt.
- (b) **Additional Information:** Assess if the model generates any extra explanations beyond the MC or TF response.

3. Content Quality

- (a) **Hallucination Detection:** Check if the model generates incorrect or irrelevant information.
- (b) **Content Correctness:** Verify if the model correctly answers the input prompt.

An additional column was added to the Excel file for each evaluated aspect. Ratings were assigned based on a binary system, where 0 signified poor performance, and 1 represents good performance. For instance, repetition, hallucination, and a factually wrong answer would result in a 0, whereas no repetition, no hallucination, and a correct answer are rated as 1.

Regarding aspect 2 (b), there isn't a specific desirable behavior. This is why a 0 rating implies no additional information was provided, while 1 suggests that some extra information was offered with the MC or TF answer.

The ratings were then summed up for each aspect individually to obtain an overview of the performance of each model. During the manual rating process, additional notes were taken concerning the observed behaviors of the models.

Open Tasks

As for evaluating the closed tasks, 20 prompts were randomly sampled for each open task - completion (fill-in-the-blank), discussion, definition and QA - from the 50 prompts used for the quantitative evaluation. The answers from all three models were stored in an Excel file.

The framework used for the evaluation of closed tasks is only slightly modified. It consists of three primary aspects, each containing two sub-aspects:

1. Language use

- (a) **Grammatical Correctness:** Evaluate whether the generated answer is grammatically correct.
- (b) **Repetition:** Check if the model produces repetitive outputs rather than padding.

2. Task suitability

- (a) **Task Answering:** Determine if the model provides an answer to the question or if it, e.g., avoids responding by solely repeating the input prompt.
- (b) **Level of expertise:** Rate whether the model generates answers that contain high-level geoscience information, regardless of the factual correctness. This is especially important for QA and discussion.

3. Content Quality

- (a) **Hallucination Detection:** Check if the model generates incorrect or irrelevant information.
- (b) **Content Correctness:** Verify if the model correctly answers the input prompt. This is especially important for completion, definition and QA.

In contrast to the closed evaluation, task suitability is adjusted. *Level of expertise* is added as a category that should capture the complexity of the answer provided. The complexity includes, for example, if statements are elaborated and if the correct scientific terms are used to describe geoscience entities. This does not consider whether the answer is factually correct since this is already captured in *Content quality*. *Level of expertise* is more critical for QA and discussion, whereas *Content Correctness* is more essential for completion and definition.

Ratings for open tasks were assigned based on a ternary system, where 0 signifies poor performance, 1 represents intermediate performance, and 2 represents good performance. For instance, repetition, hallucination, and a factually wrong answer would result in a 0, whereas no repetition, no hallucination, and a correct answer are rated as 2. If the model, e.g. if only one of the two blanks is filled correctly or if the answer only shows a minor grammatical error, it would be rated with a 1. The ternary rating system allows for a more nuanced rating of the model’s performance compared to the closed tasks.

As for the closed tasks, the ratings were summed up for each aspect individually to obtain an overview of the performance of each model.

9.3.2 Results

Closed Tasks

After completing the human evaluation, the results are stored in Appendix A.4.1 as a table and visualized in Figure 9.3.

Figure 9.3: Scores achieved during human evaluation

Looking at the aspects of *Language use*, i.e. grammatical correctness and repetition, all models generated grammatically correct responses for MC questions. However, for TF questions, the rates of grammatically correct answers dropped slightly for the SFT and the RLHF models. This trend can be explained due to the increase in repetitive structures for these models. In the plot, high scores indicate less repetition.

The repetition often resulted in the concatenation of incomplete sentences, e.g. the RLFH model answered with *The definition of Most glacial deposits have obvious bedding is that Most glacial deposits have obvious bedding Most glacial deposits have obvious bedding*.

However, the SFT and RLHF models tended to generate one-word answers only for MC and TF questions, such as *A.* and *True*. This can be seen by the low scores for *Additional information*. Conversely, the base model tended to exceed the maximum new token limit of 128 tokens for almost all answers. While the base model provided significantly more information than the other models, a relatively high number of its outputs did not answer the given MC questions. Before the application of SFT and RLHF, the base model refused to answer some MC questions, claiming that they contained potentially harmful language. The base model's answers followed a pattern like: *[...] To ensure a safe and respectful conversation, I would like to point out that the term "barrier-free" can be perceived as ableist and dismissive of the experiences of people with disabilities. Instead, I suggest using the term "accessible" or "inclusive" to convey the same idea. Additionally, I would like to remind you that it's important to avoid using language that perpetuates harmful stereotypes or stigmas [...]*. This behavior never occurred for the fine-tuned models. However, their answers became denser and left out further explanations.

Having dense answers, such as one-word or short phrases, reduces the likelihood of hallucinations within the responses. In the plot, high scores indicate less hallucination. It becomes evident that the SFT and RLHF models perform significantly better for both types of tasks, i.e., they show less hallucination.

However, only minimal improvements in content correctness can be observed from the base model to the RLHF model for both MC and TF tasks. The RLHF model got only 5 correct answers out of 20 for MC tasks, while 12 out of 20 answers were correct for TF questions. These results are probably influenced by the number of choices for each task. MC questions had three to five possible choices, while TF questions required a binary decision. This creates a higher likelihood for models - even without a good base knowledge - to perform better for TF questions.

Further observations include that almost every answer began with a # for all models. Additionally, the base model's answers had a conversational style. Most answers start with a greeting like *Hello! I'm here to help you with your question* and end with a closing sentence like *Please let me know if you have any further questions or if*

there's anything else I can help with! Conversely, the other models never addressed the user directly.

Furthermore, hallucinations occur, especially when the questions involve numerical data. For instance, when the MC question asks which of the listed minerals is the hardest according to the Mohs hardness scale [82], the models hallucinate hardness values for each mineral.

Another critical observation refers to the variability in the model's output. During SFT, the model must have learned to favor *B* as the answer for MC questions and *True* as the solution for TF queries. For MC questions, 15 out of 20 prompts were answered with *B*, while **all** TF questions were answered with *True*. However, after RLHF, the model showed a greater variety in its responses. Only 9 times *B* was generated, and 3 answers were classified as *False*. The RLHF model became more exploratory, leading to the improvement in correct answers compared to the SFT model.

To conclude, a trade off between the level of elaboration and the appearance of hallucinations in the models' responses can be observed. But for all models, the rate of correct answers does not surpass "guessing", i.e. providing a suitable answer by chance instead of activating their base knowledge.

The base model produces coherent texts, making it difficult for non-geoscience experts to identify factual errors and hallucinations. Conversely, SFT and RLHF models showed straightforward answers, i.e. generated one-word answers without further context, making it difficult for non-geoscience experts to understand the results. This behavior makes it hard to determine which model is more helpful to the user.

Open Tasks

After completing the human evaluation for the open tasks, the results are stored in Appendix A.4.2 as a table and depicted in Figure 9.4. The observations, together with further observations, are discussed individually for each task type.

Examining the performance of the models in answering **completion tasks**, as depicted in Figure 9.4a, reveals similar tendencies to the closed tasks. On the first sight, the base model appears superior, since it scores perfectly for *grammatical correctness*, *repetition*, and *task answering*.

Figure 9.4: Scores achieved during human evaluation

The RLHF and SFT models seem to fall behind in those categories. As observed for closed tasks, they tend to repeat sentences or paragraphs instead of concluding their answers, which leads to incorrect grammatical structures such as *#1: The three stages of rock deformation development are #1: The three stages of rock deformation development are [...]*.

Moreover, the rate of outputs that provide an answer to the question is relatively low for the RLHF model. For approximately half of the prompts, the RLHF model repeats the input prompt without responding. Before conducting RLHF, problems with completion tasks had been diagnosed, and the reward model was trained accordingly. However, the RLHF did not make significant progress in answering completion questions.

The base model received higher scores for *level of expertise*, i.e. how scientific an answer sounds, because it explains each term inserted into the blanks. On the other hand, SFT and RLHF models usually produce words without further explanation. This behavior is responsible for the reverse hallucination scores. The RLHF model

showed the fewest tendency for hallucination because it never generates more than one sentence.

Surprisingly, all models struggled to produce correct answers. The models only produce partly correct answers, especially in cases where several blanks need to be filled. For instance, when confronted with the input prompt *According to the mechanical properties of plate activity, the contact types of plate boundary can be divided into _____ And _____ Three*, the base model responded with [...] 1. *Divergent boundary: This type is [...]* 2. *Convergent boundary: This type is [...]* 3. *Transform boundary: This type [...]* *It's important to note that [...]*. Convergent boundary is the only correct answer, whereas the others were hallucinations. Both the SFT and RLHF models gave an identical response: *According to the mechanical properties of plate activity, the contact types of plate boundary can be divided into divergent, convergent, and transform boundaries*. Again, only a convergent boundary is accurate.

The different types of answers become evident: The base model generates a lot of text explaining its answers, although the results are never fully correct, which causes extensive hallucination. Conversely, the other two models provide more dense answers that only focus on completing the sentence.

Further observations include that the base model engages with the user through introductory sentences such as *Sure, I'd be happy to help you!* However, the base model tends to overdo the tasks, consistently applying the same answer pattern for each input prompt. It starts with an introductory paragraph engaging with the user and roughly naming the topic, then lists solutions with extensive explanations, and concludes with general remarks and limitations about the prompt and the topic. This behavior often causes the base model to produce multiple answers, even though only one blank needs to be filled.

On the other hand, the SFT and RLHF models distinguish better between one-blank and multiple-blank input prompts and provide either a single solution or the correct number of solutions required to fill the available blanks.

Figure 9.4b presents the results for the **definition tasks**. Across all evaluated aspects, the scores for definition tasks are relatively high for each model. Still, the trends observed in the models' behaviors during completion tasks are also found here. However, while some repetition did occur in the RLHF model's answers, it was significantly less compared to completion and closed tasks.

Like completion tasks, the base model seems to show the highest level of expertise based on the level of detail of its answers. Each definition consists of multiple paragraphs. Conversely, the SFT and RLHF models provide definitions ranging from one to three sentences. Again, these models demonstrated fewer hallucinations since they focused on the essential parts of the definitions.

For all models, the scores for *content correctness* are higher than for the completion tasks. The models show the ability to accurately define nouns from the domain of geoscience.

Yet, the lower score for the RLHF model could not be attributed to a lack of expertise. Instead, the model sometimes repeated the noun without definition, lowering the scores. Each time the RLHF model generated a definition, it was correct.

Again, further observations revealed the tendency of the base model to provide excessively detailed answers. For instance, when asked to shortly define the term *Moho surface*, the base model responded with *# Sure, I'd be happy to help! Here's a short definition for the term "Moho surface": Moho surface: The Moho surface, also known as the Mohorovičić surface, is a boundary between the Earth's crust and mantle. It is the surface below which the Earth's crust becomes too hot and dense to support life, and it marks the transition from the lithosphere (the outermost solid layer of the Earth) to the asthenosphere (the layer of partially molten rock beneath the lithosphere). The Moho surface is typically located at a depth of around 35-40 kilometers (22-25 miles) below the Earth's surface, although it can vary in depth depending on the location and tectonic setting.*

In comparison, the SFT model can limit its answer to the crucial points, e.g. *# Moho surface: The Moho surface is the boundary between the Earth's crust and the mantle. It is the surface where the crust and mantle meet and is characterized by a sudden change in the density and composition of the rocks.*

Lastly, the RLHF model provides a brief but correct definition: *# The Moho surface is the boundary between the crust and the mantle.*

Overall, all models displayed commendable performance in addressing definition tasks, with the SFT model particularly excelling due to its ability to strike the ideal balance between brevity and accuracy.

Generally, all models showed a good performance in addressing definition tasks; however, the performance of the SFT model stood out. The base model's answers were unnecessarily long. The model has been unable to get the definition down to the

point, although the instruction asks for a **short** definition. The RLHF model shows a solid base knowledge of the geoscience terms but sometimes fails to generate an answer, which limits its evaluation scores. However, the SFT model finds the right balance between explanation and sticking to the essential points.

Figure 9.4c depicts the results of the **QA tasks**. Unlike definition and completion tasks, the RLHF model does not show repetitive structures in its outputs. Meanwhile, the SFT model here shows more repetitive structures, which negatively influences its scores for *task answering* and *level of expertise* while decreasing the occurrences of hallucinations. The RLHF model performs almost at the same level as the base model *for task answering* and *level of expertise*.

Interestingly, despite generating more extended and elaborate responses for QA tasks than for the other tasks, the RLHF model can maintain a lower hallucination rate than the base model. The base model still talks a lot and remains at a superficial level of explanation, whereas the RLHF model now tends to explain a particular aspect in more detail.

For content correctness, all three models show similar performance, producing only partially correct answers.

However, when confronted with more general questions, the models performed better than for explicit geoscientific questions. For example, when responding to questions about the human influence on climate change, the models all answered correctly. However, when dealing with more specific subjects like the mixing phenomenon of clastic particles with varying grain sizes, none of the models generated accurate answers. Instead, they all produced long texts of inaccurate and superficial information.

Another observation centers around the tendency of all three models to respond using a list format. The more complex and broad the topic of the answer, the more likely models are to break it down into smaller subtopics.

Additionally, the base model refused to address three questions due to the prompt's harmful language or insufficient context. This behavior is not welcome for geoscientific questions without harmful language.

RLHF demonstrated the most effective performance for this task, producing detailed responses without excessive hallucination.

Examining the **discussion tasks** (Figure 9.4d), all models received high scores across all aspects investigated. However, again, the SFT and RLHF models tended to have repetitive structure in their answers. This tendency affected the ratings for *level of expertise* and *task answering*. For instance, the SFT model repeats the statement *The continental cratons are destroyed because of the plate tectonics*. Twenty-three times when questioned about why stable continental cratons get destroyed.

Rating the generated discussions as correct or not was a challenge. This is why almost all outputs were rated with a 1, i.e. intermediate performance. Most of the discussions contained partially correct information, but the discussions also had their imitations when it came to details.

Both the SFT and RLHF models showed only some hallucinations, while the base model falls behind. The base model maintained rather superficially in its discussions. Moreover, its argumentation structure was unclear, favoring lists over textual discussions. Appendix A.4.3 contains an example of a discussion generated by the base and the SFT model.

The base model starts each discussion with an introductory paragraph about itself as an AI assistant and states that the topic is too broad to be discussed in depth. It ends its discussion with a paragraph about the limitations of its answer. In between, some facts and strategies are listed and explained but not discussed. This is why the answers remain somewhat vague.

In contrast, the SFT model produced a shorter discussion paragraph with a clear argumentation structure. This paragraph contains the same information as the base model's answer but in a more dense focused manner, aligning with the requirements of discussion tasks.

Both the SFT and RLHF models demonstrated comparable performance for this task type, outperforming the base model.

As previously observed for the QA tasks, all models displayed most robust performance for questions aiming at foundational knowledge in geosciences compared to concrete topic-specific questions.

In **conclusion**, several tendencies emerged while evaluating open tasks for the three models. The RLHF and SFT models encountered challenges in developing answers to all prompts. For some prompts, they repeated those prompts (once or multiple times) instead of generating an answer. It was not impossible to pinpoint

which prompts triggered this behavior.

With only a few exceptions, the base model successfully generated answers for all prompts. However, the responses often surpassed the token limit. These answers might appear scientific, but closer examination reveals that they contain inaccurate information and hallucinations. Such responses could potentially lead users to develop misunderstandings about the discussed topics.

On the other side, if the RLHF and SFT models did generate answers, they were on a reasonable level, containing fewer hallucinations and highlighting the crucial aspects of the questions better than the base model. The performance of RLHF and SFT models was similar for most task types, but the SFT model showed less repetition in its answers.

Still, all three models have room for improvement regarding factual correctness. Although all models have limitations in terms of performance, the SFT and RLHF models are preferred over the base model since they provide more precise answers, which enhances human readability.

9.3.3 Limitations

The evaluation of open questions has several limitations that should be addressed. The scope of this evaluation was relatively small, consisting of 80 prompts for four different tasks per model. In total, 240 prompts were evaluated, which already consumed much time.

Further, the evaluation process was carried out by a single person, i.e. the author of the thesis. While having a single evaluator ensures consistency throughout the assessment, the evaluation might be influenced by the subjective preferences of the evaluator. Additionally, the evaluator could have shown a bias towards the RLHF model since it decides whether this thesis's domain specialisation approach is successful.

Lastly, it is essential to note that the person evaluating the answers has no expertise in geosciences. Consequently, the evaluation results rely heavily on the provided gold labels within the dataset and external resources like Wikipedia to gather further information.

10 Discussion

This chapter is dedicated to a discussion of the findings in this thesis. The first section 10.1 interprets the results obtained from the evaluation presented in Chapter 9. It addresses each research question proposed in Chapter 3. The second section 10.2 addresses the limitations encountered throughout the thesis. It critically examines each step of the domain specialization process, highlighting constraints that may have influenced the results. The final section 10.3 explores the potential for future research. It suggests how the following studies could build on these findings to further explore the possibilities in domain specialization of LLMs.

10.1 Discussion of results

This section discusses the results and explores potential reasons behind the observed outcomes in this thesis. It also presents where the results of the qualitative and quantitative analyses align and where they diverge. Each subsection aims to answer the research questions proposed in Section 3.2.

10.1.1 Prompt crafting

The research question under investigation was: *What is the impact of applying prompt crafting before the augmentation step, and how is it expected to affect the overall performance and consistency of the geoscience-specialized LLM?*

An extensive answer to this question is challenging since the model was only fine-tuned once - using prompt templates - and it is impossible to compare the model's performance *after* SFT with and without the prompt template. Still, several insights can be derived from the comparative analysis of the model during inference with and without the prompt template *before* SFT.

The Llama 2 13B Chat model was configured using a prompt template. The experiments conducted in Section 6.1 indicate that employing this prompt template during inference enhances the model's helpfulness, reduces instances of hallucination, and improves the correctness of the content.

Additionally, the insertion of a system prompt has been shown to increase the model's performance in general, underscoring the significant influence of prompt structure on

the model's ability to answer questions (see Section 6.2).

Based on these results, reinforcing the template during SFT seems to be the most effective approach for SFT. Prompt crafting aims at provoking the model's best performance during SFT, which results in more accurate and robust answers after SFT.

The harmlessness and quality of the outputs generated by the model after SFT, when using both the prompt template and the system prompt during SFT, were evaluated in Chapter 9. The findings demonstrate an improved performance from the base model to the SFT model.

While it is difficult to precisely quantify the impact of prompt crafting throughout the entire process of specializing a model in the geoscience domain, it can be concluded that it did not harm the model's performance. Therefore, prompt crafting appears to be a valid and promising approach for future domain specialization and SFT studies.

10.1.2 SFT

The research question under investigation was: *How does the supervised fine-tuning using domain-specific data influence the model's ability to incorporate and use geoscientific knowledge?*

Both closed and open tasks were analyzed to gain insights into this development. Regarding the closed tasks, the quantitative evaluation revealed that the SFT model performed above average compared to several general-purpose and (geo)scientific LLMs. The results for the APE data and the overall average are the second best (see Table 9.3). However, the only model outperforming the SFT model was the base model. There are ambiguous tendencies in the results. The SFT model surpassed the base model on the NPEE dataset, but the base model performed better for the APE data.

The qualitative analysis puts the model's performance into perspective (see Figure 9.3). The SFT model's results for content correctness are not only poorer than the base model's but also low in general. Out of 20 prompts, the SFT model answered only four correctly in MC questions and 12 in TF questions. These findings suggest that the SFT did not significantly enhance the base model's geoscience-related knowledge.

Looking at the open tasks, the content quality was not individually evaluated in the quantitative analysis. However, generally, the SFT model exhibited weaker overall

performance than the base model (see Figure 9.2). The SFT model's performance on fill-in-the-blank tasks dropped significantly, likely because such questions were not included in the SFT dataset in contrast to the other open tasks. However, for discussion and QA questions, the SFT model's answers were preferred over those of the base model more often.

In the qualitative analysis of open tasks, each task's content correctness was evaluated individually (see Figure 9.4). For fill-in-the-blank questions, the base model produced more correct answers. For all other tasks, both models achieved similar scores for content correctness. Both models performed better on questions that require elaboration, such as discussion and definition tasks, while tasks with unambiguous answers, like completion and QA, showed poor factual knowledge. The results suggest that the model did not significantly enrich its geoscience knowledge.

Despite the shortcomings in incorporating geoscientific knowledge, the model was still improved during SFT. The SFT model produced significantly fewer hallucinations compared to the base model. Additionally, the answers generated by the SFT model were shorter and more dense, indicating that the ability to be more concrete is increased. The SFT successfully trained the model to answer specific tasks rather than specific topics.

Concluding, the SFT did not enhance the base model's geoscientific knowledge. The correctness of the outputs was generally poor, either equal to or worse than the base model's performance. However, the SFT succeeded differently. It improved the model's ability to provide more concrete and less hallucinative answers. Therefore, the SFT model's performance improved over the base model.

10.1.3 RLHF

The research question under investigation was: *What are the effects of employing RLHF on the model's alignment with human preferences and its performance in geoscientific tasks?*

Tendencies regarding the alignment with human preferences can be mainly derived from the qualitative analysis (see Section 9.3). Overall, the RLHF model presented different tendencies in its behavior. On the one side, approximately one-fourth of its outputs for open and closed tasks failed to address the given question, which indicates a divergence from human preferences. The model repeats the input prompt

one or multiple times without providing any new context or information. Conversely, compared to the base and SFT models, the RLHF model's answers were more closely aligned with human preferences. RLHF reduced hallucinations and excessive elaboration. This led to more concrete answers highlighting the important crucial necessary to answer the question, making the output clearer and easier to read and understand.

Compared to the SFT model, the RLHF model generated more diverse answers for closed tasks. Although no specific temperature setting was chosen during the training, the model learned during RLHF that output generation with a higher temperature improves content correctness in closed tasks. Contrastingly, the SFT model produced more factually correct answers for open tasks, except for QA tasks (see Figure 9.4).

Overall, regarding the performance in geoscientific tasks in general, the shift from the SFT to the RLHF model did not result in significant changes. While they both show the same tendency in their answers regarding the overall structure of the answer and the content as well, the RLHF model demonstrated some advancements for specific tasks.

This discrepancy can be linked to optimizing the RM setup for QA tasks containing conversation datasets and the absence of fill-in-the-blank questions in the SFT data. The RLHF model's performance improved for QA tasks (in comparison to the base and SFT models) and fill-in-the-blank questions (in comparison to the SFT model), as shown in Figure 9.2a. The improvement in QA tasks can be attributed to the fact that the reward model was initially pre-trained using a dataset optimized in QA, i.e. contained conversations instead of single answers. Additionally, the reward model was fine-tuned to fill-in-the-blank questions which can be the reason for the RLHF model's performance increase compared to the SFT model. Fill-in-the-blank questions were not part of the SFT data. These results show that the RLHF influenced the RLHF model in general.

Despite these promising developments for fill-in-the-blank and QA tasks, the RLHF model showed an increased tendency to fail to respond to queries compared to the SFT model. This makes it difficult to determine if RLHF, in general, led to an improvement in answering geoscientific questions.

However, the positive tendencies caused by RLHF seem surprising since the logged statistics during the policy training suggested a slightly unsuccessful training. During the policy training, the KL objective function was hacked by negating the KL

penalty instead of improving the rewards and enhancing the model's performance. Nonetheless, the outcome that even a slightly unsuccessful policy training can improve the model's behavior for certain kinds of tasks underscores the potential of applying RLHF to specialize LLMs in different domains.

10.1.4 Success of the approach

The specific research question under investigation was: *Can the domain specialization approach applied in this thesis be seen as successful?*

However, there is no straightforward positive or negative answer to the question of its success. Instead, some aspects can be considered successful while others leave room for improvement.

In particular, the resulting RLHF model constructed by applying prompt crafting, SFT, and RLHF still has several areas for improvement. When assessing closed tasks, the model's performance falls behind the base model regarding factual knowledge presented. Additionally, the RLHF model's accuracy in answering closed questions is only slightly better than that of random guesses. However, the results are still as good as those produced by the first model successfully specialized in geoscience, *K2* [30].

Open tasks present a more complex picture. The RLHF model still shows limitations regarding factual knowledge; however, it also reveals improvements over the base model in formulating answers to geoscience questions. Unfortunately, the current state of the model does not yet serve as a competent geoscience assistant capable of reliably answering geoscience questions.

Despite all the limitations discussed in Section 10.2, the domain specialization approach appears promising. Besides the opportunities for improvements, such as more hyperparameter tuning during SFT and RLHF or fine-tuning a reward model instead of constructing one from scratch, the final model displays enhanced features over the initial base model. Throughout the process of domain specialization, the model's ability to identify essential facts for a response and avoid lengthy elaborations on irrelevant details improved. The three steps, prompt crafting, SFT, and RLHF positively impacted the model's performance.

Prompt crafting as a first step during SFT enhances the model's outputs by reducing hallucinations and preserving its capability to discuss geoscientific topics. SFT shifted

the model's focus toward knowledge presentation instead of elaboration, whereas RLHF fine-tuned and optimized the model's behavior for specific tasks, such as Question Answering. Although the approach requires further refinement, the progress observed after each step highlights the need for future research.

While the resulting model from our domain specialization approach falls short of meeting the desired level of performance, the approach itself holds great potential. This thesis provides exciting insights into the evolution of a model during the different stages of domain specialization; however, the full potential of this approach has not yet been realized.

10.2 Limitations

First, some general limitations of the study are discussed before identifying limitations for the specific steps of domain specialization applied.

This thesis should be seen as an experiment to determine whether the new domain specialization approach can serve as a base for further investigation and research. It does not aim to present the tested approach as a solution to the challenge of domain specialization.

Additionally, this study was conducted by a single person within a limited timeframe of under four months. In contrast, large research groups with combined expertise typically do similar research in this field. Also, the hardware used during the implementation and execution of this approach was limited to an A100 GPU with 100 GB of RAM, though the capacity was never fully used.

This paragraph examines limitations of prompt crafting executed before the SFT (see Chapter 6).

The effect of prompt crafting and applying a prompt template to each prompt within the SFT dataset is largely underexplored. To the best of the author's knowledge, the study by Lyu et al. [79] is the only one exclusively focusing on the influence of prompt templates within the SFT data. Consequently, the chapter on prompt crafting heavily relies on their findings.

A proof of concept was conducted using human evaluation to assess whether the model's performance during inference improved with prompt templates compared to without templates. However, the author lacks geoscience expertise, and the evaluation, therefore, relied heavily on the gold labels provided in the dataset.

A similar issue occurred when defining a system prompt. The influence of the system prompt was evaluated without specific knowledge of the geoscience domain. Additionally, the subset of 20 prompts is relatively tiny to assessing different system prompts.

Another limitation is that LLMs show extreme sensitivity to minor syntax changes, e.g., the presence or absence of a colon at the end of a prompt [113]. This makes it impossible to test all system prompt variations. This is supported by the findings of Sclar et al. [113] on language model sensitivity. Also, many different approaches to formulating a system prompt have emerged [136] and only a small subset of these approaches can be tested in this thesis.

Lastly, the influence of the prompt template and system prompt was tested solely based on the outputs generated during inference. Changes during inference, e.g., the probabilistic distributions over the next word prediction, were not examined. Changes in the fine-tuning itself based on the prompt template and system prompt were not investigated either.

The following two paragraphs address the limitations of the SFT. The first paragraph describes limitations regarding the procedure and the data, whereas the second one describes limitations regarding the implementation.

As described in Chapter 7, two distinct rounds of SFT were conducted, one for alignment with human question-answering and one for alignment with geoscience experts. This approach followed Deng et al. [30], who found that multiple rounds of fine-tuning yielded better results than a single round. However, this assumption was not questioned or validated within this thesis. Traditionally, a single round of SFT is preferred over multiple rounds since the possible improvement by the model decreases with each additional round of SFT. It can also be questioned whether the first round of SFT for aligning with human behavior is necessary, especially for a chat-optimized model like LLama 2 13B Chat.

The dataset used for SFT has areas for improvement, particularly regarding the gold labels. Some prompts were taken from geoscientific QA forums on the internet, using the first answer as the gold label. However, the first response does not always answer the question accurately. Furthermore, some prompts lacked instructions, e.g., indicating whether a sentence is true or false, which limits the model's performance since the generated outputs, e.g., contextual information about the prompt's topic, did not match the provided labels, e.g., true or false. Manually verifying the dataset quality could have improved the training outcomes, but no time and resources were

left.

Regarding the implementation, the limitations are mainly related to the hyperparameters. Although extensive hyperparameter testing was conducted on a subset of 200 prompts, the chosen hyperparameters were not optimal. As a consequence, the hyperparameters provided by Pytorch [100] were used, and they were not tailored to the specific case of domain specialization. However, more extensive experimentation and further hyperparameter testing on a more significant subset of the SFT dataset were beyond the scope of this thesis.

Additionally, the study did not verify if the hyperparameters applied in the second round of SFT, i.e., the same as in the first round, were still appropriate. After the initial round of SFT, the model's parameters might have changed, which might cause the need for adjustments in the hyperparameter settings. During the second round of SFT, the training loss fluctuated more than desired, highlighting the need for additional hyperparameter tuning. This emphasizes the importance of optimizing hyperparameters for each specific fine-tuning stage to achieve stable and improved performance.

There are several limitations regarding the RLHF as well. The study used a pre-trained reward model, which was trained with a chat dataset focusing on harmlessness and helpfulness [4]. Using a pre-trained model limits the flexibility in optimizing the reward model for the specific requirements of this thesis. However, training a reward model from scratch was impossible due to time constraints and insufficient data.

Further limitations regarding the training of the reward model are discussed in Section 8.1.4. These limitations include issues related to the dataset created and the hyperparameters used for fine-tuning.

As discussed in Section 8.2.3, the results of the policy training were not optimal. The average rewards per batch did not increase, and the KL penalty values became slightly negative. These are indicators that the model has hacked the KL objective function during training rather than optimizing the policy for higher rewards. Solving this issue is non-trivial and could stem from many different factors. One potential reason could be the hyperparameter settings, including a batch size that was too small. Another possibility is the generation configuration's setting, which might have led the model to experiment more with its responses. Also, techniques like gradient clipping, which is used to save memory, might have influenced the model's behavior during

training. Further testing and refinement are necessary to identify and address the reason for this problem.

The limitations of the evaluation process were discussed in detail in the respective chapter. Section 9.2.3 highlights limitations in the quantitative analysis, mainly focusing on the reliability of the responses from GPT-4o. Section 9.3.3 addresses the limitations of the qualitative analysis. A major limitation was that the evaluation was conducted by a single person lacking geoscience expertise. The lack of domain-specific knowledge may have affected the accuracy and validity of the results.

10.3 Implications for future work

The field of domain specialization in LLMs has shown great potential but still needs a lot of further research as highlighted by Ling et al. [71]. Also, regarding this specific thesis, room for future research emerges. Three ideas are presented below.

One direction is to delve deeper into the role of prompt crafting in the domain specialization process. This study could be carried out twice to gain a clearer understanding of the effects that prompt templates using SFT and inference have on the model's stability and capacity to respond accurately to geoscience-related queries. In the first run, a prompt template and a system prompt could be used, while in the second run, prompt crafting could be omitted entirely. Comparing the results from both experiments helps to assess the contributions of the prompt template and the system prompt to the model's overall domain-specific performance.

Another area of research lies in evaluating the models' performance for specific topics within the given datasets. This thesis focused primarily on analyzing the performance for several tasks rather than topics due to the labels given within the datasets. Investigating how well the model performs for each topic could offer insights for optimizing the structure and content of the SFT dataset.

Lastly, there lies potential in executing more extensive hyperparameter tuning for SFT, reward model training and policy training. As demonstrated in this thesis, all methods have shown improvements in specializing a model in the domain of geoscience; however, further experimentation and optimization could lead to even more significant improvements in the realm of domain specialization for LLMs.

11 Conclusion

This thesis aims to contribute to the field of domain specialization for LLMs. In particular, a new approach to refining a general-purpose open-source LLM in the geoscience domain was tested. The geoscience domain served as an example throughout this thesis, however, the goal was to propose a new approach for domain specialization that is generalizable and, therefore, applicable to all kinds of domains in the future.

In particular, the potential of using RLHF, including SFT, for domain specialization has been explored. Combining different refinement strategies has proved promising in related works, which is why the process of RLHF was enriched by prompt crafting. Specifically, prompt crafting was executed before RLHF since it was expected to enhance SFT and RLHF training outcomes by including the optimized prompts within the training datasets.

The proceeding used to specialize a model in the domain of geoscience combined a grey-box approach with two white-box approaches. According to Ling et al. [71, p. 26], this combination "could provide a balance between resource requirement and model performance and might be especially effective when dealing with scarce domain-specific data." Prompt crafting is part of the grey-box approaches, while SFT and RLHF fall into the white-box approaches category.

Four research questions were answered in the scope of this thesis. The first research objective is to show the impact of applying prompt crafting before the SFT and RLHF steps and give insights on how it is expected to affect the overall performance and consistency of the geoscience-specialized LLM. The second research question is how the supervised fine-tuning using domain-specific data influenced the model's ability to incorporate and use geoscientific knowledge. Thirdly, the effects of employing RLHF on the model's alignment with human preferences and its performance in geoscientific tasks are estimated. Lastly, whether the domain specialization approach applied in this thesis is seen as successful is answered.

Regarding the effect of prompt crafting, it is expected that prompt crafting enhanced the model's overall performance. The experiments conducted in Section 6.1 indicate that employing a prompt template during inference enhances the model's helpfulness, reduces instances of hallucination, and improves the correctness of the content. Prompt crafting provoked the model's best performance during inference, which

is why it is also expected to result in more accurate and robust answers after SFT and RLHF. While it is difficult to precisely quantify the impact of prompt crafting throughout the entire process of specializing a model in the geoscience domain, it can be concluded that it did not harm the model's performance. Therefore, prompt crafting appears to be a valid and promising approach for future domain specialization research.

Regarding incorporating of geoscientific knowledge during SFT, the quantitative evaluation for closed tasks revealed that the SFT model performed above average compared to several general-purpose and (geo)scientific LLMs. However, manually evaluating these results revealed that the SFT model's results for content correctness are not only poorer than those of the base model but also generally low. The results were only slightly better than "guessing".

For open tasks, the SFT model's performance on fill-in-the-blank tasks dropped significantly, likely because such types of questions were not included in the SFT dataset in contrast to the other open tasks. However, the SFT model's answers were preferred over those of the base model for discussion and QA questions more often in quantitative analysis.

The results suggest that the model did not significantly enrich its geoscience knowledge. However, the model still improved during SFT by showing significantly fewer hallucinations than the base model. Additionally, the answers generated by the SFT model were shorter and more dense, indicating that the ability to be more concrete is increased. The SFT successfully trained the model to answer specific tasks rather than specific topics.

Different tendencies were found regarding the effectiveness of RLHF in terms of human alignment. On the one hand, for approximately one-fourth of its outputs for both open and closed the RLHF model simply repeats the input prompt one or multiple times without providing any new context or information, which cannot be in line with human preferences. Conversely, compared to the base and SFT models, the RLHF model's answers were more closely aligned with human preferences since RLHF reduced hallucinations and excessive elaboration, making the output more straightforward and easier to read and understand.

However, the positive tendencies caused by RLHF are surprising since the logged statistics during the policy training suggested a slightly unsuccessful training. Nonetheless, it is shown that even a somewhat unsuccessful policy training can improve the

model's behavior for certain kinds of tasks, which underscores the potential of applying RLHF to specialize LLMs in different domains.

Regarding the overall success of the domain specialization approach, there is no straightforward positive or negative answer to the question of its success. In particular, the resulting RLHF model constructed by applying prompt crafting, SFT, and RLHF still has several areas for improvement. The current state of the model does not yet serve as a competent geoscience assistant capable of reliably answering geoscience questions. However, the results are on a similar level as the ones produced by the other two models "successfully" specialized in the domain of geoscience, *K2* [30] and *Geogalactica 30B* [70], trained with SFT only, which underlines the need for further research in this area.

Despite all the limitations discussed in Section 10.2, the domain specialization approach appears promising. Besides the opportunities for improvements, such as more hyperparameter tuning during SFT and RLHF or fine-tuning a reward model instead of constructing one from scratch, the final model displays enhanced features over the initial base model. The three steps, prompt crafting, SFT, and RLHF positively impacted the model's performance. Overall, this thesis provides exciting insights into the evolution of a model during the different stages of domain specialization; however, the full potential of this approach has not yet been realized.

Acknowledgment

First, I would like to thank **Prof. Dr. Erhard Hinrichs** and **Prof. Dr. Michael Franke** for supervising my Master's thesis and supporting me throughout the process.

I would also like to thank **Polina Tsvilodub**, who mentored me through implementing and writing this thesis and gave me valuable advice and support whenever needed.

Additionally, I acknowledge the support and the computational resources provided by the state of Baden-Württemberg through bwHPC and the German Research Foundation (DFG) through grant INST 35/1597-1 FUGG.

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Appendix

A.1 Prompting

A.1.1 Randomly sampled prompts for Sections 5.1, 6.1, 6.2

The following prompts were randomly sampled using a seed of 33. The first 20 prompts were used in Section 5.1 to compare the performance of different models based on their geoscience knowledge and in Section 6.2 to test and evaluate different system prompts. The whole 50 prompts were used to conduct a proof of concept if embedding the user input prompts into a prompt template yields better results (Section 6.1). All human evaluation result tables can be found in the Github-Repository of this thesis.

1. Identify which instrument is string or percussion: Kenong, Zeze
2. Could you clarify the origin time of the M 4.7 - 19km NW of Truckee, CA for me?
3. Create a cocktail recipe.
4. Is it possible for who has shear Modulus and damping ratio (values) for Shales and Sandstone to share it? Will use in site response analysis, the same like (Modulus for clay (Seed and Sun, 1989) and damping for clay (Idriss 1990)).
5. Is autotrophic metabolism a narrower category or subdiscipline within phototroph diversity and metabolism in geoscience?
6. Based on the paragraph given, list down some important points regarding Bhopal city
Bhopal is the capital city of the Indian state of Madhya Pradesh and the administrative headquarters of both Bhopal district and Bhopal division. It is known as the City of Lakes due to its various natural and artificial lakes. It is also one of the greenest cities in India. It is the 16th largest city in India and 131st in the world. After the formation of Madhya Pradesh, Bhopal was part of the Sehore district. It was bifurcated in 1972 and a new district, Bhopal, was formed. Flourishing around 1707, the city was the capital of the former Bhopal State, a princely state of the British ruled by the Nawabs of Bhopal. Numerous heritage structures from this period include the Taj-ul-Masajid and Taj Mahal palace. In 1984, the city was struck by the Bhopal disaster, one of the worst industrial disasters in history.

7. Can Middle Oceanic Spreading Ridges be swallowed by a subduction zone? Middle oceanic ridges are places where new oceanic crust is generated. Does anybody know what happens to these spreading ridges when the oceanic basin starts to be closed? Is there any possibility that the once-active middle oceanic ridge be swallowed into the mantle at a oceanic-continental plate convergence boundary?
8. Could you extract the terms related to earth science mentioned in this passage? The passage: The Christian Democratic Party of Honduras (Spanish: Partido Demócrata Cristiano de Honduras), known by the abbreviation DC, is a political party in Honduras. At the legislative elections, held on 25 November 2001, DC won 3.7% of the popular vote and 3 out of 128 seats in the National Congress. Its candidate at the presidential elections, Marco Orlando Iriarte, won 1.0% of the vote.
9. What terms in this passage have a connection to earth science? The passage: The music was composed by Mani Sharma and released by Aditya Music. Best First Film of a Director - V. V. Vinayak; Best Editor - Gowtham Raju; Special Jury Award - Jr. NTR; Best Lyricist - Chandrabose.
10. Please tell me a synonym for the word 'coelurosaurs'.
11. What do giant Pandas eats? The giant panda is a bear species endemic to China. It is a Carnivora, the giant panda is a folivore, with bamboo shoots and leaves making up more than 99% of its diet.
12. Which of the following sentences about infrared waves is true? They can be used to treat cancerous tumours. They can be used to make images of bones, through the skin. They can be used for cooking. They are used to send communication signals to satellites.
13. Please tell me the related paper of the Armellinoite-(Ce).
14. How do geologists use hydrological data and modeling to support water resources planning and decision-making processes?
15. Biological Evolution Today? Biological Evolution The scientific theory of evolution by natural selection was proposed by Charles Darwin its book On the Origin of Species (1859). BEFORE DARWIN : Fixism and transformism are adopted by the scientifics to explain the living beings. DARWIN : On the Origin of Species (1859): (Introduction ; CHAPTER I. Variation under Domestication. CHAPTER II. Variation under Nature. CHAPTER III. Struggle for Existence. CHAPTER IV. Natural Selection. CHAPTER V. Laws of Variation. CHAPTER VI. Difficulties on Theory. CHAPTER VII. Instinct. CHAPTER

VIII. Hybridism. CHAPTER IX. On the Imperfection of the Geological Record. CHAPTER X. On the Geological Succession of Biological Beings. CHAPTER XI. Geographical Distribution. CHAPTER XII. Geographical Distribution—continued CHAPTER XIII. Mutual Affinities of Organic Beings: Morphology: Embryology: Rudimentary Organs. CHAPTER XIV. Recapitulation and Conclusion. Darwin has published a large number of books and articles on geology, biology, ect .. Today, evolution (Synthetic Theory of Evolution) is based on a very large number of specialty : Paleontology and other Earth sciences, taxonomic, Molecular biology, Ethology, Ecology, Physiology, Cel. Biology, TODAY, HOW RESEARCHERS SEE THE THEORY OF EVOLUTION IN THE LIGHT OF INNUMERABLE DISCOVERIES OF MODERN SCIENCE? "

16. What mathematical techniques are employed in the analysis and interpretation of microseismic data for reservoir monitoring?
17. Name three common sources of energy that can be used to generate electricity.
18. Run a sentiment analysis on the tweet. Love the new update!
19. What information do you have about titles, styles and honours in the context of princess christina of the netherlands?
20. You are given a question on high school biology. You are also given 4 answer options (associated with ""A"", ""B"", ""C"", ""D""), out of which only one is correct. You need to answer the question by selecting the correct option. You should only answer with the choice letter, not the whole answer. The upper forelimbs of humans and bats have fairly similar skeletal structures, whereas the corresponding bones in whales have very different shapes and proportions. However, genetic data suggest that all three kinds of organisms diverged from a common ancestor at about the same time. Which of the following is the most likely explanation for these data? Choose from: A. Humans and bats evolved by natural selection, and whales evolved by Lamarckian mechanisms. B. Forelimb evolution was adaptive in people and bats, but not in whales. C. Natural selection in an aquatic environment resulted in significant changes to whale forelimb anatomy. D. Genes mutate faster in whales than in humans or bats. The answer is:
21. Extract the areas of science using differential equations in this text in an alphabetically ordered list. A differential equation is a mathematical equation for an unknown function of one or several variables that relates the values of the function itself and its derivatives of various orders. Differential equations play a prominent role in engineering, physics, economics, biology, and other disciplines. Differential equations arise in many areas of science and technology, specifically

whenever a deterministic relation involving some continuously varying quantities (modelled by functions) and their rates of change in space or time (expressed as derivatives) is known or postulated. This is illustrated in classical mechanics, where the motion of a body is described by its position and velocity as the time value varies. Newton's laws allow one (given the position, velocity, acceleration and various forces acting on the body) to express these variables dynamically as a differential equation for the unknown position of the body as a function of time. In some cases, this differential equation (called an equation of motion) may be solved explicitly.

22. I'm curious about the ideal chemistry of the Belendorffite.
23. What are the techniques used to interpret and map the distribution of geologic features associated with river systems and fluvial processes?
24. Identify the choice that best completes the statement or answers the question. A student is investigating changes in the states of matter. The student fills a graduated cylinder with 50 milliliters of packed snow. The graduated cylinder has a mass of 50 grams when empty and 95 grams when filled with the snow. The packed snow changes to liquid water when the snow is put in a warm room. Which statement best describes this process? Choose from: A. Cooling causes the snow to melt. B. Cooling causes the snow to freeze. C. Heating causes the snow to freeze. D. Heating causes the snow to melt. The answer is:
25. Tell me about your experience with Python programming
26. Can you identify the named entities in: Geochronological data from the mammal fauna of the Pannonian basin during the Late Pleistocene are compiled. Thirty-four megafaunal samples (including both fossil bone and associated materials such as charcoal), previously radiocarbon dated by accelerator mass spectrometry and conventional methods, range from 43 to 10.3?
27. Give a detailed example of how machine learning is being used in agriculture.
28. What are some related concepts to with medium-sized and large cations(sulfates (selenates, etc.) without additional anions, with h₂o) in geoscience?
29. Could you share the origin time of the M 6.5 - Carlsberg Ridge?
30. Write a regular expression to extract the numbers from the given string. This task evaluates the numbers 48 and 101
31. What is relational databaseA relational database is a (most commonly digital) database based on the relational model of data, as proposed by E. F. Codd in 1970. A system used to maintain relational databases is a relational database management system (RDBMS). Many relational database systems are equipped

with the option of using SQL (Structured Query Language) for querying and updating the database.

32. Does subfamily bathymetrinae a. h. clark fall under the broader concept of family antedonidae norman in geoscience?
33. Is international standard system a narrower category or subdiscipline within the national geologic map database project-usgs and aasg in geoscience?
34. 'It is simply not possible to find a true balance between biodiversity and sustainable economic development in savanna grasslands. Economic development will always come at the expense of biodiversity.' To what extent do you agree with this view?
35. What are some narrower categories or subdisciplines within family cyzicidae stebbing?
36. Could you clarify the timescale of the Bicentenaria argentina for me?
37. Based on the following paragraph on the current use of obsidian, what's the difference between obsidian scalpels and steel scalpels? Obsidian can be used to make extremely sharp knives, and obsidian blades are a type of glass knife made using naturally occurring obsidian instead of manufactured glass. Obsidian is used by some surgeons[who?][example needed] for scalpel blades, although this is not approved by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for use on humans. Well-crafted obsidian blades, like any glass knife, can have a cutting edge many times sharper than high-quality steel surgical scalpels: the cutting edge of the blade is only about three nanometers thick. All metal knives have a jagged, irregular blade when viewed under a strong enough microscope; however, obsidian blades are still smooth, even when examined under an electron microscope. One study found that obsidian incisions produced fewer inflammatory cells and less granulation tissue in a group of rats after seven days but the differences disappeared after twenty-one days. Don Crabtree has produced surgical obsidian blades and written articles on the subject. Obsidian scalpels may currently[when?] be purchased[by whom?] for surgical use on research animals.
38. Make a listing of the top 5 most successful retail stores in the world.
39. You are given a question on high school microeconomics. You are also given 4 answer options (associated with "A", "B", "C", "D"), out of which only one is correct. You need to answer the question by selecting the correct option. You should only answer with the choice letter, not the whole answer. Which of the following tax systems is designed to redistribute income from the wealthy to the

- poor? Choose from: A. A progressive tax system B. A regressive tax system C. A proportional tax system D. An excise tax system The answer is:
40. Any comments about these Trace Fossils?
 41. Based on the sedimentary structures like flaser bedding and intermingling of marine and terrestrial sediments, these traces are probably from tidal flats. Fellow geologists I appreciate your comments in advance. A word file and Also the photos are attached below. Regards
 42. In the realm of Earth sciences, which discipline is most closely linked to the term 'calina'? Choose from: A. Geology B. Oceanography C. Geophysics D. Meteorology E. Hydrology F. Climatology G. Geochemistry H. Geography I. Geodesy The answer is:
 43. I'd like to know the related paper of the Lemmleinite-Ba.
 44. What are some specific examples of ocean-floor metamorphism within geoscience?
 45. Can you provide a synonym for the word 'short wavelength infrared'?
 46. Can you tell me the sample description of the Muirite?
 47. What is the benefit of repeating aquifer pumping tests with higher pumping rates? I have a series of single-well, continuous pump test and recovery data with pump discharge rates that range between 2 and 4.2 l/s. The draw-down of these tests range between 1.05 to 1.68 m and were conducted over a period of 20 hours. What would be the benefit, if any, of repeating these tests at a higher pumping rate?
 48. What are few things that could impact your EV range on long trips
 49. Who is Laika and why is she famous? Laika was a Soviet space dog who was one of the first animals in space and the first to orbit the Earth. A stray mongrel from the streets of Moscow, she flew aboard the Sputnik 2 spacecraft, launched into low orbit on 3 November 1957. As the technology to de-orbit had not yet been developed, Laika's survival was never expected. She died of overheating hours into the flight, on the craft's fourth orbit. Little was known about the effects of spaceflight on living creatures at the time of Laika's mission, and animal flights were viewed by engineers as a necessary precursor to human missions. The experiment, which monitored Laika's vital signs, aimed to prove that a living organism could survive being launched into orbit and continue to function under conditions of weakened gravity and increased radiation, providing scientists with some of the first data on the biological effects of spaceflight. Laika died within hours from overheating, possibly caused by a failure of the central R-7 sustainer to separate from the payload. The true cause and time of her death were not

made public until 2002; instead, it was widely reported that she died when her oxygen ran out on day six or, as the Soviet government initially claimed, she was euthanised prior to oxygen depletion. In 2008, a small monument to Laika depicting her standing atop a rocket was unveiled near the military research facility in Moscow that prepared her flight. She also appears on the Monument to the Conquerors of Space in Moscow.

50. What are the mathematical methods used in the analysis and interpretation of seismic attenuation and dispersion for subsurface characterization?

A.2 Supervised Fine-Tuning

A.2.1 Learning Rate

This section presents the absolute loss values obtained during a small-scale fine-tuning experiment utilizing 200 prompts with various learning rates. Additionally, the figures depicting the loss development at different learning rates can be found. Two different approaches to finding the best learning rates are roughly explained. The first Subsection A.2.1, deals with a initial approach that did not yield in helpful results and the second Subsection A.2.1 provides the data for the approach actually used in determining the learning rate.

Approach: Loss over Learning Rate

In this subsection, an initial attempt to define best the learning rate is described. The **training** losses at the end of the small-scale SFTs across different learning rates, as shown in Table A.1, served as basis. For visualizing the loss development at varying learning rates, Figure A.1 displays the plot of the final losses over their learning rates. To better understand the loss trend, a polynomial curve of degree 4 was fitted to these data points.

Initially, the idea was to identify the point of the steepest slope. However, it turned out that the polynomial function $2.225 \times 10^5 x^4 - 4.303 \times 10^4 x^3 + 2921 x^2 - 83.01 x + 2.596$ had the steepest slope for a negative learning rate. Consequently, this methodology was not able to provide any helpful information in determining the optimal learning rate.

Approach: Loss over time per learning rate

For this approach, the **evaluation** loss at 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% progress of the small-scale FT was measured (see Table A.2), and the corresponding values were plotted (see Figure A.2). A straight line was then fitted through these points for every learning rate. The learning rate associated with the greatest negative slope was considered the most promising, as a large and consistent decrease in loss potentially indicates effective learning.

The range of tested learning rates was iteratively extended, i.e. in the first and second runs the largest learning rates showed the best performance, which is why the learning

lr	train loss	lr	train loss
1e-3	2.525	5e-3	2.223
1e-4	2.594	6e-3	2.177
1e-5	2.597	7e-3	2.134
2e-3	2.433	8e-3	2.095
2e-4	2.590	9e-3	2.068
2e-5	2.597	0.01	2.037
3e-3	2.347	0.03	1.794
3e-4	2.585	0.05	1.714
3e-5	2.596	0.07	1.703
4e-3	2.280	0.09	2.008
4e-4	2.578		
4e-5	2.596		

Table A.1: Overall training loss results for testing different learning rates on a sample of 200 prompts for SFT

rates were increased until a decrease in performance was visible in the plots (third run).

A.2.2 Experimental Results for human alignment with a learning rate of 2e-04

Input prompt	Without SFT	With SFT
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<p>What terms in this passage have a connection to earth science? The passage: The music was composed by Mani Sharma and released by Aditya Music. Best First Film of a Director - V. V. Vinayak; Best Editor - Gowtham Raju; Special Jury Award - Jr. NTR; Best Lyricist - Chandrabose.</p>	<p>There are no terms in the passage that have a connection to earth science. The passage is related to the awards and recognition given to individuals in the field of filmmaking, and does not mention any geoscientific concepts or terminology.</p>	<p>1. Music 2. Composer 3. Director 4. Editor 5. Lyricist 6. Film 7. Director 8. Editor 9. Lyricist 10. Film 11. Music 12. Composer 13. Director 14. Editor 15. Lyricist [...] 96. Composer 97</p>
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<p>Identify which instrument is string or percussion: Kenong, Zeze</p>	<p>Hello! I'd be happy to help with your questions about geoscience. However, I'm a large language model, I don't have the ability to identify instruments as string or percussion. The terms "Kenong" and "Zeze" do not appear to be geoscience-related, and I couldn't find any information about them in my databases.</p>	<p>Zeze is string, Kenong is percussion. Please answer the questions related to geoscience. You are given a question on high school geography. You need to answer the question by selecting from the answer options (A) List three ways in which the United States is unique among the world's nations. Choose from: A. The United States is the only nation that has a president. B. [...] The answer is:</p>
--	---	--

Table A.3: Examples of generated outputs before SFT and after SFT with a learning rate of 2e-04

Figure A.1: The light blue dots represent the overall train loss measured over the learning rate, whereas the dark blue dot shows the recommended lr by Pytorch [100], i.e. $2e-4$. A polynomial of degree 4 is fitted through the points to best depict the loss development.

A.2.3 Experimental Results for human alignment with a learning rate of $2e-05$

	Input prompt	Without SFT	With SFT
better with SFT	Is it possible for who has shear Modulus and damping ratio (values) for Shales and Sandstone to share it? [...]	[...] Shear modulus: Shear modulus is a measure of the stiffness of a rock and is typically expressed in units of Pa or GPa. For shales, the shear modulus can range from around 100 to 1000 MPa, depending on the type of shale and the specific conditions of the rock (e.g., Kulander et al., 1993; Gholami et al., 2013).	I can provide you with some general information about the shear modulus and damping ratio of shales and sandstones. However, I cannot share specific values for these parameters as they can vary widely depending on the specific type of rock, its mineral composition, and other factors. [...]

equal	Can Oceanic Spreading Ridges be swallowed by a subduction zone? [...]	Middle Yes, it is possible for a middle oceanic ridge to be swallowed by a subduction zone. This process is known as "ridge subduction" [...]	Yes, it is possible for a middle oceanic spreading ridge to be consumed by a subduction zone. This process is known as "ridge-pushed subduction" [...]
better with-out SFT	Please tell me the related paper of the Armellinoite-(Ce).	Armillinoite-(Ce) is a rare mineral that is not well studied, and there may not be many papers specifically dedicated to it. However, I can suggest a few resources that may be helpful: 1. Mindat.org: [...]	[...] The related papers of Armellinoite-(Ce) are: 1. "Armillinoite-(Ce): A new member of the Armellinoite group" by A. K. S. Chauhan, et al. (2017) in the Journal of Mineralogy. This paper describes the discovery of Armellinoite-(Ce) and its crystal structure, chemical composition, and optical properties. [...]

Table A.4: Examples of generated outputs before SFT and after SFT with a learning rate of 2e-05

A.2.4 Hyperparameter for alignment with humans

```
# Settings chosen as here: https://github.com/pytorch/torchtune/blob/main/recipes/configs/llama2/13B\_lora.yaml
training_arguments = TrainingArguments(
    output_dir="Model/SFT_for_expert_alignment",
    num_train_epochs=1,
    per_device_train_batch_size=2,
    per_device_eval_batch_size=2,
    gradient_accumulation_steps=16,
    optim="paged_adamw_32bit",
```

Learning Rate	25%	50%	75%	100%
0.001	2.622	2.587	2.482	2.295
0.0001	2.624	2.623	2.620	2.612
0.00001	2.626	2.625	2.624	2.624
0.002	2.615	2.526	2.288	1.991
0.0002	2.624	2.621	2.612	2.593
0.00002	2.625	2.625	2.624	2.624
0.003	2.606	2.444	2.096	1.797
0.0003	2.624	2.619	2.601	2.567
0.00003	2.625	2.625	2.624	2.623
0.004	2.599	2.366	1.970	1.657
0.0004	2.624	2.615	2.589	2.533
0.00004	2.625	2.625	2.624	2.622
0.005	2.589	2.283	1.868	1.571
0.006	2.580	2.215	1.790	1.496
0.007	2.571	2.147	1.721	1.440
0.008	2.559	2.081	1.658	1.383
0.009	2.547	2.033	1.621	1.357

Table A.2: Evaluation loss results after each quarter of SFT on a sample of 200 prompts for different learning rates

```

save_strategy="epoch",
learning_rate=0.00002,
lr_scheduler_type="cosine",
warmup_ratio=0.03,
warmup_steps=50,
logging_strategy="steps",
logging_steps=10,
evaluation_strategy="steps",
eval_steps=0.03,
save_safetensors=True,
seed=42,
bf16=True,
weight_decay=0.01,
)

peft_config = LoraConfig(

```


(a) First test: twelve lrs between $1e-05$ and $4e-03$

(b) Second test: $4e-03$, $5e-03$, $6e-03$, $7e-03$, $8e-03$, $9e-03$

(c) Third test: 0.01 , 0.03 , 0.05 , 0.07

(d) All learning rates

Figure A.2: For each learning rate tested, the development of the evaluation loss is plotted over the steps of the training. For each lr, a straight line is fitted through the points. The line for a lr of 0.01 showed the overall steepest slope.

```

r=8,
lora_alpha=16,
lora_dropout=0.05,
target_modules=["q_proj", "v_proj", "k_proj", "
                o_proj", "up_proj", "down_proj", "gate_proj"
                , "lm_head"],
bias="none",
task_type="CAUSAL_LM",
)

```

A.3 Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback

A.3.1 Hyperparameter for reward model training

```
peft_config = LoraConfig(  
    r=8,  
    lora_alpha=16,  
    lora_dropout=0.05,  
    task_type=TaskType.SEQ_CLS,  
)  
  
training_arguments = TrainingArguments(  
    output_dir=f"{DIR}Training_Outputs",  
    num_train_epochs=1,  
    per_device_train_batch_size=2,  
    per_device_eval_batch_size=2,  
    gradient_accumulation_steps=32,  
    optim="paged_adamw_32bit",  
    learning_rate=0.0003,  
    weight_decay=0.01,  
    lr_scheduler_type="cosine",  
    save_strategy="epoch",  
    logging_strategy="steps",  
    logging_steps=5,  
    evaluation_strategy="steps",  
    eval_steps=1,  
    eval_accumulation_steps=5,  
    seed=42,  
    bf16=True,  
    gradient_checkpointing=True,  
    remove_unused_columns=False  
)
```

A.3.2 Hyperparameter and generation arguments for policy training

```

ppo_config = PPOConfig(
    batch_size=4,
    mini_batch_size=4,
    gradient_accumulation_steps=1,
    ppo_epochs=1,
    model_name=MODEL_PATH,
    learning_rate=0.000002,
    remove_unused_columns=False,
    seed=42,
    use_score_scaling=True,
    use_score_norm=True,
    score_clip=0.5,
    optimize_device_cache=True,
    optimize_cuda_cache=True,
)

generation_kwargs = {
    "top_p": 1.0,
    "top_k": 0.0,
    "max_new_tokens": 256,
    "eos_token_id": 50256,
    "pad_token_id": 50256,
    "do_sample": True,
}

```

A.3.3 Examples of generated outputs after SFT and after RLHF

Type	Prompt	Answer Model	Reference Model	Answer Policy Model
------	--------	--------------	-----------------	---------------------

mc	Which of the following maps would likely have the largest scale? A. A map of a country B. A map of a Region C. A map of the world D. A map of a city E. A map of weather Patterns	#1: A map of a country #2: A map of a region #3: A map of the world #4: A map of a city #5: A map of weather patterns The answer is #1: A map of a country.	#D. A map of a city
fitb	Main types of grain debris in endogenous sedimentary rocks	#Common clay minerals:	#1: #2: #3: #4: #5: #6: #7: #8: #9: #10: #11: #12: #13: #14: #15: #16: #17: #18: #19: #20: #21: #22: #23: #24: #25: #26: #27: #28: #29: #30: #31: #32: #33: #34: #35: #36: #37: #38:
disc	The Mystery of Earth's Lead Isotopes	#The Mystery of Earth's Lead Isotopes The lead isotopes of Earth are a mystery that has puzzled scientists for decades. The lead isotopes of Earth are a mystery that has puzzled scientists for decades. [...]	#The #Mystery #of #Earths #Lead #Isotopes
noun	sedimentary facies	# Sedimentary facies: A facies is a set of sedimentary rocks that are deposited in a specific environment.	# Sedimentary facies: A facies is a rock unit that is part of a sedimentary basin.

qa	Please answer the following question: 40. Joints	#40: Joints
tf	Mylonite is a rock formed by dynamic metamorphism	#True.

Table A.5: Examples of generated outputs after SFT and after RLHF for each type of task in the evaluation data

A.4 Evaluation

A.4.1 Overview of human evaluation for closed tasks

	Language use		Task suitability		Content quality	
	Grammatical Correctness	Repetition	Task Answering	Additional Information	Hallucination Detection	Content Correctness
Multiple Choice						
Base	20	20	14	18	4	4
SFT	20	20	20	2	19	3
RLHF	20	19	19	5	17	5
True-False						
Base	20	19	20	20	9	12
SFT	18	19	20	5	15	10
RLHF	17	16	20	10	16	12

Table A.6: Overview of the results of the human evaluation for closed tasks. The maximum value that could have been reached by a model per aspect is 20.

A.4.2 Overview of human evaluation for open tasks

A.4.3 Example: Output generated for discussion questions

Base model:

#1: Advanced prediction of geological disasters in underground engineering or underground mining

As a helpful and respectful assistant, I would like to point out that the term "geological disasters" is quite broad and can encompass a wide range of events, including natural hazards and human-induced risks. To provide a more accurate and helpful response, I would suggest rephrasing the question to focus on a specific aspect of geological disasters, such as predicting rockfalls, landslides, or subsidence in underground engineering or mining.

Regarding the prediction of geological disasters, it is important to note that while advances in technology and data analysis have improved our ability to forecast and

	Language use		Task suitability		Content quality	
	Grammatical	Repetition	Task An-	Domain	Hallucination	Content
	Correct-		swering	exper-	Detection	Correct-
	ness			tise		ness
	Completion					
Base	40	40	40	37	15	16
SFT	34	24	28	20	23	10
RLHF	26	24	18	10	28	4
	Definition					
Base	40	40	38	40	26	32
SFT	40	38	34	34	38	32
RLHF	38	32	28	24	34	21
	QA					
Base	40	40	34	34	13	13
SFT	40	32	30	25	22	13
RLHF	40	36	32	30	19	15
	Discussion					
Base	40	40	36	36	23	25
SFT	37	31	28	27	31	25
RLHF	36	31	27	26	30	22

Table A.7: Overview of the results of the human evaluation for open tasks. The maximum value that could have been reached by a model per aspect is 40.

prepare for such events, predicting the exact timing and location of a disaster is often difficult or impossible. However, by analyzing geological data, monitoring changes in the ground, and using machine learning algorithms, experts can identify patterns and trends that can help anticipate potential risks and inform mitigation strategies.

Some of the advanced techniques used in predicting geological disasters include:

1. **Geophysical monitoring:** This involves using sensors and other instruments to measure ground deformation, seismic activity, and other geophysical parameters that can indicate the likelihood of a geological disaster.
2. **Geochemical analysis:** This involves analyzing the chemical composition of rocks and soil to identify signs of instability or potential hazards.
3. **Remote sensing:** This involves using satellite and aerial imagery to identify changes in the ground surface and subsurface features that may indicate the presence

of a geological disaster.

4. **Machine learning:** This involves using algorithms to analyze large datasets of geological and environmental information to identify patterns and trends that can help predict the likelihood of a geological disaster.

It is important to note that while these advanced techniques can help predict geological disasters, they are not foolproof and should be used in conjunction with other methods, such as on-site inspections and expert judgment, to ensure the most accurate and comprehensive assessment of risk. Additionally, it is important to consider the ethical and social implications of predicting geological disasters, as well as the potential consequences of such predictions for affected communities.

SFT model:

#1: Advanced prediction of geological disasters in underground engineering or underground mining

Advanced prediction of geological disasters in underground engineering or underground mining is a crucial aspect of ensuring the safety of workers and the surrounding environment. Geological disasters such as rockfalls, landslides, and subsidence can cause significant damage and loss of life. To predict these disasters, geologists and engineers use advanced techniques such as remote sensing, geophysical surveys, and numerical modeling. These techniques allow for the identification of potential hazards and the development of early warning systems. Additionally, advanced prediction can help to identify areas of high risk and inform the design of structures and infrastructure to mitigate the effects of geological disasters.

Antiplagiatserklärung

Ich erkläre hiermit, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit selbständig verfasst habe, dass ich keine anderen als die angegebenen Hilfsmittel und Quellen benutzt habe, dass ich alle wörtlich oder sinngemäß aus anderen Werken übernommenen Aussagen als solche gekennzeichnet habe, dass die Arbeit weder vollständig noch in wesentlichen Teilen Gegenstand eines anderen Prüfungsverfahrens gewesen ist, dass ich die Arbeit weder vollständig noch in wesentlichen Teilen bereits veröffentlicht habe, dass das in Dateiform eingereichte Exemplar mit dem eingereichten gebundenen Exemplar übereinstimmt.

Tübingen, July 30, 2024

A handwritten signature in black ink, reading "A. Skupch". The signature is written in a cursive style with a large initial "A" and a stylized "Skupch".

Annica Skupch